

R&I PEERS

Pilot experiences for improving Gender Equality in research organisations

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D5.1 - Final report on GEPs impact progress

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LIST OF CONTENTS

1. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS	5
2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	6
3. INTRODUCTION	7
4. Evaluation of impacts in the Università degli Studi di Salerno (UNISA)	7
4.1 Description of the Università degli Studi di Salerno (UNISA)	7
4.2 Analysis of the State indicators in UNISA.....	8
4.3 Analysis of the Process indicators in UNISA.....	11
5. Evaluation of impacts in Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute - CNTI	13
5.1 Description of CNTI.....	13
5.2 Analysis of the State indicators in CNTI	13
5.3 Analysis of the Process indicators in CNTI	16
6. Evaluation of impacts in CIC nanoGUNE.....	18
6.1 Description of Centro de Investigacion Cooperativa en Nanociencias - CIC nanoGUNE	18
6.2 Analysis of the State indicators CIC nanoGUNE	18
6.3 Analysis of the Process indicators in CIC nanoGUNE	21
7. Evaluation of impacts in Galilee Research Institute Ltd - MIGAL	24
7.1 Description of MIGAL	24
7.2 Analysis of the State indicators in MIGAL	24
7.3 Analysis of the Process indicators in MIGAL	27
8. Evaluation of impacts in Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts - ZRC SAZU	29
8.1 Description of ZRC SAZU	29
8.2 Analysis of the State indicators	29
8.3 Analysis of the Process indicators.....	32
9. Evaluation of impacts in the National agency for the promotion of scientific research - ANPR	34
9.1 Description of ANPR	34
9.2 Analysis of the State indicators in ANPR.....	34
9.3 Analysis of the Process indicators of ANPR.....	36
10. Evaluation of impacts in the General Secretariat for Family Policy and Gender Equality - GSFPGE ...	38
10.1 Description of GSFPGE.....	38
10.2 Analysis of the State indicators of GSFPGE	38

10.3 Analysis of the Process indicators of GSFPGE	40
11. CONCLUSION	42
12. BIBLIOGRAPHY AND SITOGRAPHY	43
Appendix I - Survey from the pilot organisations - Objective data collection (State indicators)	44
Appendix II – Data from GEPs.....	79

1. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
ANPR	National agency for the promotion of scientific research
CUG	Comitato Unico di Garanzia (National Committees for equal opportunities in English)
EC	European Commission
GEC	Gender Equality Committee
GE	Gender Equality
GSFPGE	General Secretariat for Family Policy and Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
H2020	Horizon 2020
CIC nanoGUNE	Asociacion - Centro de Investigacion Cooperativa en Nanociencias
CNTI	Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
MIGAL	Galilee Research Institute Ltd
PO	Project Officer
PC	Project Coordinator
Piloting partner	The R&I-PEERS partner who designed and implemented the GEP
RPO	Research performing organisation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
UNISA/OGEPO	Università degli Studi di Salerno/ Observatory for the Gender Studies and Equal Opportunity
ZRC SAZU	Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the final progress of the 7 GEPs proposed within the R&I PEERS Project (GA 788171) by the piloting partners of the Mediterranean area (UNISA, CNTI, CIC nanoGUNE, MIGAL, ZRC SAZU, ANPR, GSFPGE). It evolves the analysis already produced with the “D4.5 - Mid-term Report on GEPs impact progress”.

This deliverable contains a qualitative analysis on the basis of:

- data related to 2021 in each organisation for observing their changes after the GEPs activities) with the survey defined from the pilot organisations (see Appendix I - Survey from the pilot organisations - Objective data collection),
- data returning a picture of the GEPs implementation according to the process indicators collected to analyse the success of strategies implemented within each GEP.

The result of the analysis will facilitate each organisation to continue the implementation and improve the efficacy of the GEP also after the project ends.

Section 3 describes the data collection approach used for process and state indicators, while section 4 provides impact analysis.

3. INTRODUCTION

This section describes the data collection approach used for process and state indicators, while section 4 describes a first impact analysis of actions implemented in each GEP.

R&I-PEERS has defined and is implementing seven GEPs within UNISA, CNTI, CIC nanoGUNE, MIGAL, ZRC SAZU, ANPR, GSFPGE. These GEPs were firstly “formally adopted by the leading administrative bodies in each institution between December 2018 and April 2019” and then evolved, as explained in the deliverable “D4.4 – Final GEPs definition improvement”. This section is organised into sub-sections, one per each piloting partner, discussing the impacts of GEPs. Each sub-section contains the results of the analysis of data that each piloting organisation collected from:

- 1) the Top-down survey (Analysis of objective data within the piloting organisations) that provides the State values of indicators that return the Institutionalisation of Gender Equality in each organisation.
We collected data related to 2021 (that were available from the different organisations in 2022). We compare them to the data related to 2018 for the ex-ante (baseline).
- 2) data collected by each piloting organisation containing values of Process indicators that return a picture of the implementation of the GEPs according to the thresholds values were identified for each one of the indicators within the GEPs definition (see Appendix II).

The next sections describe results from the seven piloting organisations.

4. Evaluation of impacts in the Università degli Studi di Salerno (UNISA)

In the following sub-sections, we give a short reminder describing the University of Salerno. Then, we analyse data from the State indicators (see Appendix I) and the Process indicators (see Appendix II).

4.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI SALERNO (UNISA)

The Università degli Studi di Salerno (<https://www.unisa.it/>) is located in Fisciano (Salerno) and has more than 40,000 students. It is the largest university in the South of peninsular Italy, with its 17 Departments (humanistic and STEM). Particularly sensitive to gender issues, the university has already carried out some actions in the field of Gender Equality, such as courses on women's history and gender studies for students, thanks to the commitment of the Observatory for Gender studies and Equal Opportunity (OGEPO), which was established in 2011. “The mission of the University of Salerno is to carry out research and educational programmes, developing links with the surrounding area while respecting the environment, with the aim of creating, enriching and, at the same time, offering a scientific, cultural heritage to students, enterprises, institutions and in general to the whole community.

Core Values

- Secularism, pluralism, and independence from any ideological, political, and economic orientation;
- Freedom of thought, in research and teaching;

- Equal educational and professional opportunities;
- Sustainable growth and development of the local area;
- Safeguarding the right to health care;
- Protection of the environment” (<https://web.unisa.it/en/university/mission>).

4.2 ANALYSIS OF THE STATE INDICATORS IN UNISA

This section describes the analysis of data collected in UNISA related to taking a picture of the state of Gender Equality in the organisation (see Appendix I) at the end of 2021 (last official data from the administration provided at the end of each year). In particular, this picture returns data provided by the organisation on the Staff members with roles of responsibility per gender, the statistics of employers' position in the organisation per gender and information about specific initiatives, structures and policies of the organisation concerning Gender Equality, such as the existence of a Gender Equality board, the amount of a dedicated budget for Gender Equality actions, the existence of the practice that ensures a gender-balanced composition for the staff recruitment committees, the existence of practices that ensure a work-life balance. In particular, this section provides an analysis of the evolution of these data in the time frame 2018-2021.

Comparing data collected in 2018 (at the beginning of the project) with data provided by the organisation and related to 2021 (the last official data from the administration before the R&I-Peers project ends), we observe that:

- no significant changes characterise the Number of Management and decision-making per gender and per level from 2018 to 2021, even if there was a little improvement in the Number of females with respect to the Number of males for people with high levels of responsibilities for management and decision-making positions (including for example Rector, General Manager, Presidents of the didactic councils, Directors of Departments, Rector's Delegates, Vice-Rector, Academic Senate, Board of Governors, Scientific Advisory Board, other) and people with a medium level of responsibility for management and decision-making positions (includes Responsible for a specific office of the organisation, senior executives, heads office, Rector contacts, President of Appennino, President of the National Committee for equal opportunities - in Italian “Comitato Unico di Garanzia / CUG”-, PhD coordinators, President of the foundation, College of auditors, Didactic committee, other).

- an increasing number of females and decreasing number of males characterises the medium level of the category of people with a high level of responsibilities for employers that do not occupy research positions (neither professors nor researchers) from 2018 to 2021, reaching a balance for it. The high level and the initial level have small changes

- the number of professors and researchers per gender changed. There was an improvement of females and males considering full professors (level A), but the % did not change in a significant way. Also the number of females and males professors (level B) was improved, and in this case the percentage of females changes from 39% in 2018 to 46% in 2021, while the % of males changes from 61% in 2018 to 54% in 2021. The number of professors in level D changed improving more the number of males, even if it remains balanced per gender.

- Even if the number of fellows (females and males both decreased) changed from 2018 to 2021 with a small decrease in the number of both, females and males, the gender balance remains substantially unchanged from 2018 to 2021 (the % for females changed from 57,5% in 2018 to 57% in 2021, and males from 42,5% of 2018 to 43% of 2021. The Number of Ph.D. students (Females and Males) was improved from 2018 to 2021, but its balance is unchanged, and it is confirmed the greater number of females than males in this starting position of the research career.

- % of people in Boards of the organisation per gender is an important indicator of the gender balance in the management and decisional positions in the organisation, and it does not show significant changes with values from 32% in 2018 for females to 33% in 2021 and, 68% of males in 2018 and 67% in 2021.

- The % of projects coordinators/project managers per gender indicates that during 2018 the projects' coordinators in UNISA were 31% females and 69% males and it did not change in 2021

- The University of Salerno did not appoint a Board for Gender Equality, as UNISA already has the OGEPO that promotes gender in research and curricula and the CUG that promotes gender and wellbeing in the workplace.
- In 2018 UNISA awarded a budget of 68000,00 Euros for Gender Equality actions, and this budget was reduced to 20000,00 in 2021. However, it was obtained to open a position for a researcher on Gender Equality.
- There are no internal rules for a balanced Staff recruitment committee, as this is compulsory for Italian national law.

Work-life balance tools are available and used in UNISA. In particular, the personnel can access smart-working measures, can require a parental leave, maternity but also part-time working hours, leave due to a child's illness, and a paid leave for disabled people (art. 42 dlgs 151/2001) and law 104). This was already possible in 2018, and the experience of COVID19 reinforced the use of smart working.

4.3 ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS INDICATORS IN UNISA

The strategies and actions of the GEP within UNISA, as planned and evolved according to the suggestions emerging during the project life, are explained in the deliverable "D4.4 - Final GEPs definition improvement" and they are listed in the table contained in Appendix II, that also contains the indicators and thresholds related to each strategy. The strategies were classified according to the five areas identified in the "Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans" [2]. Analysing the strategies carried out within the GEP (see the appendix II), we observed that they are Very satisfactory (according to the established thresholds). The situation for UNISA is summarised in the figure that follows with a scorecard representation. All the Unsatisfactory or Satisfactory strategies (but do not reach the maximum level of satisfaction) were influenced by the crisis produced by COVID19 pandemic. For example, the "Workshops for students, PhD students and researchers with national and international experts about the inclusion of a gender perspective in research projects and in curricula", encountered difficulties in engaging in 2020 and 2021 the number of participants planned at the beginning.

The organisation of "training initiatives on the elimination of gender-based violence (e.g. trainings, contest; theatrical performances, etc.)" (even if Satisfactory in number) was difficult also because many cultural activities were reduced due to the crisis. The same phenomenon interested the "establishing a networks with stakeholders and enterprises on a national and regional level". The university also delayed some other activities, such as "Design and implementation of an ad hoc study area for children (6-14 years) of UNISA's students and employees; Identification of suitable spaces for the creation of a playroom for children", as it was not a priority in that phase.

D5.1 - Final report on GEPs impact progress

Dissemination level – PU

GEP Area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	
Gep Strategy	Questionnaire for researchers and professors on gender perspective in research and teaching, with particular attention to STEM disciplines	
Level of satisfaction x N of completed questionnaires	NA as the strategy is running	
Gep Strategy	Workshops for students, PhD students and researchers with national and international experts about the inclusion of a gender perspective in research projects and in curricula	
Level of satisfaction x N of participants 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants 2021		
Gep Strategy	Introduction of an interdisciplinary teaching on GE in the educational offering of all UNISA PhD courses	
Level of satisfaction x N of participants		
Gep Strategy	Activation of Master and Postgraduate courses on GE and diversity management	
Level of satisfaction for the activation		
Gep Strategy	Establishment, through an open tender, for a position as a researcher with a temporary employment relationship (RTDA) specialised in gender issues	
Level of satisfaction x N of positions announced		
Gep Strategy	Promotion of courses on gender equality as free choice courses among students of all disciplines.	
Level of satisfaction x N of flyers and messages		
Gep Strategy	Fundraising activities for financing grants for research projects and post-doc projects that include a gender dimension; (also with the support of funds and resources outside UNISA); financing awards for MA thesis developed with a gender perspective.	
Level of satisfaction x N of grants given		
GEP Area	Work-life balance and organisational culture	
Gep Strategy	Creation of ad hoc rooms/ nurseries, as dedicated spaces for breastfeeding, milk pumping, diaper changing. Identification of spaces within the bathrooms for installing baby-changing stations.	
Level of satisfaction x N of rooms/spaces		
Gep Strategy	Design and implementation of an ad hoc study area for children (6-14 years) of UNISA's students and employees; identification of suitable spaces for the creation of a playground for children.	
Level of satisfaction when strategy done		
Gep Strategy	Strengthening the existing initiative Summer Camp for the children of UNISA employees, ensuring the canteen service and opening hours throughout the parents' working day.	
Implements Actions	This activity was interrupted due to Covid outbreak. Summer camps were organised again in 2022. It is a Multidisciplinary Sports Activity Program	
Level of satisfaction when strategy done		
Gep Strategy	Identification of flexible working methods more congenial to the conciliation of time: such as smart-working and teleworking	
Level of satisfaction when strategy done		
Gep Strategy	Incentives aimed at supporting young scholars with children in tow during research periods abroad	
Level of satisfaction x Number of fundraising actions	NA	
Gep Strategy	Services for the promotion of the well-being of UNISA's employees	
Level of satisfaction when strategy done		
Gep Strategy	Revision of the place-names of the two Campuses of UNISA, Fisciano and Baronissi, (streets, squares, areas) on a gender-perspective	
Level of satisfaction x revision completed		
Gep Strategy	Improvement of Gender Budgeting	
Level of satisfaction x publication of 2nd Gender budgeting		
Gep Strategy	Support to the applicant student in the alias activation procedure and during the management of the alias career	
Level of satisfaction x n of alias careers followed		
Gep Strategy	Analysis of national legislation and screening of a selection of institutional documents and communications from a gender perspective (for the introduction of the correct use of gender-neutral language)	
Level of satisfaction when strategy done		
GEP Area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	
Gep Strategy	Promotion of the R&I PEERS website on UNISA's official site, OGEPO's website and social pages	
Level of satisfaction when available		
Thresholds	Very satisfactory when available	
Results and Comments	This strategy is Very satisfactory	
Gep Strategy	Questionnaire on equal opportunities for UNISA's personnel	
Level of satisfaction x responses x questionnaire		
Gep Strategy	Involvement of students and PhD students' associations in the main strategic actions of the project aimed at building gender awareness	
Level of satisfaction x N of student associations involved		
Gep Strategy	Guidance session for high-school students to promote GE and studies and job opportunities within the STEM field	
Level of satisfaction x N of sessions organised		
Gep Strategy	Analysis of annual statistical indicators of the career paths of female and male researchers at the beginning of their careers	
Level of satisfaction when available		
GEP Area	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	
Gep Strategy	Awareness-raising activities on the importance of the presence of women in leadership positions, in the decision-making bodies (Academic Senate and the Board of Directors) and in evaluation committees.	
Level of satisfaction x N of activities carried out		
Gep Strategy	Support to female candidates in decision-making-bodies of UNISA, also with the request of the introduction of a quota system.	
Level of satisfaction x N of activities carried out	NA	
GEP Area	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	
Gep Strategy	Strengthening educational and training initiatives on the elimination of gender-based violence (e.g. trainings, contests, theatrical performances, etc.)	
Level of satisfaction x N of activities carried out in 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants in 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of activities carried out in 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants in 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of activities carried out in 2021		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants in 2021		
Gep Strategy	Establishment of a networks with stakeholders and enterprises on a national and regional level	
Level of satisfaction x establishment of a network		

Legenda

Figure: levels of satisfaction with UNISA GEP

5. Evaluation of impacts in Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute - CNTI

In the following sub-sections we provide a short description of the CNTI. Then, we analyse data from the State and Process indicators.

5.1 DESCRIPTION OF CNTI

Cyprus Neuroscience & Technology Institute – CNTI (<http://www.futureworldscenter.org/>) is a research, non-profit, non-governmental, non-partisan independent organisation based in Cyprus, active in programs with future orientation in areas related to human brain-modern technology-social transformation and the repercussions of relevant research for humanity. It is a small organisation. The scope of activities of the organisation involves the application of technology towards social transformation, and bridging literacy, economic, and digital divides.

5.2 ANALYSIS OF THE STATE INDICATORS IN CNTI

This section describes the analysis of data collected in CNTI related to taking a picture of the state of Gender Equality in the organisation (see Appendix I) at the end of 2021 (last official data from the administration provided at the end of each year). In particular, this picture returns data provided by the organisation on the Staff members with roles of responsibility per gender, the statistics of employers' position in the organisation per gender and information about specific initiatives, structures and policies of the organisation concerning Gender Equality, such as the existence of a Gender Equality board, the amount of a dedicated budget for Gender Equality actions, the existence of the practice that ensures a gender-balanced composition for the staff recruitment committees, the existence of practices that ensure a work-life balance. In particular, this section provides an analysis of the evolution of these data in the time frame 2018-2021.

First of all, we need to specify that CNTI reduced its dimensions. This is evident in the data collected from the administration (see Appendix I).

Comparing data collected in 2018 (at the beginning of the project) with data provided by the organisation and related to 2021 (the last official data from the administration before the R&I-Peers project ends) we observe that:

- a small decrease characterises the Number of Management and decision-making per gender and per level from 2018 to 2021, both for females and males with high levels of responsibility for management and decision-making positions and people with a medium level of responsibility for management and decision-making positions. However, the balance by gender is unchanged.

- No changes are observed for males when comparing the Number of employees in your organisation per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers) in 2018 and 2021 respectively for the higher, medium and initial level of responsibility; when considering females, we can see 1 more female in the higher level in 2021, and 1 less female in the medium level; there are no changes in the initial level.

- the number of professors and researchers per gender changed as in 2018, some employees (males) were professors respectively of level A and B. In 2021 no one is a professor.

- When we look at data related to people in the educational process, i.e. the number of research fellows per gender, the total number is the same (3) and unchanged from 2018 to 2022. However, in 2021 fellows are all females.

- % of people in Boards of the organisation per gender was perfectly balanced in 2018, and its composition remained at 50% of females and 50% of males in 2021.

- The % of project coordinators/project managers per gender indicates that during 2018 the project coordinators in CNTI were 60% females and 40% males; in 2021, this % changed with a perfect balance. Indeed, there were 50% of females and 50% of males. However, it is necessary to consider that this situation changed in the context of reduction of employees.

- CNTI appointed the Board for Gender Equality, on the 2nd Jan 2022.
- In 2018 CNTI planned a budget of 10000,00 Euros for Gender Equality actions. In 2021, it was decided to plan the budget based on external projects; moreover, a budget of 500-1000 euros is made available for each action after the GEP Officer requests it.
- Staff recruitment committees' composition in CNTI was balanced per gender already from 2018.
- Work-life balance tools were available in CNTI in 2018 and confirmed in 2021. In particular, these tools are Smart working, Teleworking, flexible working and parental leave.

All data collected per gender in the organisation are categorised by females and males. Data about "Other" are not collected as well as any information on the ethnicity to avoid discrimination.

5.3 ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS INDICATORS IN CNTI

The strategies and actions of the GEP within CNTI, as planned and evolved according to the suggestions emerging during the project life, are explained in the deliverable “D4.4 - Final GEPs definition improvement” and, they are listed in the table contained in Appendix II, that also contains the indicators and thresholds related to each strategy. The strategies were classified according to the five areas identified in the “Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans” [2]. Analysing the strategies carried out within the GEP (see appendix II), we observed that they are Very satisfactory (according to the established thresholds). The situation for CNTI is summarised in the figure that follows with a scorecard representation. All the strategies that are Unsatisfactory, or are Satisfactory (but do not reach the maximum level of satisfaction) were influenced by the reduction of the number of employees in CNTI combined with the crisis produced by the COVID19 pandemic. For example, the “Organization of a national photo competition portraying women in science” was postponed to 2023, due to the COVID19 and economic crisis.

Because of the reduced number of employees in the organisation, small meetings were considered sufficient instead of the “Organization of a yearly workshop to inform employees about the policies on the national and organisational level aimed to improve work-life balance”. This underlines that any crisis can produce profound consequences in small organisations.

GEP Area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
Gep Strategy	Organization of a national photo competition portraying "women in science"
Level of satisfaction x N of photos submitted	
Gep Strategy	Introduction of mechanisms to facilitate leaves for education and research
Level of satisfaction when the strategy is executed	
GEP Area	Work-life balance and organisational culture
Gep Strategy	18 weeks paid parental leave through which the employer will be allowed to work remotely from home for the whole period of the leave
Level of satisfaction x N of employees using it 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of employees using it 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of employees using it 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N of employees using it 2022	NA
GEP Area	Work-life balance and organisational culture
Gep Strategy	The organization will pay the remaining 25% of the maternity leave paid by the Social Insurances (75%)
Level of satisfaction x N of employees using it 2021 (as asked in 2021)	
Gep Strategy	Organization of a yearly workshop to inform employees about the policies on the national and organizational level aimed to improve work-life balance
Level of satisfaction x workshops or small meetings organised 2019	
Level of satisfaction x workshops or small meetings organised 2020	
Level of satisfaction x workshops or small meetings organised 2019	
Level of satisfaction x workshops or small meetings organised 2020	
Gep Strategy	Inclusion of relevant information on national work-life balance related legislation to the FWC's website
Level of satisfaction when the strategy is done	
Gep Strategy	Introduction of the possibility of flexible working hours and remote work
Level of satisfaction x N of employees using it	
Gep Strategy	Review of all FWC's policy papers
Level of satisfaction when the strategy is done	
Gep Strategy	Organization of a seminar to inform employees on the newly implemented policies
Level of satisfaction x N of employees attending	
GEP Area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Gep Strategy	Regular workshops / webinars dedicated to grant and project application writing
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of project proposals writing 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N of project proposals writing 2022	
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees 2022	
Gep Strategy	Regular workshops / webinars dedicated to academic writing
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of academic writing 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N of academic writing 2022	
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees 2022	
Gep Strategy	Organization of a Structured Democratic Dialogue (SDD) Workshop on a national level with youth to identify actions to reduce gender gap among young researchers
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees	
Gep Strategy	Establishment of a procedure for the equal hiring of researchers based on gender
Level of satisfaction when the strategy is established	
GEP Area	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
Gep Strategy	Inclusion of planned measures in FWC's internal policy documents
Level of satisfaction when the strategy is done	
Gep Strategy	Person in charge to provide information, help and advice to employees regarding the available policies
Level of satisfaction when the strategy is done	
Gep Strategy	Establishment of an equal participation of the two genders in CNTI's Board by introducing a specific clause in the policy document
Level of satisfaction when the strategy is established and done	
Gep Strategy	Organization of a yearly workshop on gender bias in decision making bodies
Level of satisfaction 2019	
Level of satisfaction 2020	
Level of satisfaction 2021	
Level of satisfaction 2022	NA

Figure: levels of satisfaction of CNTI GEP

6. Evaluation of impacts in CIC nanoGUNE

In the following subsections, we briefly describe the CIC nanoGUNE - Asociacion - Centro de Investigación Cooperativa en Nanociencias (<https://www.nanogune.eu/>) and then we analyse data coming from the State indicators and the Process indicators.

6.1 DESCRIPTION OF CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA EN NANOCIENCIAS - CIC NANO GUNE

CIC nanoGUNE is a private non-profit making association created in 2006. Its mission is performing world-class nanoscience and nanotechnology research for the competitive growth of the Basque Country. It has medium dimension with employees that are mainly men. This organisation is characterised by a strong presence of people that are temporary staff; therefore in this situation, where the majority of the staff are Men, and many of them are new in the organisation, a clear and transparent GEP is essential to preserve the memory and the awareness of Gender Equality, as well as implementing actions aiming to promote the importance of using gender balance perspective in the recruitment phase, in the strategies for career progression.

6.2 ANALYSIS OF THE STATE INDICATORS CIC NANO GUNE

This section describes the analysis of data collected in CICnanoGUNE related to taking a picture of the state of Gender Equality in the organisation (see Appendix I) at the end of 2021 (the last official data from the administration provided at the end of each year). In particular, this picture returns data provided by the organisation on the Staff members with roles of responsibility per gender, the statistics of employers' position in the organisation per gender and information about specific initiatives, structures and policies of the organisation concerning Gender Equality, such as the existence of a Gender Equality board, the amount of a dedicated budget for Gender Equality actions, the existence of the practice that ensures a gender-balanced composition for the staff recruitment committees, the existence of practices that ensure a work-life balance. In particular, this section provides an analysis of the evolution of these data in the time frame 2018-2021.

Comparing data collected in 2018 (at the beginning of the project) with data provided by the organisation and related to 2021 (the last official data from the administration before the R&I-Peers project ends) we observe that:

- the Number of Management and decision-making per gender and level from 2018 to 2021 changed with 1 more female and 1 more male in the high levels of responsibility for management and decision-making positions and an improvement of 3 females in the medium level of responsibility for management and decision-making positions, while males decreased from 3 in 2018 to 1 in 2021. Data return a more balanced situation per gender in 2021 with respect to 2018.

- No changes are observed for males when comparing the Number of employees in your organisation per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers) in 2018 and 2021 for the higher and medium levels of responsibility, there are 2 males less; the number of males in the initial level of responsibility did not change. When considering females, we can see 1 more female in the higher level in 2021 and 2 more females in the initial level.

- CIC nanoGUNE, differently from universities, does not include roles such as professors, but research professors. According to the OECD Frascati Manual, the career level used in each organisation has been transformed in level A B C. CIC nanoGUNE, when collecting data related to the number of professors and researchers per gender, in level C included research Fellows (Tenure track) plus postdocs and, in level D Ph.Ds. Differently from other organisations in other countries, there are no permanent positions in levels C and D.

The number of professors and researchers per gender changed from 2018 to 2021. CIC nanoGUNE in 2018 had only males (ten) included in the high level (level A) that were increased to 12 in 2021. Level B decreased from 2 males in 2018 to 0 in 2021. There were no females at levels A and B in 2018 and 2021. The number of females and the number of males at level C decreased, but this was stronger for females (from 23 in 2018 to 14 in 2021) than males (from 27 in 2018 to 23 in 2021). A small improvement was observed in the number of females at level D. These changes are very small. Only the observation in the medium period can return a significant picture. It is also important to consider that the organisation works in a STEM sector, and the gender balance is also connected with the balance in the STEM faculties.

- When we look at data related to people in the educational process, i.e. the number of research fellows per gender, the total number of females decreases from 23 in 2018 to 1 in 2021, while the number of males decreases from 27 in 2018 to 2 in 2021. This is also a consequence of the COVID19 pandemic.

- Considering the % of people in Boards of the organisation per gender females were 40% in 2018, and this % was improved to 57% in 2021, while males decreased from 60% in 2018 to 43% in 2021.

- The % of project coordinators/project managers per gender indicates a complete inversion, with 100% of females as project coordinators in 2021.

- CIC nanoGUNE appointed a Board for Gender Equality on 24th May 2018.
- In 2018 CIC nanoGUNE awarded a percentage of its budget of 0,37% for Gender Equality actions. No specific budget has been indicated in 2021
- No gender balance Staff recruitment committees' composition was foreseen in 2018; in 2021 it was introduced the need of gender balance for the Staff recruitment committee's composition in CIC nanoGUNE.
- The Work-life balance tools available in CIC NanoGUNE till 2018 were parental leave, maternity leave and part-time. In 2021 also Teleworking was added (also pushed by COVID19 pandemic).

All data collected per gender in the organisation are categorised by females and males. Data about "Other" are not collected as well as any information on the ethnicity to avoid discrimination.

6.3 ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS INDICATORS IN CIC NANO GUNE

The strategies and actions of the GEP within CIC nanoGUNE, as planned and evolved according to the suggestions emerging during the project life, are explained in the deliverable "D4.4 - Final GEPs definition improvement" and they are listed in the table contained in Appendix II, that also contains the indicators and thresholds related to each strategy. The strategies were classified according to the five areas identified in the "Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans" [2].

Analysing the strategies carried out within the GEP (see appendix II), we observed that they are Very satisfactory (according to the established thresholds). The situation for CIC nanoGUNE is summarised in the figure that follows with a scorecard representation. All the strategies that are Unsatisfactory or

Satisfactory (but do not reach the maximum level of satisfaction) were influenced by the crisis produced by the COVID19, in particular in the year 2020 with the peak of the pandemic.

D5.1 - Final report on GEPs impact progress
Dissemination level – PU

Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	
Gep Strategy	Employee information about the GEP and GEC
Level of satisfaction x N attendee 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N attendee 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N attendee 2022	
Gep Strategy	Employee information about the Gender distribution at CIC nanoGUNE
Level of satisfaction x strategy and activities done in 2020	
Level of satisfaction x strategy and activities done in 2021	
Gep Strategy	Promote the gender-balanced participation of employees in communication actions and dissemination activities.
Level of satisfaction x Gender distribution for the events	
Gep Strategy	Collective/group-based mentoring with focus on gender equality.
Level of satisfaction x Number of events 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Number of events 2020	
Level of satisfaction x Number of events 2021	
Level of satisfaction x Number of events 2022	
Gep Strategy	One-to-one mentoring
Level of satisfaction when mentoring established	
Gep Strategy	Collective/group-based mentoring with focus on gender equality.
Level of satisfaction x organisation of practical seminar in 2019	
Level of satisfaction x organisation of practical seminar in 2022	
Gep Strategy	Sensibilize the employees to gender equality in research.
Level of satisfaction x Number attendees	
Gep Strategy	Promoting gender balance among invited speakers of conferences organized by nanoGUNE.
Level of satisfaction for gender balance among invited speakers in 2022	
Work-life balance and organisational culture	
Gep Strategy	Definition of the responsibilities for implementation and communication of the GEP
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Arrange regular GEP follow-up meetings with the GEC
Level of satisfaction x N of meetings organised 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of meetings organised 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N of meetings organised 2022	
Gep Strategy	Monitor the implementation of the GEP and create a yearly report that includes level of achievement of the foreseen objectives and actions.
Level of satisfaction when report generated 2020	
Level of satisfaction when report generated 2021	
Gep Strategy	Include information about the institutional gender equality policies at the useful documents section of the intranet.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Include the GEP into the next Strategic Plan of CIC nanoGUNE (2021- 2025).
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Include nanoGUNE's commitment towards gender equality in the main documents of the entity (web page, etc.).
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Include gender equality criteria (equality clauses) for the subcontract of external services.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Include the sex variable in all the administrative databases and forms used at nanoGUNE.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Make sure all people-related data are disaggregated by sex at the biennial activity reports.
Level of satisfaction document approved 2021	
Level of satisfaction document approved 2022	
Gep Strategy	Training about inclusive and gender sensitive communication.
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees	
Gep Strategy	Developing nanoGUNE's guidelines for an inclusive use of language at both external and internal communication.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Review nanoGUNE's most relevant communications from a gender inclusive standing point, to verify that the guidelines are being followed.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Develop communication campaigns to enhance women's contributions to research.
Level of satisfaction x N of campaign 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of campaign 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N of campaign 2022	
Gep Strategy	Make policy makers aware of potentially existing discriminatory effects in calls for grants and the need of promoting measures to make all calls inclusive.
Level of satisfaction as no report is necessary	
Gep Strategy	Promote the offer of nursery/child-care facilities to attendants of conferences organized or co-organized by nanoGUNE.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Include in the useful-documents section existing work-life balance support measures available at the Centre.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Revision of documents of Pregnancy Protocol.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Offer the possibility to telework (if possible, depending on the position) if requested and required due to work-life balance issues.
Level of satisfaction x Telework approval and N of employees benefitting	
Gep Strategy	Promote scheduling of meetings during core working hours (9-17).
Level of satisfaction x approval of the strategy and annual e-mail to all employees as reminder	
Gep Strategy	Agreement with nursery nearby for better rates.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gep Strategy	Encourage the mutual support of employees through the setting-up of a "family club" to be coordinated by volunteers and institutionally supported by the center.
Level of satisfaction when done	
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	
Gep Strategy	Training for the management team and hiring panels on equality and non-bias attitudes.
Level of satisfaction x N of trainings 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of trainings 2021	
Gep Strategy	Adapt the hiring protocol to ensure equal opportunities.
Level of satisfaction when adapted	
Gep Strategy	Adapt the hiring protocol to ensure equal opportunities.
Level of satisfaction when a template is done	
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	
Gep Strategy	Training on team management and problem solving considering the gender perspective.
Level of satisfaction x N of attendees	
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	
Gep Strategy	Protect from abuse and gender based or sexual harassment.
Level of satisfaction x establishment of the protocol against sexual harassment	
Gep Strategy	Definition of responsible individuals who will be counsellors in case of sexual and gender-based harassment.
Level of satisfaction x confidential counsellors were identified and email for communicating cases of harassment established	

Figure: levels of satisfaction of CIC nanogune GEP

More in detail, the strategy “Employee information about the GEP and GEC” encountered difficulties in the years 2020 and 2021 due to the impossibility of organising a face-to-face meeting to inform employees during the pandemic period. The same problem occurred in the most critical year (2020) for the strategies “Promote the gender-balanced participation of employees in communication actions and dissemination activities” and “Collective/group-based mentoring with a focus on gender equality”. The pandemic had less impact in 2020 on the strategies “Arrange regular GEP follow-up meetings with the GEC” and “Develop communication campaigns to enhance women’s contributions to research”. The criticalities due to the pandemic have been recovered by extending the project (four months more), intensifying activities in the following years, and doing, when possible, online activities and multiplying their number.

The only strategy of the GEP which, at the end of the project, can be considered unsatisfactory is "Training on team management and problem-solving considering the gender perspective". This strategy, due to the pandemic, had an unsatisfactory impact.

7. Evaluation of impacts in Galilee Research Institute Ltd - MIGAL

In the following sub-sections we provide a short description of the MIGAL organisation. Then, we analyse data from the State and Process indicators.

7.1 DESCRIPTION OF MIGAL

MIGAL – Galilee Research Institute Ltd. (<https://www.migal.org.il/en>) is an internationally recognised and multi-disciplinary research institute specialised in biotechnology and computational sciences, plant science, precision agriculture and environmental sciences as well as food, nutrition and health. It is located in the periphery of Israel, and almost half of its employees are women, and over many Master's degree students. As a leading institute for applied research in the region, MIGAL aims to strengthen and promote scientific innovation and spur economic growth. This organisation, due to the high number of Master Degree students is particularly important to continuously implement actions related to strategies providing opportunities to improve professional and scientific competences in a gender-sensitive perspective .

7.2 ANALYSIS OF THE STATE INDICATORS IN MIGAL

Comparing data collected in 2018 (at the beginning of the project) with data provided by the organisation and related to 2021 (last official data from the administration before the R&I-Peers project ends) we observe that:

- the Number of Management and decision-making positions per gender and per level from 2018 to 2021, changed
improving the number of males, while the number of females decreased both in the higher and in the medium levels; this improved the gender GAP.

- also considering the Number of employees in your organisation per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers) in 2018, they were mainly males (56%). They became 33% in 2021: However, the more balanced composition in 2021 with respect to 2018 resulted from a reduction in the number of females and males in that position. The Number of employees that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers) in the medium responsibility level as well as the initial level are more balanced. The period from 2018 to 2021 shows a reduction both for females and males.

- We observe a similar situation in the number of professors and researchers per level and gender both in 2018 and 2021. Indeed, we find more males than females in level A, with 19% females and 81% males in 2018. In 2021 the balance by gender was improved with 23% of females as professor in level A. A more balanced situation was observed in 2018 in level B, which includes 48% females and 52% males; these values evolved toward a more unbalanced situation with 36% females and 64 % males in level C.

- When we look at data related to people in the educational process, 57% of research fellows were males in 2018, and this % decreased to 53% in 2021, reaching a substantial balance per gender.

- Considering the % of people in Boards of the organisation per gender, females were 12% in 2018, and this % was improved to 19% in 2021, while males decreased from 88% in 2018 to 81% in 2021.

- The % of project coordinators/project managers per gender indicates that 75% are males and 25% are females in 2021.
- MIGAL did not appoint a Board for Gender Equality.
- No gender balance Staff recruitment committees' composition was not available in MIGAL neither in 2018 nor in 2021.
- The Work-life balance tools available in MIGAL till 2018 were smart-working, parental leave and other services, such as Yoga and Pilates classes held during working hours. In 2021 also Teleworking smart-working, parental leave and illness leaves payment of a sick day from the first day, uniform treatment of ill leave without distinction between family member/child have been done available.

All data collected per gender in the organisation are categorised by females and males. Data about "Other" are not collected as well any information on the ethnicity to avoid any discrimination.

7.3 ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS INDICATORS IN MIGAL

The strategies and actions of the GEP within MIGAL, as planned and evolved according to the suggestions emerging during the project life, are explained in the deliverable "D4.4 - Final GEPs definition improvement" and they are listed in the table contained in Appendix II, that also contains the indicators and thresholds related to each strategy.

The monitoring related to the process indicators is mainly Very satisfactory and Satisfactory (see the following figure). However, there is an Unsatisfactory result with respect to the area "Gender balance in leadership and decision-making", In fact, the strategy "Workshop on the importance of promoting and supporting the career of women researches...." has several unsatisfactory indicators, in particular those referred to the years 2019 and 2021. In particular, the unsatisfactory results concern the number of organised workshops and the number of attendees in 2019 and 2021. However, we can observe that the level of satisfaction related to the indicator "N Women researchers promoted in their professional positions" is "Very satisfactory".

Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	
Gep Strategy	English workshops with a special mentor woman for improving speech and professional writing.
Level of satisfaction when a workshop is done	
Gep Strategy	All of MIGAL job publications submitted since the approval of the GEP are written in a gender-sensitive language and as well as in bilingual language.
Level of satisfaction when done in a sistematic way	
Work-life balance and organisational culture	
Gep Strategy	Strengthen the connection among all employees
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2018	
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of Women and Men who attended workshops, 2018	
Level of satisfaction x N of Women and Men who attended workshops, 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of Women and Men who attended workshops, 2020	
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	
Gep Strategy	MIGAL chose a group of young female researchers to promote them and their abilities/skills in a special course designed for them.
Level of satisfaction x N of Women who had evidences of progresses in their abilities and skills.	
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	
Gep Strategy	Workshops on the importance of promoting and supporting the career of women researchers. Several workshops were organised about the importance of promoting and supporting the career of women researchers. These workshops dealt with issues such as promoting the presence of women in decision-making bodies.
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised and N attendees 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N attendees 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N attendees 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N attendees 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N Women researchers promoted in their professional positions	
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	
Gep Strategy	Establishing institutional mechanisms to combat gender-based violence and clear and transparent protocols to address these issues.
This is a strategy introduced in the new GEP version and then it will produce feedbacks in the future	

Legenda

- Very Satisfactory
- Satisfactory
- Unsatisfactory

Figure: levels of satisfaction of MIGAL GEP

8. Evaluation of impacts in Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts - ZRC SAZU

In the following sub-sections, we provide a short description of ZRC SAZU. Then, we analyse data from the State and Process indicators.

8.1 DESCRIPTION OF ZRC SAZU

The Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts - ZRC SAZU (<https://www.zrc-sazu.si/en/>) is one of the leading research and educational centres in Slovenia. More than three hundred research associates are organised into eighteen independent but coordinated and interconnected institutes. Work at ZRC SAZU is distinctly interdisciplinary and based on cooperation, complementation, and synergy. The diverse research areas can be summed up in the study of cultural, social, and natural phenomena, processes, and practices.

8.2 ANALYSIS OF THE STATE INDICATORS

Comparing data collected in 2018 (at the beginning of the project) with data provided by the organisation and related to 2021 (the last official data from the administration before the R&I-Peers project ends), we observe that:

Number of Management and decision-making per gender and per level from 2018 to 2021 decreased, both for females and males with high levels of responsibility for management and decision-making positions. The number of females with a medium level of responsibility for management and decision-making positions was improved as the number of males. ZRC SAZU included in the high level of management and decision-making positions director, director deputies and director assistants; in the medium level included heads of institutes and heads of publishing houses. Finally, included the heads of administrative units in the initial management level.

- The category of people with a high level of responsibilities for employers that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers) includes: 1) in the high-level the heads of administration departments, 2) in the medium-level employees in administration departments and technical support, 3) in the initial level of responsibility the administrative staff. An increasing number of females and decreasing number of males characterises the medium level.

There is a greater number of females than males in all the levels of responsibilities; the number of females was improved in the higher level (from 2 in 2018 to 4 in 2021), while there was 1 male in 2018 and 2021. We observe a decrease in the number of females and males in the medium and initial levels. The picture also returns an unstable situation with fewer males than females in 2021.

- ZRC SAZU is an RPO, and, differently from universities, employees do not occupy positions of professors. For cross-organisation data comparison, the career level used in each organisation can be transformed into levels A, B, and C according to the OECD Frascati Manual. ZRC SAZU, when collecting data related to the number of professors and researchers per gender, this category included Research advisors in level A, Senior Research associate for level B, Research associate for level C and Assistants with Ph.D. for Level D.

The number of professors and researchers per gender changed from 2018 to 2021. The number of female and male full professors (level A) decreased, with a tendency to reach a balance per gender (22 females and 24 males in 2021). Also the number of female and male professors (level B) changed, becoming more balanced in 2021 (18 females and 19 males).

The number of professors in level C changed with 9 more females and 1 more male in 2021 with respect to 2018, improving the already existing gap between females and males. The number of professors in level D changed with 3 more females and 3 more males in 2021 with respect to 2018.

- Even if the number of fellows (females and males both decreased) changed from 2018 to 2021, there were no male fellows in 2021. This reduction could also be connected with the pandemic crisis.

- % of people in Boards of the organisation per gender is an important indicator of the gender balance in the management and decisional positions in the organisation. It shows changes from 2018 to 2021, with a decrease in the percentage of females (from 49% to 43%) and an increase in the percentage of males (from 51% to 57%). The board composition seems to be less balanced in 2021 with respect to 2018; but this change is the normal variation that in the short term can occur in a balanced board (a composition from 40% and 60% distributed among females and males can be considered balanced).

- The % of project coordinators/project managers per gender changed from 2018 to 2021. In particular, the percentage of females changed from 61% to 53% and the percentage of males improved from 39% in 2018 to 47 in 2021. The evolution from 2018 to 2021 produced a more balanced percentage of project coordinators/managers per gender.

- ZRC Sazu did not appoint a Board for Gender Equality. The board will be appointed and approved by the board of directors before June 2023.
- In 2018 ZRC Sazu dedicated 0,5% of its budget for Gender Equality, and this % unchanged in 2021.
- There are no internal rules for a balanced Staff recruitment committee, as the Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition to comply with a Slovenian national law that establishes it.
- Work-life balance tools are available in ZRC SAZU. In particular, these tools are teleworking and parental leave. In 2018 also smart working was adopted. Note that parental leave is regulated by law, not by the organisation decisions. The Slovenian law enables one year of paid parental leave, and there is a well-developed and accessible system of public nurseries. Because of that, there are no specific childcare facilities in the research organisation.

All data collected per gender are categorised by females and males. Data about "Other" are not collected as well as any information on ethnicity.

8.3 ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS INDICATORS

The strategies and actions of the GEP within ZRC SAZU, as planned and evolved according to the suggestions emerging during the project life, are explained in the deliverable "D4.4 - Final GEPs definition improvement" and they are listed in the table contained in Appendix II, that also contains the indicators and thresholds related to each strategy. The strategies were classified according to the five areas identified in the "Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans" [2].

Analysing the strategies carried out within the GEP (see appendix II), we observed that they obtained impacts mostly "Very satisfactory" (according to the established thresholds), with few strategies "Satisfactory" or "Unsatisfactory". The situation for ZRC SAZU is summarised in the figure that follows with a scorecard representation. All the Unsatisfactory or Satisfactory strategies (but do not reach the maximum level of satisfaction) were strongly influenced by the crisis produced by the COVID19, particularly in the year 2020 with the peak of the pandemy.

D5.1 - Final report on GEPs impact progress Dissemination level – PU

GEP Area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	
Gep Strategy	Establishing mechanisms to provide advising on integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching	
Level of satisfaction x appointing GE officer		
Level of satisfaction x informing employees		
Gep Strategy	Publication of an educational book dedicated to female researchers (from Slovenia and the region, in historical perspective)	
Level of satisfaction when done		
GEP Area	Work-life balance and organisational culture	
Gep Strategy	Regular statistics to gain insight into the extent of the use of available services, particularly those provided by the institution (summer research workshops for kids, recreational options, sport days, etc.).	
Level of satisfaction x preparation and presentation to DMB 2018		
Level of satisfaction x preparation and presentation to DMB 2019		
Level of satisfaction x preparation and presentation to DMB 2020		
Level of satisfaction x preparation and presentation to DMB 2021		
Gep Strategy	Yearly needs analysis (questionnaire)	
Level of satisfaction x analysis done and x N of respondents, and analysis incorporated into report 2020		
Level of satisfaction x analysis done and x N of respondents, and analysis incorporated into report 2021		
Gep Strategy	Increasing availability of work from home and flexible working hours	
Level of satisfaction x N of institutes that made available this opportunity 2018		
Level of satisfaction x N of institutes that made available this opportunity 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of institutes that made available this opportunity 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of institutes that made available this opportunity 2021		
Gep Strategy	Survey of changes in the employees' needs caused by the Covid-19 pandemic	
Level of satisfaction x survey done and results presented		
Gep Strategy	Development and implementation of gender-sensitive models in a specific set of documents at ZRC SAZU	
Level of satisfaction x N of documents updated		
GEP Area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	
Gep Strategy	Yearly gender-segregated statistics on indicators of career paths of early-career researchers (the number of new young researchers and post-docs; the number of graduates; the number of those who left ZRC SAZU and of those who stayed after their PhD/post-doc project).	
Implements Actions	Regular collection of statistical data	
Level of satisfaction x N of collections 2018		
Level of satisfaction x N of collections 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of collections 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of collections 2021		
Gep Strategy	Regular trainings for mentors	
Level of satisfaction x N of trainings and number of attendees 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of trainings and number of attendees 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of trainings and number of attendees 2021		
Gep Strategy	Regular workshops for grant and project application writing	
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops and attendees 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops and attendees 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops and attendees 2021		
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops and attendees 2022		
Gep Strategy	Regular workshops for improving academic writing	
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2021		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants 2021		
Gep Strategy	Yearly workshops on promotion criteria and how to achieve them	
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants Women 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants Men 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants Women 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants Men 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of workshops 2021		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants Women 2021		
Level of satisfaction x N of participants Men 2021		
Gep Strategy	Promoting the visibility of female scientists through special PR campaigns and special channels of social media	
Level of satisfaction x N of campaigns 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of campaigns 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of campaigns 2021		
Level of satisfaction x N of campaigns 2022		
Gep Strategy	Organizing events to promote female researchers (girls/women in science activities and programmes)	
Level of satisfaction x N of events 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of events 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of events 2021		
Level of satisfaction x N of events 2022		
Gep Strategy	Regular trainings for young researchers on how to communicate their research results to the media and broader audiences.	
Level of satisfaction x N of trainings 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of Women attendees 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of Men attendees 2019		
Level of satisfaction x N of trainings 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of Women attendees 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of Men attendees 2020		
Level of satisfaction x N of trainings 2021		
GEP Area	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	
Gep Strategy	Policy on ethics, equal opportunities, and integrity in research.	
Level of satisfaction x when adopted		
GEP Area	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	
Gep Strategy	Establishing the Commission for ethics, integrity, and equal opportunities in research	
Level of satisfaction x when established		
Gep Strategy	Appointing a Gender Equality Advisor	
Level of satisfaction x when appointed		
Gep Strategy	Code of conduct in the case of gender-based violence and sexual harassment: update of existing regulation.	
Level of satisfaction x when established, or preparatory work running		
Gep Strategy	Needs analysis in the field combating gender-related violence and sexual harassment	
Level of satisfaction x when done		
Gep Strategy	Establishing channels for anonymously reporting disrespectful behaviour, abuse, and sexual harassment.	
Level of satisfaction x when established and functioning		

Legenda

- Very Satisfactory
- Satisfactory
- Unsatisfactory

Figure: levels of satisfaction of ZRC Sazu GEP

More in detail, the strategies "Regular trainings for mentors" and "Yearly workshops on promotion criteria and how to achieve them" started very well in 2019, but the pandemic had a strong influence on achieving the expected impact determining an insufficient number of workshops and attendees. The "Regular trainings for young researchers on how to communicate their research results to the media and broader audiences" strategy is strangely discontinuous, with Very satisfactory results in 2020 and Unsatisfactory results in 2019 and 2021.

If the crisis produced by the COVID19 pandemic negatively impacted some strategies. One strategy probably benefited from the pandemic: "Increasing availability of work from home and flexible working hours"

9. Evaluation of impacts in the National agency for the promotion of scientific research - ANPR

In the following sub-sections, we provide a short description of the ANPR and then analyse data coming from the State and Process indicators.

9.1 DESCRIPTION OF ANPR

The National Agency for the Promotion of scientific Research – ANPR (www.anpr.tn) was created in 2008 by the law n° 2008-60 dated on August the 4th, 2008 and amended by the law n° 2010-42 of July the 26th 2010. Under the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research guardianship, ANPR has the status of scientific and technological public establishment with administrative and financial autonomy. The GEP is conceived as a living plan that feeds on all the improvements provided by coordination, partners, the advisory board members or other parties. As a Research Funding Organization (RFO), ANPR works in a national context, recognising the important historic place occupied by women in society in general and in the field of science in particular.

9.2 ANALYSIS OF THE STATE INDICATORS IN ANPR

Comparing data collected in 2018 (at the beginning of the project) with data provided by the organisation and related to 2021 (the last official data from the administration before the R&I-Peers project ends), we observe that:

- the Number of Management and decision-making positions per gender and per level from 2018 to 2021 changed, improving the number of males both in the higher and in the medium level of responsibility, while the number of females was unchanged at the higher level (which remains balanced per gender) of responsibility and decreased in the medium level producing a gender GAP in this level.

- considering the Number of employees in your organisation per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers) the number of females grew from 2018 to 2021 for the higher (from 2 to 3) and medium levels (from 9 to 12); the number of females in the initial level is the same (3) in 2018 and 2021. The number of males is unchanged at all levels. Data show that the medium level is quite unbalanced with more females than males.

- The composition of boards per gender in 2021 (% of people in Boards of the organisation per gender) is perfectly balanced with 50% females and 50% males.

- The % of project coordinators/project managers per gender indicates an unbalanced situation, with the female percentage decreasing from 80% in 2018 to 72,72% in 2021.

- ANPR appointed its Board for Gender Equality on April the 1st 2021.
- Staff recruitment committees' composition was foreseen to have a gender-balanced composition.
- The Work-life balance tools available in ANPR till 2018 with telework, parental leave and other services, such as a contribution to back-to-school expenses for children, a contribution to expenses for religious holidays, the distribution of restaurant tickets.

All data collected per gender in the organisation are categorised by females and males. Data about "Other" are not collected as well as any information on ethnicity to avoid discrimination.

9.3 ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS INDICATORS OF ANPR

The strategies and actions of the GEP within ANPR, as planned and evolved according to the suggestions emerging during the project life, are explained in the deliverable "D4.4 - Final GEPs definition improvement" and they are listed in the table contained in Appendix II, that also contains the indicators and thresholds related to each strategy. The strategies were classified according to the five areas identified in the "Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans" [2].

Analysing the strategies carried out within the GEP (see appendix II), we observed that they obtained impacts mostly "Very satisfactory" (according to the established thresholds). The situation for ANPR is summarised in the figure that follows with a scorecard representation. Some strategies in the area of "Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content" that required the organisation of events achieved an Unsatisfactory result only in 2021, with excellent results in the other years. The two strategies that appeared most critical with "Unsatisfactory" results were those, in some way, related to leadership: "Establishing a Women in Science Excellence Prize (Award)" and "Organization and/or participation in events on gender bias in decision making bodies".

Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	
Gep Strategy	Regular trainings for mentors
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2019	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2020	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2021	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N workshops organised 2022	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of participants per year 2019	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of participants per year 2020	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of participants per year 2021	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of participants per year 2022	Very Satisfactory
Gep Strategy	Organisation and participation in events on relevance of gender dimension in Research area
Level of satisfaction x N events organised 2018	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N events organised 2019	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N events organised 2020	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N events organised 2021	Unsatisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N events organised 2022	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of beneficiaries 2018	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of beneficiaries 2019	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of beneficiaries 2020	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of beneficiaries 2021	Unsatisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of beneficiaries 2022	Very Satisfactory
Gep Strategy	Establishing a Women in Science Excellence Prize (Award)
Level of satisfaction x N of Women researchers awarded	Unsatisfactory
Gep Strategy	Establishing a social media channel/a brochure/a series of podcasts... promoting achievements of female Tunisian researchers
Level of satisfaction x Social media channels established	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of flyers brochure/a series of podcasts... distributed 2018	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of flyers brochure/a series of podcasts... distributed 2019	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of flyers brochure/a series of podcasts... distributed 2020	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of flyers brochure/a series of podcasts... distributed 2021	Unsatisfactory
Level of satisfaction x N of flyers brochure/a series of podcasts... distributed 2022	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x Number (n) of flyers brochure/a series of podcasts... distributed	Very Satisfactory
Number (n) of roll-up produced	Very Satisfactory
Work-life balance and organisational culture	
Gep Strategy	Establishing a Committee for equal opportunities
Level of satisfaction x establishment of the committee	Very Satisfactory
Gep Strategy	Analysis of language of ANPR's documents and official communication and detecting areas where the use of gender sensitive language could be improved
Level of satisfaction x Analysis report status	Satisfactory
Gep Strategy	Improvement of official documents and communication practices at ANPR (Toolkit for employees...)
Level of satisfaction x Training on gender sensitive communication and New practices Toolkit adopted	Satisfactory
Gep Strategy	Regular analysis of Employees needs/requirements (questionnaire)
Level of satisfaction x Analysis incorporated into report	Very Satisfactory
Gep Strategy	Improving working policies and condition to make them sensitive to special needs of employees and their families
Level of satisfaction x Facilities/condition available	Satisfactory
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	
Gep Strategy	Yearly statistic indicators of career paths of employees
Level of satisfaction x availability of statistical indicators 2020 (related to 2019)	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x availability of statistical indicators 2021 (related to 2020)	Very Satisfactory
Level of satisfaction x availability of statistical indicators 2022 (related to 2021)	Very Satisfactory
Gep Strategy	Gathering regularly gender disaggregated statistics
Level of satisfaction based on the availability of statistics	Satisfactory
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	
Gep Strategy	Organisation and/or participation in events on gender bias in decision making bodies
Level of satisfaction x N of HL events per year	Unsatisfactory
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	
Gep Strategy	Establishing channels to report anonymously disrespectful behavior, abuse and sexual harassment
Level of satisfaction x channel established	Very Satisfactory

Figure: levels of satisfaction of ANPR GEP

10. Evaluation of impacts in the General Secretariat for Family Policy and Gender Equality - GSFPGE

In the following sub-sections, we provide a short description of the GSFPGE and then analyse data from the State and Process indicators.

10.1 DESCRIPTION OF GSFPGE

The General Secretariat for Family Policy and Gender Equality – GSFPGE, is the Greek governmental organisation (part of the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs) competent to promote Gender Equality in all political, economic, and social life sectors. By definition, the issue of Gender Equality is closely linked with all its activities. It is subjected to a gender-neutral legal framework, and a gender quota regarding decision-making bodies. All these results in high percentages of women in decision-making bodies, create a gender-neutral institutional culture, which ensures equal career opportunities, equal wages and equal recognition of achievements as well as the absence of gender stereotypes, and, to a degree, explains the high percentage of women employees among the staff. However, the questionnaire that was answered in the early stage of the GEP definition revealed important differentiations among men and women regarding their needs and perceptions within the daily operation of the organisation and that even within a gender-neutral institutional framework and culture, the traditional gender division of labour in the family still proves to be critical for women’s careers. It would welcome measures for balancing professional and family life like telework and work from home, flexible work hours/days and children-friendly facilities.

10.2 ANALYSIS OF THE STATE INDICATORS OF GSFPGE

Comparing data collected in 2018 (at the beginning of the project) with data provided by the organisation and related to 2021 (the last official data from the administration before the R&I-Peers project ends), we observe that:

- the Number of Management and decision-making positions per gender and per level from 2018 to 2021 changed, improving the number of females in the higher level of responsibility, while it decreased in the medium level from 8 females in 2018 to 0 in 2021.

There were 2 males in the higher level in 2018 and 2021, while there were no males in the medium level neither in 2018 nor in 2021. Independently from the changes, there is a situation of unbalance per gender at the higher level. The situation was balanced at the medium level in 2021 with 0 females and 0 males; the aim is to reach a balance requires also maintaining active the positions in the organisations;

- considering the Number of employees in your organisation per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers), the number of females grew from 2018 to 2021 for the higher (from 5 to 8) while this number decreased in the medium level (from 8 to 0); the number of females decreased also in the initial level (from 44 to 40). The number of employees is unbalanced in the different levels per gender. The number of males unchanged in the high (2 males) and medium levels (0 males). Moreover, the number of males in the initial level decreased from 17 to 8.

- The composition of boards per gender in 2021 (% of people in Boards of the organisation per gender) is quite balanced, with 60% females and 40% males.

- The % of project coordinators/project managers per gender indicates changes from 2018 to 2021, with a tendency to balance this percentage per gender. Indeed, for 100% of females in 2018, 66,7% of females and 33,3% of males in 2021 were project coordinators or project managers.

- GSFPGE did not appoint its Board for Gender Equality.
- There is no rule in GSFPGE related to the gender balance within the Staff recruitment committees' composition.
- The Work-life balance tools available in GSFPGE include flexible working hours and parental leave.

All data collected per gender in the organisation are categorised by females and males. Data about "Other" are not collected as well as any information on the ethnicity to avoid discrimination.

10.3 ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS INDICATORS OF GSFPGE

The strategies and actions of the GEP within GSFPGE, as planned and evolved according to the suggestions emerging during the project life, are explained in the deliverable "D4.4 - Final GEPs definition improvement" and they are listed in the table contained in Appendix II, that also contains the indicators and thresholds related to each strategy. The strategies were classified according to the five areas identified in the "Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans" [2].

Analysing the strategies carried out within the GEP (see appendix II), we observed that they have been strongly influenced by the crisis produced by the COVID19 pandemic. Many of the strategies related to events, travels etc. have been primarily unsatisfactory, in particular, the strategies: "Organization/attendance of seminars for employees to improve the skills relevant for their career advancement", "Introducing mechanisms to facilitate leaves for education and research (e.g. sabbatical, nonpaid leave, fellowship abroad)", "Institutionalising an open day for parents to bring their kids to the office once or twice a year", "Training on team management and problem-solving considering the gender perspective" and "Regular organisation/attendance of training seminars for GSFPGE staff covering several general GE aspects". All the other strategies have been mostly "Very satisfactory".

GEP Area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
Gep Strategy	Regular organisation/attendance of training seminars for GSDFPGE staff covering several general GE aspects (including use of non-sexist language-Guide, raising awareness of gender perspective in research content for GSDFPGE staff involved in evaluation of research proposals)
Level of satisfaction x N of seminars 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of participants seminar 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of seminars 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of participants seminar 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of seminars 2021	
Level of satisfaction x N of participants seminar 2021	
Gep Strategy	Analysis of language of GSDFPGE's documents and official communication and detecting discrepancies with language use suggested in the guidelines developed by GSGE
Level of satisfaction x N of documents analysed	
Gep Strategy	Development and implementation of gender sensitive models in communication practices and specific set of documents in GSDFPGE
Level of satisfaction when models implemented and communicated	
GEP Area	Work-life balance and organisational culture
Gep Strategy	Institutionalizing "an open day" for parents to bring their kids to the office once or twice a year
Level of satisfaction x N of openday 2019	
Level of satisfaction x N of openday 2020	
Level of satisfaction x N of openday 2021	
Gep Strategy	Introducing the possibility of flexible working hours
Level of satisfaction for internal steps beginning	
Gep Strategy	Introducing the possibility of telework
Level of satisfaction x introduction of telework	
Gep Strategy	Including relevant information on national work-life balance related legislation to the GSDFPGE's website
Level of satisfaction x Number of Posts	
GEP Area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Gep Strategy	Regular data collection and statistic reports on demographic structure with data disaggregated according to gender and position
Level of satisfaction x Number of reports 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Number of reports 2020	
Level of satisfaction x Number of reports 2021	
Level of satisfaction x Number of reports 2022	
Level of satisfaction x % of Woman in senior/decision Making 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Level of satisfaction x %of Woman in senior/decision Making 2020	
Level of satisfaction x % of Woman in senior/decision Making 2021	
Level of satisfaction x % of Woman in senior/decision Making 2022	
Gep Strategy	Organisation / attendance of seminars for employees to improve the skills relevant for their career advancement)
Level of satisfaction x Number of seminars 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Number of participants 1st seminar 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Number of participants 2nd seminar 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Number of participants 3rd seminar 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Number of seminars 2020	
Level of satisfaction x Number of participants seminar 2020	
Level of satisfaction x Number of seminars 2021	
Level of satisfaction x Number of participants 1st seminar 2021	
Level of satisfaction x Number of participants 2nd seminar 2021	
Level of satisfaction x Number of participants 3rd seminar 2021	
Gep Strategy	Introducing mechanisms to facilitate leaves for education and research (e.g. sabbatical, nonpaid leave, fellowship abroad)
Level of satisfaction x Number of Women 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Number of Man 2019	
Level of satisfaction x Number of Women 2020	
Level of satisfaction x Number of Man 2020	
Level of satisfaction x Number of Women 2021	
Level of satisfaction x Number of Men 2021	

Figure: levels of satisfaction of GSDFPGE GEP

11. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we provide some elements for reflection and lessons learned from the monitoring activity in R&I-Peers.

All the organisations took advantage of defining and implementing the GEP, even if the COVID19 pandemic and socioeconomic difficulties introduced some problems. The organisations are implementing their GEPs and discussed their sustainability (see the deliverable “D7.10- Exploitation and Sustainability Plan”).

The main lessons learned from monitoring are the following:

- monitoring activity underlined that the activities planned within the different GEPs were frequently very Satisfactory, and the level of satisfaction decreases according to criticalities introduced by factors external to the organisations, such as the COVID19 pandemic, or internal factors, such as the reduction of the number of employees due to economic crisis. The presence and support coming from policymakers and funding programmes is crucial for each organisation, and monitoring Gender Equality indicators returns the health status of the organisation in general;
- with respect to the work-life balance, it has been observed that the COVID-19 pandemic was generally a critical factor that accelerated the process for the adoption of smart working or similar types of work. In some cases, the process is incomplete due to the difficulty of overcoming some legal issues where a new culture of responsibility should be promoted.
- monitoring has to be able to measure “the progress towards achieving the objectives” providing “an opportunity to learn and find out what needs to be improved ” (<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/step-step-guide-funding/step-5>) in each organisation related to the institutionalisation of Gender Equality. For this reason, it is important to include an indicator that returns the GEP implementation level yearly;
- monitoring has to be flexible enough to suggest and follow the evolution of the GEPs according to the needs of the organisations, also introducing new strategies in the years, which the staff of each organisation can better accept. Indeed, monitoring activities have to cross the needs emerging in each organisation, and this can improve the acceptance of the proposed strategies within the Gender Equality Plans;
- monitoring, particularly for organisations such as universities, needs to focus on strategies and indicators that return the situation related to the gender balance in the different faculties (also in the STEM field). Indeed, other organisations working mainly in the STEM sectors have difficulties to attract more women as, they observe that it does not exist a number of people balanced per gender in STEM;
- monitoring indicators need to be contextualised in different countries, as policies and regulations can profoundly influence the adoption and institutionalisation of a specific strategy. This is the case (for example) of building recruitment bodies adopting the concept of Gender Balance; in some countries, this is established by a National law; in other cases, this is not established and could be

introduced as a strategy and, consequently the indicator in the GEP, aiming to institutionalise a quota system within the recruitment body (as an example),

- monitoring has to consider strategies and indicators on a different temporal scale; indeed, some strategies and actions can produce changes at the institutional level that can be observed in the short term, medium term and long term. For example, the indicators related to the Gender balance in leadership and decision-making are usually related to observation in the medium and long term, mainly in organisations with a medium and big dimension. Moreover, the decision-making positions are a short number of positions in each organisation, and monitoring if the gender balance principles are applied requires a monitoring action in the time;
- it is crucial to consider and include monitoring indicators that show the evolution in the organisation of the Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content, as this kind of indicator returns the cultural change that is produced within the organisation. This aspect is crucial for the Research Performing Organisations (independently from their dimension or geographical location);
- during the project life, we observed that the different organisations collect data according to a binary approach. This was mainly due to avoiding discrimination (frequent in different historical periods). However, the evolution in the gender culture is producing the need to evolve data collection from the binary approach (usually followed by the organisations) toward an Alias approach. This approach started in a big university as UNISA. It is important to consider and introduce indicators that guarantee inclusiveness, avoiding discriminations.

12. BIBLIOGRAPHY AND SITOGRAPHY

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3. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/876509>

Appendix I - Survey from the pilot organisations - Objective data collection (State indicators)

Objective data are collected within the partners that are implementing the GEPs carrying out “Analytical measures, targets, indicators, monitoring and evaluation”.

UNISA

2018 Objective data collection

Organization name
University of Salerno

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	39	76	
2 Medium level of responsibility	49	60	

Number of employees in your organization per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	2	5		EP - senior executives
2 Medium level of responsibility	275	301		C (civil servants) - D (officials / office managers)
3 Initial level of responsibility	11	25		B - (lower-level state employees)

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other
Level A (full professor)	53	175	
Level B (associate professor)	147	233	
Level C (RU)	115	120	
Level D (RTDA/B)	43	43	

Number of fellows per gender	Male	Other
Female		
122	90	

Number of Ph.D. Students per gender (for university only)		
Female	Male	Other
249	246	

% of people per level management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	17	34	
Middle level management	22	27	
initial level management	N/A	N/A	

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
32	68	

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
X	
If Yes, Specify the date	
OGEPO (study gender in research)- CUG (promotes gender and wellbeing in the workplace)	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender		
Female	Male	Other
31	69	

Budget for Gender Equality actions
€ 68000 for years

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
	X

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
X	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No

X	
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If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
X		X	X

If Other Specify
maternity, part-time, illness for child, paid leave for disabled people (art. 42 dlgs 151/2001) and law 104)

2021 Objective data collection

Organization name
University of Salerno

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	43	72	0
2 Medium level of responsibility	57	50	0

Number of employees in your organization per level and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	3	4		EP - senior executives
2 Medium level of responsibility	285	280		C (civil servants) - D (officials / office managers)
3 Initial level of responsibility	9	19		B - (lower-level state employees)

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other
Level A (full professor)	75	227	0
Level B (associate professor)	195	225	0
Level C (RU)	78	95	0
Level D (RTDA/B)	49	57	0

Number of fellows per gender		
Female	Male	Other
118	89	0

Number of Ph.D. students per gender (for university only)		
Female	Male	Other
256	250	

% of people per level for management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	19%	32%	
Middle level management	26%	23%	
initial level management	N/A	N/A	N/A

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
33%	67%	

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
X	
If Yes, Specify the date	
12.06.2012	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2020		
Female	Male	Other
30%	70%	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2021		
Female	Male	Other
31%	69%	

Budget for Gender Equality actions
€ 20000,00

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
X	

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
X	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
X	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
X		X	X

If Other Specify
Maternity, part-time, illness for child, paid leave for disabled people (art. 42 dlgs 151/2001) and law 104)

CNTI

2018 Objective data collection

Organization name
CNTI

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	4	4	0
2 Medium level of responsibility	2	1	0

Number of employees in your organization per level and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	1	2	0	..
2 Medium level of responsibility	2	1	0	..
3 Initial level of responsibility	1	0	0	..

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other
Level A	0	1	0
Level B	1	1	0
Level C	0	0	0
Level D	0	0	0

Number of fellows per gender		
Female	Male	Other
1	2	0

Number of Ph.D. students per gender (for university only)		
Female	Male	Other

% of people per level for management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	0	0	0
Middle level management	60	40	0
initial level management	50	50	0

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
50	50	0

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
	x
If Yes, Specify the date	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender		
Female	Male	Other
60%	40%	

% of budget for Gender Equality actions
10

Explanation

(the % is respect to the Total budget of the organisation)

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
x	

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
x	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
x	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
	x	x	x

If Other Specify
Flexible working

2021 Objective data collection

Organization name
CNTI

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	1	2	0
2 Medium level of responsibility	1	0	0

Number of employees in your organization per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	0	0	0	N/A
2 Medium level of responsibility	1	1	0	Accountant, Technician
3 Initial level of responsibility	1	0	0	Marketing

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other
Level A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Level B	N/A	N/A	N/A
Level C	N/A	N/A	N/A
Level D	N/A	N/A	N/A

Number of fellows per gender		
Female	Male	Other
3	0	0

% of people per level management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	33	66	0
Middle level management	50%	50%	0
initial level management	0	0	0

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
50%	50%	0

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No

x	
If Yes, Specify the date	
2 nd Jan 2022	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2020		
Female	Male	Other
100	0	0

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2021		
Female	Male	Other
50	50	0

% of budget for Gender Equality actions
Still based on projects; budget of 500-1000 euro is made available for each action after the GEP Officer requests it.

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
x	

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
x	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
x	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
x	x	x	

If Other Specify

CIC nanoGUNE

2018 Objective data collection

Organization name
CIC Nanogune

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility		1	
2 Medium level of responsibility		2	

Number of employees in your organization per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility		3		Director, Research Director, Finance Director
2 Medium level of responsibility	3	3		Managers
3 Initial level of responsibility	7	10		
	2	8		Technicians
	4	0		Director's Assitant, Secretaries and projects assistant
	1	2		Maintenance tech, Projects engineer, external services tech

Number of Proferssors/Researchers in your organizaion per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other	
Level A	0	10		
Level B	0	2		
Level C	23	27		Fellows (Tenure track)+postdocs
Level D	16	25		PhD students

Number of fellows per gender		
Female	Male	Other
23	27	

Fellows (Tenure track)+postdocs

Number of Ph.D. Students per gender (for university only)		
Female	Male	Other
16	25	

% of people per level management in the organization and per gender			Other
	Female	Male	
Top level management	0	100%	
Middle level management	50	50	
initial level management	41,2	58,8	
	20	80	Technicians
	100	0	Director's Assitant, Secretaries and projects assistant
	33,3	67,7	Maintenance tech, Projects engineer, external services tech

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
40	60	
16,7	83,3	
20	80	
66,7	33,3	

TOTAL
Governing Board
International Advisory Committee
Gender Equality Committee

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
yes	
If Yes, Specify the date	
24/05/2018	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender		
Female	Male	Other
7,7	92,30%	

% of budget for Gender Equality actions	0,37
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Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
	No yet

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
Yes	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
Yes	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
No	No	Yes	Yes

If Other Specify
Maternity leave and part-time.

2021 Objective data collection

Organization name
CIC nanoGUNE

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	1	2	0
2 Medium level of responsibility	3	1	0

Number of employees in your organization per level and gender that do not occupy research	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility

positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)				
1 Higher level of responsibility	1	1	0	Director, Research Director, Finance Director
2 Medium level of responsibility	3	1	0	Managers
3 Initial level of responsibility	9	10	0	

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other	
Level A	0	12	0	
Level B	0	0	0	
Level C	14	23	0	Fellows (Tenure track)+postdocs
Level D	18	24	0	PhD students

Number of fellows per gender			
Female	Male	Other	
1	2		Fellows (Tenure track)+postdocs

% of people per level for management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	50%	50%	
Middle level management	75%	25%	
initial level management	47%	53%	

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
57%	43%	0

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality

Yes	No
yes	
If Yes, Specify the date	
Firstly at 01/06/2017 and renewed 24/05/2018	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender from 2020 to 2021

Female	Male	Other
100%	0%	0

% of budget for Gender Equality actions

17000,00 Euros

Explanation

(the % is respect to the Total budget of the organisation)

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition

Yes	No
Yes	-

Work life balance

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work life balance?

Yes	No
Yes	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?

Yes	No
Yes	

If yes select the service

Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
No	Yes	Yes	No

If Other Specify

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MIGAL

2018 Objective data collection

Organization name
MIGAL

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other	Explanation
1 Higher level of responsibility	12	29	0	1 Dean, President, General manager, Director of a faculty, Director of a department, Director of a laboratory, other
2 Medium level of responsibility	18	20	0	2 Responsible for a specific office of the organization, other

Number of employees in your organization per level and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Explanation
				Administrative and support staff
				Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	7	9	0	..
2 Medium level of responsibility	28	26	0	..
3 Initial level of responsibility	9	10	0	..

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organisation per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other	Explanation
				For cross-organisation data comparison, the career level used in each organisation can be transformed in level A B C according to the OECD Frascati Manual Category A: The single highest grade/post at which research is normally conducted. ❖ Example: for RPOs “director of

Level A	7	30	0	<p>research”, or for universities “full professor”. ● Category B: Researchers working in positions not as senior as top position (A) but more senior than newly qualified doctoral graduates (ISCED level 8). ❖ Example: “senior researcher” or “principal investigator” for universities ❖ Example: Associate professor. ● Category C: The first grade/post into which a newly qualified doctoral graduate would normally be recruited. ❖ Examples: for RPOs and Universities: “researcher”, “investigator” or “post-doctoral fellow”. ● Category D: Either doctoral students at the ISCED level 8 who are engaged as researchers, or researchers working in posts that do not normally require a doctorate degree. ❖ Examples: “Ph.D. students” or fellowships (without a Ph.D.).</p>
Level B	10	11	0	
Level C	1	1	0	
Level D	0	0	0	

Number of fellows per gender		
Female	Male	Other
70	95	0

Number of Ph.D. students per gender (for university only)		
Female	Male	Other
12	42	0

% of people per level for management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other	Explanation 1 Dean (for Universities, President, General manager, Director of a faculty, Director of a department, Director of a laboratory, other 2 Responsible for a specific office of the organization, other
Top level management				
Middle level management				
initial level management				

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender			Explanation Faculty board members, Executive board member, Equal opportunities board, Ethical Board, Scientific advisory Board, Other
Female	Male	Other	
12	88	0	

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality

Yes	No
If Yes, Specify the date	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender

Female	Male	Other

% of budget for Gender Equality actions

--

Explanation
(the % is respect to the Total budget of the organisation)

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition

Yes	No
	X

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?

Yes	No
X	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?

Yes	No
X	

If yes select the service

Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
X		X	X

If Other Specify

Yoga and Pilates classes are held during working hours
--

2021 Objective data collection

Organization name
MIGAL

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other	Explanation
1 Higher level of responsibility	10	41	0	1 Dean, President, General manager, Director of a faculty, Director of a department, Director of a laboratory, other
2 Medium level of responsibility	16	40	0	2 Responsible for a specific office of the organization, other

Number of employees in your organization per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Explanation
1 Higher level of responsibility	4	2	0	Management
2 Medium level of responsibility	7	8	0	Administration
3 Initial level of responsibility	3	4	0	Maintenance, cleanliness

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other	Explanation
Level A	11	37	0	For cross-organisation data comparison, the career level used in each organisation can be transformed in level A B C according to the OECD Frascati Manual

Level B	8	14	0	<p>Category A: The single highest grade/post at which research is normally conducted. ❖ Example: for RPOs “director of research”, or for universities “full professor”. ● Category B: Researchers working in positions not as senior as top position (A) but more senior than newly qualified doctoral graduates (ISCED level 8). ❖ Example: “senior researcher” or “principal investigator” for universities ❖ Example: Associate professor. ● Category C: The first grade/post into which a newly qualified doctoral graduate would normally be recruited. ❖ Examples: for RPOs and Universities: “researcher”, “investigator” or “post-doctoral fellow”. ● Category D: Either doctoral students at the ISCED level 8 who are engaged as researchers, or researchers working in posts that do not normally require a doctorate degree. ❖ Examples: “Ph.D. students” or fellowships (without a Ph.D.) for RPOs</p>
Level C	N/A	N/A	0	
Level D	N/A	N/A	0	

Number of fellows per gender		
Female	Male	Other
59	65	N/A

% of people per level management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	10%	38%	N/A
Middle level management	15%	37%	N/A
initial level management	N/A	N/A	N/A

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
19%	81%	=%

Explanation
Faculty board members, Executive board member, Equal opportunities board, Ethical Board, Scientific advisory Board, Other

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
	X
If Yes, Specify the date	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2020		
Female	Male	Other
25	75	N/A
% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2021		
Female	Male	Other
25	75	N/A

% of budget for Gender Equality actions
N/A

Explanation

(the % is respect to the Total budget of the organisation)

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
	X

Work life balance

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
X	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
X	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
X	X	X	X

If Other Specify

Illness leaves payment of a sick day from the first day, uniform treatment of ill leave without distinction between family member/child

ZRC SAZU

2018 Objective data collection

Organization name
ZRC SAZU

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	4	1	
2 Medium level of responsibility	8	11	

Number of employees in your organization per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	2	1		heads of administration departments
2 Medium level of responsibility	27	8		employees in administration departments
3 Initial level of responsibility	34	18		administrative staff in particular institutes

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other	
Level A	23	29		research advisor
Level B	19	15		senior research associate
Level C	57	43		research associate
Level D	13	9		assistant with PhD

Number of fellows per gender	Here we put PhD students employed as young researchers		
Female	Male	Other	
24	9		

Number of Ph.D. Students per gender (for university only)		
Female	Male	Other

% of people per level management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other	
Top level management	80%	20%		director, director deputies and director assistants
Middle level management	42%	58%		head of institutes, head of publishing house
initial level management	67%	33%		heads of administrative units

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
49%	51%	

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
	x
If Yes, Specify the date	
	adoption is in

	preparation
--	-------------

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender

Female	Male	Other
61%	39%	

we took into account project that STARTED in 2018 + research programs ongoing in 2018

research programs (more stable financing): male 68%, female 32%

% of budget for Gender Equality actions

0.5% of total budget, 2,3% of budget allocated for material costs

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition

Yes	No
	x

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?

Yes	No
x	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?

Yes	No
x	

If yes select the service

Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
	x	x	

parental leave is regulated by law in Slovenia, not by organization decisions

not really clear how smartworking differs from telework

If Other Specify

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2019 Objective data collection

Organization name

ZRC SAZU

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	4	1	
2 Medium level of responsibility	9	10	

Number of employees in your organization per level and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	
				Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	2	1		heads of administration departments
2 Medium level of responsibility	31	8		employees in administration departments and technical support
3 Initial level of responsibility	38	21		administrative staff in particular institutes

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other	
Level A	22	28		research advisor
Level B	19	15		senior research associate
Level C	57	43		research associate
Level D	13	9		assistant with PhD

Number of fellows per gender	Here we put PhD students employed as young researchers	
Female	Male	Other
	12	26

Number of Ph.D. students per gender (for university only)		
Female	Male	Other

% of people per level for management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other	
Top level management	80%	20%		director, director deputies and director assistants
Middle level management	47%	53%		head of institutes, head of

				publishing house
initial level management	67%	33%		heads of administrative units

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
46%	54%	

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
	X
If Yes, Specify the date	
it is in the process of formation	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender		
Female	Male	Other
61%	39%	

we took into account project that STARTED in 2019 + research programs ongoing in 2019

research programs (more stable financing): female 33%, male 67%

% of budget for Gender Equality actions
0.5% of total budget, 2,3% of budget allocated for material costs

Explanation
(the % is respect to the Total budget of the organisation)

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
	X

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
X	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No

x	
---	--

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Tele work	Parental leave	Other
	x	x	

parental leave is regulated by law, not by organization decisions

If Other Specify

2021 Objective data collection

Organization name
ZRC SAZU

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	4	1	
2 Medium level of responsibility	10	9	

Number of employees in your organization per level and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	4	1	0	heads of administration departments
2 Medium level of responsibility	22	4	0	employees in administration departments and technical support
3 Initial level of responsibility	31	10	0	administrative staff in particular institutes

Number of Professors/Researchers in your organization per Level and Gender (For University and RPOs only)	Female	Male	Other
Level A	22	24	
Level B	18	19	

research advisor
senior research associate

Level C	66	44		research associate
Level D	16	12		assistant with PhD

Number of fellows per gender	Here we put PhD students employed as young researchers		
Female	Male	Other	
28	15	0	

% of people per level for management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other	
Top level management	80%	20%		director, director deputies and director assistants
Middle level management	53%	47%		head of institutes, head of publishing house
initial level management	80%	20%		heads of administrative units

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
43%	57%	

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
	x
If Yes, Specify the date	
Ongoing: the board will be appointed and approved by board of directors between February 2022 and June 2023	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2020		
Female	Male	Other
65%	35%	0

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2021		
Other	Male	Other
53%	47%	0

% of budget for Gender Equality actions
0.5% of total budget, 2,3% of budget allocated for material costs

Explanation
(the % is respect to the Total budget of the organisation)

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
	x

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
x	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
x	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
x	x	x	

parental leave is regulated by law, not by organization decisions

If Other Specify

ANPR

2018 Objective data collection

Organization name
National Agency for scientific Research Promotion - ANPR

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	2	2	
2 Medium level of responsibility	7	6	

Number of employees in your organization per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	2	2		..
2 Medium level of responsibility	9	2		..
3 Initial level of responsibility	3	5		..

% of people per level management in the organization and per gender*	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	2	2	
Middle level management	7	6	
initial level management	9	2	

* Based on total HR (36)

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
0	0	

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
	x
If Yes, Specify the date	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender*		
	Male	Other
8 (80%)	2 (20%)	

% of budget for Gender Equality actions
0

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
x	

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
	x

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
x	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
	x*	x**	

* Not recognized in the due charge
** only for women

If Other Specify

2021 Objective data collection

Organization name
National Agency for scientific Research Promotion - ANPR

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	2		3
2 Medium level of responsibility	5		3

Number of employees in your organization per level and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	3		2	..
2 Medium level of responsibility	12		2	..
3 Initial level of responsibility	3		5	..

% of people per level for management in the organization and per gender*	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	17,5%	12,5%	N/A
Middle level management	45%	5%	N/A

initial level management	12,5%	7,5%	N/A
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% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
50%	50%	

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
X	
If Yes, Specify the date	
April 2021	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2020 *		
Female	Male	Other
66,66	33,33	N/A

* based on total HR

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2021 *		
Female	Male	Other
72,72	27,27	N/A

* based on total HR

Indicate the budget for Gender Equality actions (by the organisation)
No specific dedicated budget

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
x	

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
	X

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
x	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
	X	X	X

If Other Specify
Contribution to back-to-school expenses for children, contribution to expenses for religious holidays, distribution of restaurant tickets.

GSFPGE

2018 Objective data collection

Organization name
GSFPGE

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	5	2	0
2 Medium level of responsibility	8	0	0

Number of employees in your organization per level of responsibility and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	Male	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	5	2	0	..
2 Medium level of responsibility	8	0	0	..
3 Initial level of responsibility	44	17	0	..

% of people per level management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	0,714285714	0,285714286	0
Middle level management	100	0	0
initial level management	0,721311475	0,278688525	0

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other

We don't have a board

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
	V
If Yes, Specify the date	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender		
Female	Male	Other
100	0	0

% of budget for Gender Equality actions
100

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No

There is no staff recruitment committee

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
	V

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
V	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
		V	

If Other Specify

2021 Objective data collection

Organization name
GSFPGE

Number of Management and decision making per gender and per level	Female	Male	Other
1 Higher level of responsibility	10	2	0
2 Medium level of responsibility	0	0	0

Number of employees in your organization per level and gender that do not occupy research positions in the organisation (neither professors nor researchers)	Female	1	Other	Specify the responsibility
1 Higher level of responsibility	8	2	0	..
2 Medium level of responsibility	0	0	0	..
3 Initial level of responsibility	40	8	0	..

% of people per level for management in the organization and per gender	Female	Male	Other
Top level management	83,3%	16,7%	0
Middle level management	0%	0%	0
initial level management	83,3%	16,7%	0

% of people in Boards of the organization per gender		
Female	Male	Other
60%	40%	0%

The organization appointed a board for Gender Equality	
Yes	No
	V
If Yes, Specify the date	

% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender 2020		
Female	Male	Other
75%	25%	0%
% of projects coordinators/project managers per gender		

2021		
Female	Male	Other
66,7%	0,33,3%	0%

% of budget for Gender Equality actions
100%

Explanation

(the % is respect to the Total budget of the organisation)

Staff recruitment committees must have a gender-balanced composition	
Yes	No
	X

There is no staff recruitment committee

Has the organization a flexible working time for conciliating a work-life balance?	
Yes	No
X	

Has your organisation services for conciliating work-life with personal life?	
Yes	No
V	

If yes select the service			
Smartworking	Telework	Parental leave	Other
		X	

If Other Specify

Appendix II – Data from GEPs

This appendix provides the tables describing the actions implemented in the GEPs and monitored in R&I-Peers. The strategies of each GEP were classified according to the five areas indicated within the Horizon Europe Guidance for Gender Equality Plan (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/876509>).

UNISA's GEP

During the GEPs implementation, the following actions were initiated and implemented:

<u>GEP Area</u>	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Questionnaire for researchers and professors on gender perspective in research and teaching, with particular attention to STEM disciplines
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Sending the questionnaire to the researchers and professors of UNISA
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of completed questionnaires
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory N>150 Satisfactory 150>= N > 50 Unsatisfactory N<=50
<u>Results and Comments</u>	NA, as the questionnaire has been administrated. The activity is running
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Workshops for students, PhD students and researchers with national and international experts about the inclusion of a gender perspective in research projects and in curricula
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Three seminars were organized during 2019 415 Females and 225 Males attended -Seminars organised so far: -9 May 2019 “Women and Science between past, present and future” (90 participants: F60 – M30) for Master’s degree students. -28 June 2019, a Doctoral Seminar about the R&I PEERS project, equal opportunities

	<p>policies and the inclusion of the gender issue in research and equal opportunities policies in the STEM area (50 participants: F35 – M15).</p> <p>-November 2019 a one-week cycle of seminars “Explaining gender-based violence” was held in concomitance with November 25, the International Day for the elimination of violence against women. These seminars, that date to 2011, aim at raising gender awareness among students, through debates, workshops and lectures with national and international experts of academia, politics and media (500 participants: F320 – M180).</p> <p>As part of the Women's history and gender studies course, a cycle of 12 seminars were organized in 2021 and, in 2022, 13 seminars in 2022; for whose participation registration was required. In both 2021 and 2022 the participants were about 150 (70% women and 30% men).</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of participants x Year
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory Men <=64 Woman <=68</p> <p>Satisfactory 65 <= Men <= 118</p> <p>69 <=Woman <=143</p> <p>Very satisfactory Men >=119</p> <p>Woman >=144</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This activity in 2019 was Very satisfactory in terms of the number of participants (per year) and Gender with 415 females and 225 Males attended in 2019</p> <p>2020 was a critical year due to the pandemic</p> <p>Participation was Satisfactory for Woman and Unsatisfactory for Men in 2021. The activity has to be completed in 2022</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Introduction of an interdisciplinary teaching on GE in the educational offering of all UNISA PhD courses
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Annual inter and metadisciplinary lectures on research methodology in the field of Gender Studies have been included
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of participants
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: N<5</p> <p>Satisfactory: 5<= N< 20</p> <p>Very satisfactory: N>= 20</p>

<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory as more than 50 students attended courses
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Activation of Master and Postgraduate courses on GE and diversity management
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The first Master on GE (Leadership, Gender Equality, Diversity Opportunity “LEGENDO”) was approved by the Department of Humanities Board of Professors. The Master will officially start in September 2022. The call opened
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes, No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is vey satisfactory, as the master was activated
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishment, through an open tender, for a position as a researcher with a temporary employment relationship (RTDA) specialised in gender issues
<u>Implements Actions</u>	One position was established. In June 2022 the call was published to recruit, through a public competition, a professional figure (Researcher -RTDA), expert in equal opportunities and in gender studies
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of positions announced
<u>Thresholds</u>	Unsatisfactory N = 0 Satisfactory N=1 Very Satisfactory N>1
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Satisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Promotion of courses on gender equality as free choice courses among students of all disciplines.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	In 2020 and 2021 during the orientation event (“UNISA orienta”) dedicated to the students of the last year of high schools, the courses of study on GE were promoted. In particular, the IT department, to promote gender equality in the science and technology sectors, has promoted initiatives such as "Coding girls" and " I choose to be IT girl "

	<p>Courses on gender studies were advertised and promoted and can be chosen by all degrees students of the University (i.e. free choice courses).</p> <p>In particular, initially only the course of Women’s History and Gender Studies, held by Prof. Pelizzari, was present at the University level. In the last year, this course has seen the number of students enrolled grow from 20 to 150. In addition, in the a.a. 2020/2021, this course has been joined by another 2 courses on gender issues offered by other departments (Department of Political Sciences and Communication, the Department of Political and Social Studies and the Department of Humanities). Therefore, at the University level, there are currently three courses on gender contents.</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of flyers and messages
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory ≥ 0 and ≤ 500</p> <p>Satisfactory ≥ 501 and ≥ 1000</p> <p>Very Satisfactory</p> <p>≥ 1001</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory x 2020 and 2021. 2022 has to be done in the next period
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Fundraising activities for financing grants for research projects and post-doc projects that include a gender dimension: (also with the support of funds and resources outside UNISA); financing awards for MA thesis developed with a gender perspective.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>A research grant on raising awareness about gender-based violence has been reserved for a post-doctoral student at the University in 2020</p> <p>Two postdoctoral students received research grants on the gender perspective in 2021/2022</p> <p>The following interdepartmental research projects were approved and financed for two years: “Gender and Professions” (4899.44€); “Gender in scientific research” (3804.26€); “The role of the gender equality plan (GEP) in universities” (3211.03); “The new frontiers of gender studies in teaching and research” (4287.49€).</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of grants given
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory: $N \geq 3$</p> <p>Satisfactory: $3 > N \geq 1$</p>

	Unsatisfactory: N=0
<u>Results and Comments</u>	Very satisfactory
<u>GEP Area</u>	Work-life balance and organisational culture
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Creation of ad hoc rooms/ nurseries, as dedicated spaces for breastfeeding, milk pumping, diaper changing. Identification of spaces within the bathrooms for installing baby-changing stations.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>On 8 March 2019, one nursery for breastfeeding, milk pumping, and diaper changing was inaugurated. A second room is under construction (due to the coronavirus outbreak the construction was stopped)</p> <p>The project for the creation of ad hoc spaces for diaper changing in some of the bathrooms of the Departments was interrupted due to coronavirus outbreak.</p> <p>The project for the creation of ad hoc spaces for diaper changing in some of the bathrooms of the Departments was interrupted due to Covid19 outbreak.</p> <p>Now, the technical department has identified new spaces within the bathrooms for installing baby-changing stations</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of rooms/spaces
<u>Thresholds</u>	Unsatisfactory 0 Satisfactory 1-2 Very satisfactory > 2
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is satisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Design and implementation of an ad hoc study area for children (6-14 years) of UNISA's students and employees; Identification of suitable spaces for the creation of a playroom for children.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	This strategy was interrupted due to Covid outbreak Now , the technical department has identified suitable spaces for the creation of a playroom for children
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes, No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when completed
<u>Results and</u>	This strategy is Unsatisfactory, as it did not significantly evolve.

<u>Comments</u>	
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Strengthening the existing initiative Summer Camp for the children of UNISA employees, ensuring the canteen service and opening hours throughout the parents' working day.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	This activity was interrupted due to Covid outbreak. Summer camps were organised again in 2022. It is a Multidisciplinary Sports Activity Program
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory in 2019 and 2021
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Identification of flexible working methods more congenial to the conciliation of time: such as smart-working and teleworking
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Covid19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of smart working measures. During the COVID emergency a questionnaire was administered, the results of which are available at the following link: https://www.cug.unisa.it/unisa-rescue-page/dettaglio/id/2837/module/614/row/9854/emergenza-covid-19-il-sondaggio-del-cug-unisa Now, UNISA has introduced flexible and family-friendly customized working conditions and arrangements for all employees
<u>Indicators</u>	Best practices outlined, number of employees attending
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is very satisfactory as UNISA introduced facilities for conciliation. The number of employees using smart working in the period of COVID-19 pandemic are not significant, as it was compulsory to avoid to work at office when possible
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Incentives aimed at supporting young scholars with children in tow during research periods abroad

<u>Implements Actions</u>	This activity was interrupted due to Covid outbreak. Special funds will be allocated in the budget, during the 2022/2023 academic year.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of fundraising actions
<u>Thresholds</u>	Unsatisfactory: N=0 Satisfactory: 1<=N<=2 Very satisfactory: N>2
<u>Results and Comments</u>	NA, as the activity will be monitored after the project ends
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Services for the promotion of the well-being of UNISA's employees
<u>Implements Actions</u>	An Observatory on the Promotion of Wellbeing was also established within UNISA during 2021
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/no
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done Satisfactory when planned
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was very satisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Revision of the place-names of the two Campuses of UNISA, Fisciano and Baronissi, (streets, squares, areas) on a gender-perspective
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Implementation was suspended due to the Covid. In the meantime, a specific plan has been developed that will be implemented during the 2022/2023 academic year
<u>Indicators</u>	Completed: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when completed Satisfactory if it is running
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Satisfactory

<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Improvement of Gender Budgeting
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Gender Budgeting has become a process strongly embedded in the governance of the University and has a strong functional connection with the most important strategic-management documents of the University of Salerno. Gender budgeting is published periodically and regularly.</p> <p>https://trasparenza.unisa.it/altri-contenuti/bilancio-di-genere</p> <p>https://www.unisa.it/unisa-rescue-page/dettaglio/id/529/module/87/row/8036/presentazione-del-ii-bilancio-di-genere-dell-universita-degli-studi-di-salerno</p> <p>Also the second Gender budgeting is published</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Publication of 2nd Gender Budgeting: Yes, No
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very Satisfactory when done</p> <p>Satisfactory if data collection is running</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Support to the applicant student in the alias activation procedure and during the management of the alias career
<u>Implements Actions</u>	UNISA made operative an office for following the alias career for students that makes the bureaucratic procedure, alternative and temporary, reserved for transgender students more efficient.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of alias careers followed
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory $N > 10$</p> <p>Satisfactory $10 > 0 \geq N \geq 1$</p> <p>Unsatisfactory $N = 0$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This is a Satisfactory strategy with $N > 4$

<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Analysis of national legislation and screening of a selection of institutional documents and communications from a gender perspective (for the introduction of the correct use of gender-neutral language)
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The UNISA site has begun to implement the correct use of gender language both visually and in the texts; indications have been provided on the adoption of gender language at the University level for all documents produced and the guidelines disseminated by the CRUI (Conference of Rectors of Italian Universities) are adopted, adapting them to our reality.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes, No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy, also providing guidelines is Very satisfactory
<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Promotion of the R&I PEERS website on UNISA's official site, OGEPO's website and social pages
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The UNISA hosts on its official website the page dedicated to the GEP in Italian and English. The official website of OGEPO hosts a section dedicated to the R&I PEERS project and its seven GEPs (https://www.unisa.it/areavii/cpo/rei_peers_progetto_europeo)
<u>Indicators</u>	Landing page available
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when available
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Questionnaire on equal opportunities for UNISA's personnel
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Two questionnaires were administered by the CUG together with the OGEPO The data and the trend of the first questionnaire are available on the UNISA CUG website.

	<p>https://www.cug.unisa.it/unisa-rescue-page/dettaglio/id/2837/module/614/row/9854/emergenza-covid-19-il-sondaggio-del-cug-unisa</p> <p>Provided their responses 899 people.</p> <p>The processing of the second questionnaire is in progress</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of responses x questionnaire
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very Satisfactory: $N \geq 500$</p> <p>Satisfactory: $200 \leq N < 500$ C.</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: < 200</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory for the first questionnaire, while we do not have the results for the second one.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Involvement of students and PhD students' associations in the main strategic actions of the project aimed at building gender awareness
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Some seminars already during 2019 were organised with the PhD Students Italian Association (ADI), and the Italian Association of Women Artists and Professionals (FIDAPA). All UNISA associations (68) have been involved in the promotion of teachings and seminars relating to Gender Studies, but in particular the following associations:</p> <p>Link Fisciano</p> <p>Horizon</p> <p>Linguisticamente</p> <p>Studenti di Ingegneria</p> <p>https://web.unisa.it/vivere-il-campus/associazioni-studentesche/albo</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of student associations involved
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory > 9</p> <p>Satisfactory $4 \leq N < 9$</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: $N < 4$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory as the N of association was very high

<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Guidance session for high-school students to promote GE and studies and job opportunities within the STEM field
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Two meetings were done in March 2021. Three meetings were held in February 2022 within unisaorienta to sensitize high school students and in particular women to enroll in scientific faculties.</p> <p>Information material was sent to high schools to promote GS teachings and encourage women's enrollment in science subjects.</p> <p>In the STEM areas, some departments are promoting and sensitizing high school students to enroll in their courses.</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of sessions organised
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory ≥ 4</p> <p>Satisfactory $2 \leq N < 4$</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: $N < 2$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Analysis of annual statistical indicators of the career paths of female and male researchers at the beginning of their careers
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Segregated data collection has become routine; in the statistics office, the data collection is disaggregated by gender for the appropriate study analysis. These data will flow into the Gender Budgeting, published periodically and regularly.</p> <p>https://trasparenza.unisa.it/altri-contenuti/bilancio-di-genere</p> <p>https://www.unisa.it/unisa-rescue-page/dettaglio/id/529/module/87/row/8036/presentazione-del-ii-bilancio-di-genere-dell-universita-degli-studi-di-salerno</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Statistical indicators available
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when available
<u>Results and Comments</u>	Very satisfactory as the second Gender budgeting is available

<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Awareness-raising activities on the importance of the presence of women in leadership positions, in the decision-making bodies (Academic Senate and the Board of Directors) and in evaluation committees.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Three seminars were organized, held within UNISA and on the territory with other universities aimed at stopping the imbalance present in the decision-making bodies and between leadership positions.</p> <p>The first entitled "Italian women from obedience to emancipation for female leadership", carried out in October 2021, with 40 participants, of which 30 women and 10 men.</p> <p>The second entitled "Women's leadership in enterprises", carried out in May 2022, with 48 participants, of which 40 women and 8 men.</p> <p>The third seminar carried out in July 2022, for the official presentation of the 2nd Gender Budgeting of the University of Salerno, with 60 participants, of which 40 women and 20 men</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of activities carried out
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: $N < 1$</p> <p>Satisfactory: $1 \leq N \leq 3$</p> <p>Very satisfactory: $N > 3$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	Very satisfactory from 2021 to 2022 as this activity was delayed
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Support to female candidates in decision-making-bodies of UNISA, also with the request of the introduction of a quota system.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>OGPEO planned to organise 2 seminars to raise awareness among teachers so that women with the right qualifications are candidates for the decision-making bodies of UNISA.</p> <p>The board of OGPEO will undertake to encourage female candidates in all degrees of academic governance</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of activities carried out

<u>Thresholds</u>	Very Satisfactory N> 3 Satisfactory: 3<= N >=2 Unsatisfactory N <2
<u>Results and Comments</u>	To monitor after the end of the project as it is a medium-term activity
<u>GEP Area</u>	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Strengthening educational and training initiatives on the elimination of gender-based violence (e.g. trainings, contest; theatrical performances, etc.)
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Every year in November, starting from 2011, a one-week cycle of seminars “Explaining gender- based violence” is held in concomitance with November 25, the International Day for the elimination of violence against women. These seminars, that see a great participation of students, aim at raising gender awareness among them, trough debates, workshops and lectures with international and national experts. OGEPO is working together with associations and entities present in the area to promote initiatives to combat gender-based violence, such as the creation of a single intervention plan to put together, in the long term, support activities for women victims of violence (for example increasing reception centers, also using assets seized from the Camorra and dedicated to helping women) and the creation of a help desk against stalking and harassment in the workplace.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of initiatives organised and number of participants
<u>Thresholds</u>	Number of initiatives per year: Unsatisfactory 0 Satisfactory 1-4 Very satisfactory > 4 Number of participants per year and gender: Unsatisfactory Men 0-28 Women 0-39 Satisfactory Men 29 - 56 Women 40 - 77 Very satisfactory Men > 56 Women > 77
<u>Results and</u>	This is Satisfactory for N of initiatives and Very satisfactory for participants (from 2018

<u>Comments</u>	to 2021) Also in 2020 the initiative was organised remotely.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishment of a networks with stakeholders and enterprises on a national and regional level
<u>Implements Actions</u>	UNISA with the OGEPO participated in the establishment of a working group called "Interinstitutional Table for the prevention and fight against violence against women". The meetings were suspended during the pandemic and will resume in the academic year. 2022/2023 with the involvement of all the institutions participating in the table. UNISA through the team working at the GEP has strengthened relations with local institutions (Courts, Municipality, Associations) to contrast gender-based violence. Attention will be given to the consolidation of the Network with such Institutions and
<u>Indicators</u>	
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very Satisfactory N> 1 Satisfactory: N =1 Unsatisfactory N =0
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was satisfactory as one working group has been established

CNTI's GEP

<u>GEP Area</u>	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organization of a national photo competition portraying "women in science"
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The goal of supporting the career and excellence of female researchers, through the organization of a national photo competition portraying "women in science", was launched but unfortunately, it was never completed. Due to Covid-19 it was postponed to the Spring of 2023.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of photos submitted

<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory N >100 Satisfactory: 50 < N ≤ 100 Unsatisfactory N < 50
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Unsatisfactory. Indeed this strategy has not been organized. It was decided that with all the attention on Covid-19 and the economic crisis in the country, the time was not right. We hope to be able to schedule it for the Spring of 2023.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Introduction of mechanisms to facilitate leaves for education and research
<u>Implements Actions</u>	With about a dozen projects running in parallel at Future Worlds Center, there are many opportunities for our people to participate in educational workshops. Such workshops are typically week-long. Virtually every associate participates in at least 2-3 such events every year. For their participation, they (1) get time off without losing any of their financial benefits, (2) they get all their travel and subsistence expenses paid. With the split of the organization into 4-5 spin-offs, the situation is currently in a transitional period. Nevertheless, over the past 3 years at least one person was supported to conduct a PhD in Italy, while continuing to be a 50% paid employee of CNTI. https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Aliki_Economidou#Biography
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when the strategy is executed
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory
<u>GEP Area</u>	Work-life balance and organisational culture
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	18 weeks paid parental leave through which the employer will be allowed to work remotely from home for the whole period of the leave
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Over the last years, some of the employees at CNTI have become fathers and mothers. Thus, it became necessary for the organization to provide remote work options during parental leave.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of employees making use of this allowance per year and gender
<u>Thresholds</u>	If there are people in the situation for using this strategy (due to the small dimension of the organisation):

	<p>Unsatisfactory: <1; 0 man; 0 woman</p> <p>Satisfactory: 1; 1 man or 1 woman</p> <p>Very Satisfactory: >2; >=1 man and/or >=1 woman</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was: Satisfactory for 2019 and 2021, Very satisfactory for 2020, and NA as the situation of people working in the organisation did not required this</p> <p>2019 (1 Woman), 2020 (2 Woman), 2021 (1 Woman), 2022 No one</p>
<u>GEP Area</u>	Work-life balance and organisational culture
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	The organization will pay the remaining 25% of the maternity leave paid by the Social Insurances (75%)
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The organisation paid 25% for 1 person in 2021.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of employees making use of this allowance per year (if in the need)
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when used if asked
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory, as 1 person asked this strategy application in 2021.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organization of a yearly workshop to inform employees about the policies on the national and organizational level aimed to improve work-life balance
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Because of the low number of employees in the organization, small meetings were considered sufficient.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of workshops organized and Number of employees attending (per gender and per year)
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Number of workshops organized and number of employees attending (per gender and per year)</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: N <1 workshop; with Nmen <2; Nwomen <2</p> <p>Satisfactory: 1 workshop; Nmen=2; Nwomen=2</p> <p>Very Satisfactory: >1 workshop; Nmen >2; Nwomen >2</p>
<u>Results and</u>	1 Workshop was organised in 2019, The Number of employees within the organisation

<u>Comments</u>	<p>decreased, and the initially established thresholds and the method was unrealistic. One small meeting per year was organised with three people.</p> <p>The strategy was Very satisfactory considering the females (4) and males (3) who attended the workshop in 2019. It was Satisfactory in the remaining years and one more meeting needs to be organised.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Inclusion of relevant information on national work-life balance related legislation to the FWC's website
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Most employees are not aware of the current legislation regarding gender equality. Some small meetings are pending to improve this knowledge, including relative information in the website
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done and updated
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Unsatisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Introduction of the possibility of flexible working hours and remote work
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Even before the Covid-19, the organization promoted remote work. Due to Covid-19, this measure became a necessity
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of employees making use of the strategy per gender
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Number of employees making use of remote work per gender</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: $N_{people} < 2$ (1 Nmen; 1 Nwomen)</p> <p>Satisfactory: $2 \leq N_{people} \leq 4$ (Nmen 2; Nwomen 2)</p> <p>Very Satisfactory: > 4 (Nmen > 2; Nwomen > 2)</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as the max value of employees making use of it (also due to COVID 19) is: Nwomen= 5 and Nmen=6.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Review of all FWC's policy papers
<u>Implements</u>	The implementation of the yearly review lies with the Board, and more specifically with the member of the Board who has the GE in his/her portfolio. The person responsible to

Actions	<p>execute it is the Gender Equality Officer . The website contains the GEP as a relevant policy:</p> <p>https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Gender_Equality_Plan</p> <p>39 policy papers were reviewed and neutral gender-language edits were made:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Signing_an_Honour_Declaration• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Office_Rules• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Procedure:_International_Travel• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Procedure:_Reimbursing_associates_who_made_personal_payments_to_third_parties• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Time_devoted_to_projects• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Joining_Future_Worlds_Center• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Hosting_interns• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Virtual_Officing• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Using_virtual_infrastructure• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Legal-financial_aspects_of_work_contracts• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Procedure:_Self_and_Peer_Evaluation• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Counseling_for_Associates_working_with_Children_and_Vulnerable_Groups• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Procedure:_Preparing_a_grant_application• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Project_Member_Replacement• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/HOM/Reporting_Procedures• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/I_want_to_create_a_page_for_my_project• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Associate• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Intern• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Current_Associate• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Confidentiality_Agreement• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Minimum_ICT_Skills_at_FWC• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Procedure:_Termination• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/SDD_Credit_Point_System• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Lead_SDD_Facilitator• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Types_of_Truth• https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Signing_a_Letter_of_Invitation_and_a_
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	<p>Gentlemen%27s_Agreement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Key_Definitions_used_in_Dialogic_Design_Science • https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Parental_Leave_and_Remote_Work • https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Maternity_/_Paternity_allowance • https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy:_Flexible_Working_hours
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes, No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organization of a seminar to inform employees on the newly implemented policies
<u>Implements Actions</u>	1 seminar in 2019. This seminar had 9 attendees
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of employees attending
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: <5</p> <p>Satisfactory: >5 and <=10</p> <p>Very Satisfactory: >10</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This seminar with 9 attendees was Satisfactory
<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular workshops / webinars dedicated to grant and project application writing
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Every occasion a grant application is being written, all young scientists (including visiting and interns) are invited to participate.
<u>Indicators</u>	Num of workshops and Num of involved workers/students
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>No. of workshop per year: Unsatisfactory: <1 Satisfactory: >=1 and <=2 Very satisfactory >2</p> <p>Unsatisfactory <=3 women <=3 men Satisfactory: >=4 and <=7 women >=4 and <=6</p>

	men: Very satisfactory >7 women and >6 men
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory in 2019 and 2020 with 4 workshops in 2019, 2 workshops in 2020; in total, 6 men and 5 women attended these workshops (the females and males' participation were Satisfactory). The strategy was satisfactory for the number of project writing in 2021 and 2022, but unsatisfactory for the number of attendees. The reduction in the number of employees suggested to adopts an approach o learning by doing during 2021-2022, 4 EU project applications have been completed in which four people among visiting and/or interning students took part (with a balanced composition by gender).
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular workshops / webinars dedicated to academic writing
<u>Implements Actions</u>	2 workshops organised during 2019 and with the participation of 3 men. Only 2 women attended the workshops. The reduction of the dimension of the organisation suggested to adopt a strategy of learning by doing
<u>Indicators</u>	No. of workshop per year No. of precipitants
<u>Thresholds</u>	No. of workshop per year: Unsatisfactory: <1 Satisfactory: >=1 and <=2 Very satisfactory >2 No. of precipitants Unsatisfactory: Women <3 Man<3 Satisfactory: Women =3 and Man=3 Very Satisfactory: Women>3; Man>3
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This activity is Satisfactory with 2 workshops organised during 2019 and with the participation of 3 men. Only 2 women attended the workshops and then unsatisfactory for women participation. After that, the implementation of the strategy, with the learning by doing approach can be considered Satisfactory for the articles submitted (4) but unsatisfactory for the number of people involved. This provide us with an important element for considering including in this case a collaborative approach with other organisation to empower the strategy (mainly for small organisations).

<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organization of a Structured Democratic Dialogue (SDD) Workshop on a national level with youth to identify actions to reduce gender gap among young researchers
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The foreseen seminar/workshop on gender issues were not organised due to Covid-19; however, members have received training indirectly through their participation in the four MMLs organized by CNTI.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of attendees
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory: $N > 8$ Satisfactory: $3 \leq N \leq 8$ Unsatisfactory: $N < 3$
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Unsatisfactory, and it is necessary that will be planned again to collect suggestions aiming to identify actions
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishment of a procedure for the equal hiring of researchers based on gender
<u>Implements Actions</u>	“A procedure for the equal hiring of researchers based on gender” has been established but not implemented because due to the splitting of the organization and the reduced number of projects hiring was minimal
<u>Indicators</u>	Established: Yes, No When established Number of researchers (NR) hired
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory if established and $NR \geq 10$ Satisfactory if established Unsatisfactory if not established
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Satisfactory
<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Inclusion of planned measures in FWC’s internal policy documents
<u>Implements</u>	<u>All CNTI's policy documents are published online on the Future</u>

<u>Actions</u>	<p><u>Worlds pedia.</u></p> <p><u>The following links provide all relevant policies, procedures, and the Gender Equality Plan itself.</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Constitutional and Value Policy: Special Focus on the Gender Dimension 2. https://www.futureworlds.eu/w/index.php?title=Policy: Gender Equality Plan 3. https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Procedure: Hiring process <p>https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/Policy: Gender Equality Plan</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is very satisfactory
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Person in charge to provide information, help and advice to employees regarding the available policies
<u>Implements Actions</u>	GE advisor was appointed in February 2022
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory as the person was appointed
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishment of an equal participation of the two genders in CNTI's Board by introducing a specific clause in the policy document
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The BoD is comprised of 3 men and 3 women
<u>Indicators</u>	Equal composition established and done: Yes, No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory if established and equal composition done
<u>Results and</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory

<u>Comments</u>	
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organization of a yearly workshop on gender bias in decision making bodies
<u>Implements Actions</u>	One workshop was organised in 2019, where 2 females and 2 males attended. CNTI members of the group who were interested in the topic, starting from 2020 organised and were asked to attend the two virtual SDD workshops conducted by CNTI on behalf of the consortium in 2020 and 2021. The subjects of the SDDs can be reached here: https://www.futureworlds.eu/wiki/R%26I_PEERS#Structured_Democratic_Dialogue_workshops
<u>Indicators</u>	Num of workshops (NW) organized and Num of participants (NP) attending per gender and per year
<u>Thresholds</u>	Unsatisfactory: <1 workshop; <2 men; <2 women Satisfactory: =1 workshop; =2 men; =2 women Very Satisfactory: >1 workshop; >2 men; >2 women
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This activity is Satisfactory

CIC nanoGUNE's GEP

<u>GEP Area</u>	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Employee information about the GEP and GEC
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Annual seminar highlighting relevant/useful information about the GEP and the Gender Equality Committee (GEC)
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of attendees
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory: $60 \leq n \leq 70$

	<p>Satisfactory: $50 \leq n < 60$</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: $n < 50$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>The strategy is Very satisfactory in 2022 with the organisation of the seminars at 25.04.2022 that was attended by more than 70 people. It was unsatisfactory in the previous years. Indeed, seminars were suspended in 2020 and 2021 due to the Covid-19 pandemic. A seminar was carried out in 2022 with a number of attendees $n > 70$. The event was hybrid, in person and online, accessible by employees of nanoGUNE.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	<p>Employee information about the Gender distribution at CIC NanoGUNE</p>
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Create a record with the number of women and men involved in each area (research groups, administration, and services) and update it yearly to monitor the evolution. This data will be published annually in a "Gender Report" to make sure the whole nanoGUNE community is aware of the situation.</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Done:</p> <p>Yes/No</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory when done every year</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>The strategy is Very satisfactory in 2020 and 2021. Indeed, the record for 2020 is available at: https://www.nanogune.eu/sites/default/files/gender_report_2020_final_0.pdf</p> <p>A record for 2021 is available at: https://www.nanogune.eu/sites/default/files/1-2-7_2021_gender_report_final_2.pdf</p> <p>The record for 2022 has to be issued in 2023</p> <p>Moreover, a flyer with key information about the gender distribution and its development was generated and displayed on key locations at CIC nanoGUNE (interactions area, kitchen, entrance all, digital in the intranet, etc.) in 2020 and 2021.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	<p>Promote the gender-balanced participation of employees in communication actions and dissemination activities.</p>
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Promoting achievements of employees through communication channels and nominations for awards.</p>

<u>Indicators</u>	Gender distribution among the total of the events. (for events that have been communicated).
<u>Thresholds</u>	Satisfactory: 60:40 % (m:f or f:m) Very Satisfactory: 50:50 % (M:W)
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Unsatisfactory in 2020 as In 2020 the gender distribution was 66% males and 34% females. While in 2021 thi percentage was more balanced with 42% Males and 58 % Females. The the strategy was Satisfactory.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Collective/group-based mentoring with focus on gender equality.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Install informal discussions on a group level, to provide suggestions and information about requirements for the next step in a career. The discussions are led by seniors or invited external scientists.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of events per year
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory: $n \geq 2$ per year Satisfactory: $1 \leq n < 2$ per year Unsatisfactory: $n = 0$ per year
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is very satisfactory per number of events except for 2020, that was impacted by the COVID 19 pandemic. Indeed CIC Nanogune produced the following events: Number of events in 2019: 3, Carreer building (round table) Apr-19 Successful Women in science Jun-19 Industrial perspectives discussion Dec-19 Number of events in 2020: 0 (group meetings were limited due to pandemic), Number of events in 2021: 2, Carreer building (round table) Feb-21 Science to industry discussion Jun -21

	<p>Number of events in 2022: 3</p> <p>Carreer building (round table) Jan-22</p> <p>How to progress in R&D? (coffee seminar) Mar-22</p> <p>Discussion on equal opportunities in research Jun-22</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	One-to-one mentoring
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Identify professionals (both externals and internals) who would be willing to mentor and motivate our young researchers, particularly women. This will be done in collaboration with all senior scientists and the GEC.
<u>Indicators</u>	Established: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when established
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very Satisfactory as the program was established.</p> <p>Employees can assign for a one-to-one mentoring program where they jointly with the mentor define near-future career goals and monitor/refine those throughout their employment at nanoGUNE with a defined series of personal meetings. The program was established and launched in October 2021.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Sensibilize the employees to the gender dimension in research.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organize practical seminars on the gender dimension in research.
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>One each 2nd year (planned 2019 and 2022)</p> <p>Number of attendees</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory if done in 2019 and 2022

	<p>Very satisfactory: $60 \leq n \leq 70$</p> <p>Satisfactory: $50 \leq n < 60$</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: $n < 50$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Satisfactory as it was Very satisfactory for the organisation of one seminar in 2019 and also in terms of participants. Indeed, one seminar on Gender dimension in research was organized in May 2019 and more than 60 people attended.</p> <p>One seminar on Gender dimension in research is planned for the Autumn of 2022. Therefore we cannot provide any assessment on this respect.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Sensibilize the employees to gender equality in research.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organize periodic specific trainings (open to all employees) on gender equality in research
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of attendees
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory: $60 \leq n \leq 70$</p> <p>Satisfactory: $50 \leq n < 60$</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: $n < 50$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Satisfactory with 53 attendees</p> <p>Organization of training sessions with external consultants who discuss possible gender bias in research and how to avoid it. The session in March 2021 had 53 attendees (mainly online)</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Promoting gender balance among invited speakers of conferences organized by nanoGUNE.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	All conference organizers from nanoGUNE shall be requested to balance the gender distribution among the invited speakers at conferences
<u>Indicators</u>	Gender distribution among the invited speakers per organized conference.
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory when male:female distribution (%) is 50:50.</p> <p>Satisfactory when the gender distribution male:female or female:male is 60:40.</p>

	Unsatisfactory if the gender proportion (regardless of male or female) is below 40%
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Very Satisfactory for 2022 as the Organization of conferences by nanoGUNE personnel has just started as the years 2020 and 2021 were affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. The first live conference organized (Nano2022, Seville, Spain) (https://nano2022.org.es/functional-materials-by-thin-film-coatings) has invited speakers with female:male ratio of 60:40 (%).</p> <p>Further conferences are in the initial stage of organization and will have a balanced gender distribution.</p>
<u>GEP Area</u>	Work-life balance and organisational culture
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Definition of the responsibilities for implementation and communication of the GEP
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Assign the person who will be responsible for nanoGUNE's GEP and communicating it to all the employees.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Very satisfactory as the Responsible persons were assigned to the actions and GEP areas, and they are: 1) the Director</p> <p>2) the Finance Director</p> <p>3) the Outreach Manager</p> <p>4) the Research Director</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Arrange regular GEP follow-up meetings with the GEC
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Arrangement of joint meetings with the GEC and employees to follow-up and improve actions within the GEP.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of meetings per year
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory: $n \geq 2$ Satisfactory: $n = 1$ Unsatisfactory: $n = 0$
<u>Results and</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as the GEC organised more than 10 meetings from the

<u>Comments</u>	beginning of the project, and specific meetings with GEC were organised for follow-up One dedicated meeting was held in 2020 (Satisfactory) even if it was related to the picth of COVID 19 pandemic crisis, two in 2021 (Very satisfactory) and one in 2022 (by May), but consider that this is only for a half of the year.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Monitor the implementation of the GEP and create a yearly report that includes level of achievement of the foreseen objectives and actions.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Annual Report on the achievements of the foreseen objectives and actions
<u>Indicators</u>	Done per year: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done every year
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as reports for 2020 and 2021 were generated and available at: https://www.nanogune.eu/sites/default/files/gender_report_2020_final_0.pdf https://www.nanogune.eu/sites/default/files/1-2-7_2021_gender_report_final_2.pdf The report for 2022 is not generated as the year is not closed.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Include information about the institutional gender equality policies at the useful documents section of the intranet.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Generating a section in the intranet which contains all information about gender equality policies at nanoGUNE. The access is partially restricted to employees.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as the Documentation is available in the intranet at: (https://www.nanogune.eu/en/nanopeople/people/gender-equality).

<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Include the GEP into the next Strategic Plan of CIC nanoGUNE (2021- 2025).
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Inclusion of the gender dimension into the strategic planning of the institute’s research for the upcoming 5 years.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Satisfactory as the strategic plan is being written at the current (delayed due to Covid-19 to the end of 2022.). The GEP is included in the planning.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Include nanoGUNE’s commitment towards gender equality in the main documents of the entity (web page, etc.).
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Confirmation of the commitment of CIC nanoGUNE in documents and openly accessible portals, websites, etc.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory due to the Confirmation of the commitment of CIC nanoGUNE in documents and openly accessible portals, websites, etc. https://www.nanogune.eu/en/nanopeople/people/gender-equality
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Include gender equality criteria (equality clauses) for the subcontract of external services.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Agreements with subcontracted companies set up to include clauses on gender equality for the subcontracted work to be done.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as the document was approved and the clauses are part

<u>Comments</u>	of the quotations sent to customers.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Include the sex variable in all the administrative databases and forms used at nanoGUNE.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	All administrative databases regarding employees, subcontracted companies, seminars, guest researchers, etc. are extended by the sex variable.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy aiming tracking of the sex distribution for better statistics and monitoring is Very satisfactory as the sex variable has been incorporated into the new institute's database as of Oct. 2021
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Make sure all people-related data are disaggregated by sex at the biennial activity reports.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Biennial activity reports of CIC nanoGUNE contain statistical data on the institute's development and this data are disaggregated by sex to allow the reader of the report insight into the progress in gender distribution.
<u>Indicators</u>	Document approval done (Yes/No)
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done (Yes)
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Satisfactory as:</p> <p>Biennial activity reports of CIC nanoGUNE contain statistical data on the institute's development and this data are disaggregated by sex to allow the reader of the report insight into the progress in gender distribution</p> <p>One report was approved on 31 of December 2021 and it is available at https://www.nanogune.eu/sites/default/files/inline-files/activity_report_19-20_en_0.pdf</p> <p>The report for 2022 is being written and will be finalized towards end of 2022.</p>
<u>Gep</u>	Training about inclusive and gender sensitive communication.

<u>Strategy</u>	
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organize an explicative training session about the use of gender sensitive language in writing and speaking.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of attendees
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory: $40 \leq n$ Satisfactory: $15 \leq n < 25$ Unsatisfactory: $n < 15$
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory as the explicative training session about the use of gender sensitive language in writing and speaking was organised on 13 December 2021 and attended by 20 persons (limited attendancedue to the Covid-19 pandemic) in person and > 80 online.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Developing nanoGUNE's guidelines for an inclusive use of language at both external and internal communication.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Develop guidelines for inclusive use of language at both external and internal communication, both for written and visual communication. All official communication from nanoGUNE shall follow the guidelines.
<u>Indicators</u>	Document release done (Yes/No) Released documents of the organisation following the guidelines (Yes/No)
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done (Yes) Very satisfactory when done (Yes)
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory, indeed, CIC Nanogune developed guidelines for inclusive use of language at both external and internal communication, both for written and visual communication. They are described in a Document delivred at 1st of October 2021 and available in the intranet at: https://www.nanogune.eu/system/files/documentos-intranet/gep1-3-2_gender_inclusive_communication_communication_guidelines_0_0.pdf All released documents and all official communication from nanoGUNE is following the guidelines. Internal communication is overseen by all coworkers and the members of the GEC who remind employees on the guidelines on every possible occasion, in emails, seminars or announcements.

<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Review nanoGUNE's most relevant communications from a gender inclusive standing point, to verify that the guidelines are being followed.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Email templates, news, letters, responses (audio-visual), etc. shall be reviewed for consistency with the guidelines of gender sensitive communication.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory, indeed, the Email templates, news, letters, responses (audio-visual), etc. review has been done and new communications are persistently reviewed by the outreach manager. The link to them is: https://www.nanogune.eu/system/files/documentos-intranet/gep1-3-2_gender_inclusive_communication_communication_guidelines_0_0.pdf
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Develop communication campaigns to enhance women's contributions to research.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Communication campaigns shall be launched through social media to rise awareness about women in science and their contributions.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of campaigns per year
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory: $n \geq 2$ Satisfactory: $1 \leq n < 2$ Unsatisfactory: $n = 0$
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Satisfactory in 2020 with 1 campaign (3.01.2020), and Very satisfactory in 2021 with 3 campaigns (14.01.2021, 08.02.2021, 15.10.2021) and in 2022 with 4 campaigns (26.01.2022, 10.02.2022, 08.04.2022, 08.06.2022) The events of 2020, 2021 and 2022 were broadcasted on YouTube. In January, nanoGUNE launched the "Emakumeak Zientzian Instagram channel".
<u>Gep</u>	Make policy makers aware of potentially existing discriminatory effects in calls for grants

<u>Strategy</u>	and the need of promoting measures to make all calls inclusive.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Analyze potential discriminatory effects in calls for grants.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of reports to policy makers
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when no reports are needed.
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory as the analysis was done and not action was needed. No case identified by July 2022 The process is still ongoing for newly opened calls for grants.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Promote the offer of nursery/child-care facilities to attendants of conferences organized or co-organized by nanoGUNE.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Employees of nanoGUNE who (co)organize conferences shall promote the installation of nursery/child-care facilities to attendants who travel with children.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory. Nearly all conferences in 2020 and 2021 took place online due to Covid-19, there was no need for such facilities. In 2022 the conference Nano20226 held from 6 to 10. June 2022 organized again in person (and the nanoGUNE is co-organizers) was promoted nursery and childcare facilities installation.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Include in the useful-documents section existing work-life balance support measures available at the Centre.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Create a subsection with existing work-life balance support measures available at the Centre.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory. The section in the intranet was extended to have an

<u>Comments</u>	<p>overview over measures to support the work-life balance.</p> <p>Content of the section: as of July 2022: Regulations regarding meeting scheduling, telework, information about nearby nursery services and special conditions for nanoGUNE employees with registration forms.</p> <p>The link is: https://www.nanogune.eu/en/nanopeople/people/gender-equality/3-work-life-balance-gep</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Revision of documents of Pregnancy Protocol.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The pregnancy protocol shall be revised to include information about rights and obligations in an easily understandable way
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Document approval done:</p> <p>Yes/No</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory. The protocol was written and approved and is available in the documentation section in the intranet:</p> <p>https://www.nanogune.eu/en/nanopeople/safety-it/health-safety/maternity</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Offer the possibility to telework (if possible, depending on the position) if requested and required due to work-life balance issues.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The possibility to telework (if possible) shall be enabled, if requested and required due to work-life balance issues.
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Telework approval: Yes/No</p> <p>Number of employees benefiting from it</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory when approvevd</p> <p>Very satisfactory N>0</p>

<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory considering that it was approved in March 2020.</p> <p>Due to Covid-19, in parts of the years 2020-2022 teleworking was obligatory.</p> <p>It is also very satisfactory as employees used it even if we need to consider the influence of COVID 19 pandemic.</p> <p>Employees benefitting in 2019: 5%, in 2020: 44%, in 2021: 23%, in 2022: 12%. The numbers in 2020 and 2021 are higher and partly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Promote scheduling of meetings during core working hours (9-17).
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Request from the employees to organize meetings only in the core working hours and remind them regularly on the schedule
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Approval of the decision</p> <p>Annual e-mail to all employees as reminder to schedule meetings in core working hours</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory when approved</p> <p>Very satisfactory: $n \geq 1/\text{year}$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Very satisfactory considering all the indicators as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the decision to have company meetings from 9am to 5pm was approved in 2020 in 2020 meetings were arranged online due to Covid-19 pandemic. One reminder email has been sent in 2021. In 2022 this is yet to be done
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Agreement with nursery nearby for better rates.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	An agreement for a discount with a nursery nearby shall be achieved which provides nanoGUNE's employees a discount for childcare during the working days.
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Done:</p> <p>Yes/No</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done

<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Very satisfactory as the agreement was done in 2020. A 10% discount by a nursery was agreed upon and information about the nursery services added to the useful-documents section of the intranet. See the following link:</p> <p>https://www.nanogune.eu/en/nanopeople/people/gender-equality/3-work-life-balance-gep</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Encourage the mutual support of employees through the setting-up of a “family club” to be coordinated by volunteers and institutionally supported by the center.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The initiation of the family club shall be supported by the direction and time and meeting rooms allowed for regular meetings.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory as the family club was established at 15.01.2020</p> <p>However, regular meetings could not be established due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the resulting lack of personal interaction at CIC nanoGUNE.</p>
<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Training for the management team and hiring panels on equality and non-bias attitudes.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organize a training session for the management team and hiring panels on equality and non-bias attitudes.
<u>Indicators</u>	One training session per year
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: 0 training session/year</p> <p>Very satisfactory: 1 training session/year</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Very satisfactory for 2020 and 2021 as trainings related to “Awareness of unconscious bias upon hiring.” were held in 20/12/2020 and 21/11/2021.</p> <p>We do not have an evaluation for 2022 as the year is not finished.</p>

<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Adapt the hiring protocol to ensure equal opportunities.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	The responsible person is evaluating the applications and interviewing the shortlisted applicants. Upon selection a justification has to be made. The final hiring proposal is forwarded to the direction and the human resources who are overseeing the documentation and approving if the process was correct.
<u>Indicators</u>	Protocol adoption: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when adopted
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Very satisfactory:</p> <p>A protocol was implemented into the intranet hiring system of nanoGUNE. The protocol was first introduced in 2019 and updated in Oct. 2021. The protocol is now part of the internal hiring system.</p> <p>The protocol is implemented into the online forms for hiring in the intranet, i.e., a hiring process can't be concluded without evaluation of the competences of the candidate and justification why the selection was done, especially with respect to gender and further factors of relevance.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Inclusive writing of job profiles.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Create a template to ensure the inclusive writing of job profiles and attract a diverse pool of candidates. nanoGUNE's gender-equality policy and compromise should be stated in the template.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>A template for text passages of all kinds of job offers (scientific, technical, administrative) was defined to explicitly encourage application from the underrepresented gender. It was produced at 1st of October 2021.</p> <p>The template is included into the online form in the intranet which is filled by the seniors with specific information about the job. The job offer is generated by the system and controlled/revised by the administration for the appropriate writing before publication.</p> <p>The offers are published at: https://www.nanogune.eu/en/nanogune/join-us</p>

<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Training on team management and problem solving considering the gender perspective.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organize training sessions on team management and problem solving considering the gender perspective.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of attendees
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory: $n \geq 10$ Satisfactory: $8 \leq n < 10$ Unsatisfactory: $n < 8$
<u>Results and Comments</u>	Unsatisfactory till now. Indeed activities related to this strategy are postponed due to Covid-19. Planned for Autumn 2022 Are expected 15 participants
<u>GEP Area</u>	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Protect from abuse and gender based or sexual harassment.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Definition of a protocol to protect from abuse harassment/sexual harassment.
<u>Indicators</u>	Established: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when established
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very Satisfactory as a protocol was established with clear processes and personnel to be contacted in case of occurrence of any sort of gender based or sexual harassment. Link to the protocol https://www.nanogune.eu/en/nanopeople/safety-it/health-safety/sexual-gender-based-anti-harassment-protocol
<u>Gep</u>	Definition of responsible individuals who will be counsellors in casa of sexual and gender-

<u>Strategy</u>	based harassment.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Identify individuals who will be responsible for sexual and gender-based sexist harassment at nanoGUNE and communicate the names to all the employees.
<u>Indicators</u>	Communication to employees and deposit of information in the intranet done. (Yes/No)
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when communication was done and the link to the protocol has been published
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Very Satisfactory as confidential counsellors were identified among the permanently employed coworkers and an email address for communicating cases of harassment was installed. Posters with information were designed and were displayed in all aggregation areas of CIC nanoGUNE.</p> <p>The counsellors were introduced to the employees in a general seminar and their names are stated in the respective section in the intranet and on posters regarding the protocol, which are displayed at nanoGUNE.</p> <p>The link to the protocol was sent to all employees by email on 05.04.2022 and a dedicated seminar and introduction of the confidential counsellors was done on 09.05.2022.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Training of key personnel on sexual and gender-based harassment issues.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organize a specific training on sexual and gender-based sexist harassment for the confidential counsellors, managers, and senior scientists to provide them with the necessary resources and knowledge to face cases of harassment.
<u>Indicators</u>	Training done: Yes/No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when training done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very Satisfactory as a training was done on 20.07.2020
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Follow-up on the protocol for sexual and gender-based sexist harassment.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Follow up the protocol for sexual and gender-based sexist harassment, make biennial reports, and send them to The Basque Institute for Women (Emakunde).

<u>Indicators</u>	Biennial report sent to Emakunde (Yes/No)
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when report is sent
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Unsatisfactory as the protocol definition was delayed and published only in April 2022, thus the report is delayed to 2023.

MIGAL's GEP

<u>GEP Area</u>	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	English workshops with a special mentor woman for improving speech and professional writing.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	One workshop was organised. A professional instructor acts as a mentor and guide in English. The strategy aimed to allow the young female researchers to have a personal mentor to get a professional guide in their career pass. In the beginning, 4 female researchers choose an English mentor teacher. Then we brought her to give a one-year workshop for all female researchers that wish to join. About 10 researchers agreed.
<u>Indicators</u>	Done: Yes, No
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	10 Women researchers who participated in the workshop reported a significant improvement in writing, speaking, and giving lectures in scientific English.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	All of MIGAL job publications submitted since the approval of the GEP are written in a gender-sensitive language and as well as in bilingual language.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	MIGAL integrates the idea of reducing the gender gap and raising awareness of gender equality within the organisation. The use of gender-sensitive language in MIGAL is part of an expanding cultural attitude in Israel. Since the Hebrew language consists of the prominent use of two separate genders and the form of expression prevalent to this day has been the use of a masculine suffix for most of the population, it is necessary to construct a different writing method and use adapted words

<u>Indicators</u>	Very satisfactory when done in a systematic way
<u>Thresholds</u>	There is not a specific threshold for this action. It is considered very satisfactory if the action is systematically done.
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Very satisfactory as, job and internal/external publications submitted since the approval of the GEP are written in a gender-sensitive language. MIGAL encouraged women to apply for jobs in job announcement texts. This was done by implementing a change in the form of writing these announcements so that they would be written in a gender-sensitive language, rather than in a male language. Through this change, we are now able to reach a more significant number of women candidates.</p> <p>Links to Job publications are:</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/migal.research</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/migal-galilee-research-institute/jobs/</p>
<u>GEP Area</u>	Work-life balance and organisational culture
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Strengthen the connection among all employees
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Joint meetings were organised for MIGAL personnel
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Number of workshops per year</p> <p>Number of Women and Men who attended each workshop</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory N workshops= 0</p> <p>Satisfactory $1 \leq N \text{ workshops} < 4$</p> <p>Very Satisfactory $N \text{ workshop} \geq 4$</p> <p>Unsatisfactory $N W < 8$ and $N M < 6$</p> <p>Satisfactory $8 \leq N W < 15$, $6 \leq N M < 10$</p> <p>Very Satisfactory $NW \geq 15F$ and $N M \geq 10M$</p>
<u>Results and</u>	This strategy was Satisfactory for the Number of workshop organised in 2018, 2019 and

<p>Comments</p>	<p>2020, while the Number of participants disaggregated per gender and year was Very satisfactory.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information day 25 October 2018 20 18 38 Information day Midterm conference focused on gender 15 July 2019 35 Women and 25Men attended the Midterm conference focused on gender - CEO of MIGAL congratulated the project, Dr. Sigal Fishman present the R&I PEERS project and Ms. Aviv Elbaz Nudel spoke of equality from her point of view as a woman and a mother. Two woman researchers participating in the project talked about how they are doing research and how the project's workshops help and support the improvement of their abilities. At the end of the meeting, we heard the attorney Tamar Gutgold Cohen her lecture on gender equality laws in Israel. https://www.facebook.com/migal.research/videos/486105688857844/?t=25 Writing workshop for Horizon 2020, 21 August 2019, 12 Women and 16 Men attended the Writing workshop for Horizon 2020 1th Workshops: Managing ourselves in time, 08 September 2019, 19 Women and 8 Men attended the 1st Workshops: Managing ourselves in time 2nd Workshops: Managing ourselves in time, 15 September 2019 19 Women and 8 Men attended the 2nd Workshops: Managing ourselves in time "Academic writing workshop", organised in 2020, 18 Women and 12 Men attended the workshop <p>The organisational culture is in the hands of key actors and decision-makers, regional authorities and researchers. It directly affects the work-life balance of all employees at the organisation, including technical and administrative staff, students and families of researchers.</p>
<p>GEP Area</p>	<p>Gender equality in recruitment and career progression</p>
<p>Gep Strategy</p>	<p>MIGAL chose a group of young female researchers to promote them and their abilities/skills in a special course designed for them.</p>
<p>Implements Actions</p>	<p>15 female researchers were chosen for this special course.</p> <p>In that course, we gave them a variety of workshops.</p> <p>After the first year, we opened those workshops to more participants from MIGAL.</p>
<p>Indicators</p>	<p>Number of Women who had evidences of progresses in their abilities and skills.</p>

Thresholds	<p>Unsatisfactory $N W < 3$</p> <p>Satisfactory $3 \leq N W < 8$</p> <p>Very Satisfactory $N W \geq 8$</p>
Results and Comments	<p>MIGAL chose a group of young female researchers to promote them and their abilities/skills in a special course designed for them. This project includes workshops, seminars, special professional lessons to give the researchers special skills that allow them to do their work professionally and to provide them with tools to do a special SME project. The project started at the beginning of October 2018; it concentrated on specific strategies defined in the project.</p> <p>Out of 15 researchers selected to participate in the project, 7 have been promoted professionally or have expressed their professional abilities. Some researchers obtained some progress with academic writing and received a raise in their salaries. <u>The activity was satisfactory as 7 females who attended have been promoted professionally or have expressed their professional abilities.</u></p> <p>Info related to the workshops organised are the following (Title of the Workshop, Date of the Workshop, Number of Females attending the workshop, Number of Males attending the workshop, Total number of people attending the workshop, Description, Links to other information and materials (pictures, leaflet, videos, etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information day, 25 October 2018, total participants 38 • How to design a project, 28 March 2019, 18 women, Workshop -2nd Project Design-How to design a project, https://www.facebook.com/migal.research/posts/2335835999800228 • Enhancing presenting abilities 02 May 2019 18 women, Workshop - Enhancing presenting abilities_Eidit Noyderfer, https://www.facebook.com/redheadpresenter/ • 1th Academic writing workshop, 16 May 2019, 18 women, 1st Academic writing workshop - Mentoring young women researchers to write good proposal • 2nd Academic writing workshop, 06 June 2019, 18 women, 2nd Academic writing workshop • 3rd Academic writing workshop June 2019/2019 • Commercialization 07 July 2019, 18 women, Commercialization • Midterm conference focused on gender, 15 July 2019, Participants 60, Midterm conference focused on gender - CEO of MIGAL congratulated the project, Dr. Sigal Fishman present the R&I PEERS project and Ms. Aviv Elbaz Nudel spoke of equality from her point of view as a woman and a mother. Two woman researchers participating in the project talked about how they are doing research and how the project's workshops help and support the improvement of their abilities. At the end of the meeting, we heard the attorney Tamar Gutgold Cohen her lecture on gender equality laws in Israel. https://www.facebook.com/migal.research/videos/486105688857844/?t=2 • Writing workshop for Horizon 2020 21 August 2019, 12 Women, 16 Men attended Writing workshop for Horizon 2020 • 1th Workshops: Managing ourselves in time 08 September 2019 19

	<p>Women and 8 Men attended the 1st Workshops: Managing ourselves in time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2nd Workshops: Managing ourselves in time, 15 September 2019, 19 Women and 8Men attended the 2nd Workshops: Managing ourselves in time • Organisational Consultant, ODT activity, experiential learning 22 September 2019, 18 Women attended the Organisational Consultant, ODT activity, experiential learning • Writing an academic article November 2019, 18 women attended, Writing an academic article • 4th Academic writing workshop 16 July 2020, 5 women attended the 4th Academic writing workshop • Guidance for submitting grants to BSF, 26 July 2020, wide Public Guidance for submitting grants to BSF • How to write a winning ISF proposal 10 August 2020, 6 Women and 12 Men attended. • EU Researchers' Night, 03 December 2020, Wide Public EU Researchers' Night- MIGAL researchers participated in an evening dedicated entirely to making science and research accessible to the public and especially to the younger generation. MIGAL researchers recorded some of the activities and some were done live. Sigal presented the R&I peers project. https://www.facebook.com/migal.research/posts/3713357118714769 <p>This strategy was Satisfactory. The young female researchers participated in a course to promote their abilities/skills in a special workshop designed for them. Several researchers have made progress with academic writing and received a raise in their salaries; one even won as a coordinator in Horizon 2020 project. Some of the workshops did not open at the time of the Pandemic.</p>
<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	<p>Workshops on the importance of promoting and supporting the career of women researchers.</p> <p>Several workshops were organised about the importance of promoting and supporting the career of women researchers. These workshops dealt with issues such as promoting the presence of women in decision-making bodies.</p>
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Workshops in 2019 in MIGAL to promote female researchers and their abilities/skills in a unique course designed for them
<u>Indicators</u>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of workshops per Year 2. Number of women leading teams 3. Number of women in the decision-making process
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory N workshops= 0</p> <p>Satisfactory $1 \leq N \text{ workshops} < 4$</p> <p>Very Satisfactory, N workshops ≥ 4</p>

	<p>Unsatisfactory N Women <4 and N Men <3</p> <p>Satisfactory $4 \leq N \text{ Women} < 10$ and $3 \leq N \text{ Men} < 7$</p> <p>Very Satisfactory N Women ≥ 10 and N Men ≥ 7</p> <p>Number of Women leading teams:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory N W <2</p> <p>Satisfactory $2 \leq N \text{ W} < 4$</p> <p>Very satisfactory NW ≥ 4</p> <p>Number of Women in the decision-making process:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory N W <2</p> <p>Satisfactory $2 \leq N \text{ W} < 6$</p> <p>Very satisfactory NW ≥ 6</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was very satisfactory during 2020 per Number of workshops organised, and satisfactory in terms of attendees.</p> <p>It was unsatisfactory in the other years.</p> <p>It was also Very satisfactory as Women researchers were promoted in their professional positions with:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of Women leading teams: 5 2. Number of Women in the decision-making process: 9
<u>GEP Area</u>	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishing institutional mechanisms to combat gender-based violence and clear and transparent protocols to address these issues.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Regular organisation of workshops on how to include gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

<u>Indicators</u>	
<u>Thresholds</u>	
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>The activity consists of an ongoing and continuous organisation of workshops on how to preclude gender-based violence and sexual harassment.</p> <p>In MIGAL, we achieve a better gender-friendly environment for all employees.</p>

ZRC SAZU's GEP

<u>GEP Area</u>	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishing mechanisms to provide advising on integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching
<u>Implements Actions</u>	All step of the process for appointing a GE officer and informing the staff of the organisation
<u>Indicators</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender Equality counsellor officially appointed • Employees informed about the appointment and GE officer's role and responsibilities
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very ssatisfactory when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender Equality counsellor officially appointed • Employees informed
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory, as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GE advisor has been appointed in February 2022. The roles are: monitoring GEP implementation, advising project applicants on gender dimension in research, and organizing trainings on gender equality. • Employees were informed about the appointment and GE officer's role and responsibilities: https://www.zrc-sazu.si/en/node/102609
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Publication of an educational book dedicated to female researchers (from Slovenia and the region, in historical perspective)
<u>Implements</u>	Organisation of all phases for producing the book. The action aims at raising awareness of GE at the institution and also among general public, as the publication is written in a

<u>Actions</u>	popular and accessible way.
<u>Indicators</u>	Publication of the Book
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when the book is published
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as the book is in production phase. Publication expected in October 2022. The book will make visible the role of women in establishing infrastructures for research, new fields and approaches. It contributes to the community building of female researchers in the area of former Yugoslavia
<u>GEP Area</u>	Work-life balance and organisational culture
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular statistics to gain insight into the extent of the use of available services, particularly those provided by the institution (summer research workshops for kids, recreational options, sport days, etc.).
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Regular data collection and production of gender segregated statistic of attendance for: summer research workshops for kids, recreational options and sport days. The action focuses on provisions for healthy life and recreation at the workplace; provides a feedback on the offer to improve health and well-being: sport trainings, lectures, medical checkups, sport days, special days dedicated to mental and physical health.
<u>Indicators</u>	Report prepared Report presented to DMB
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when the report prepared and presented to DMB Satisfactory when produced but not presented to DMB
<u>Results and Comments</u>	These statistics were completed for 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021 and included in the report.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Yearly needs analysis (questionnaire)
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Actions aiming getting an insight into employees needs in order to provide them with suitable recreational and health-related content. Administration of a questionnaire and analysis of data collected.

<u>Indicators</u>	<p>1) Yearly analysis carried out: Yes/No</p> <p>Number of respondents (gender segregated)</p> <p>2) Analysis incorporated into report offering insight into extent of use of available services and presented to DMB</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very Satisfactory when yearly needs are collected and respondent are >70, • Satisfactory when yearly needs are collected and respondent are >50 and <=70, or when 1 time each two year data are collected • Unsatisfactory when yearly needs are collected and respondent are <50 or data are not collected in the last 2 years • Satisfactory Number of respondents (gender segregated) <p>2) Very Satisfactory when the analysis incorporated into a report offering insight into extent of use of available services and presented to DMB</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was very satisfactory for 2020 and 2021, when the yearly analysis was carried out. It is not already implemented in 2022. It was very satisfactory also considering the number of respondents; indeed, in 2020 121 people (22 Men, 99 Women) provided their answers, while in 2021 95 people (18 Men, 77 Women) answered.</p> <p>Moreover, the analysis incorporated into report making the strategy very satisfactory also in this respect.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Increasing availability of work from home and flexible working hours
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Actions aiming at reducing differences among institutes in availability of work from home
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of institutes within ZRC SAZU where flexible working hours are widely available
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very Satisfactory: all the institutes</p> <p>Satisfactory: N of institutes=15 institutes</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: N of institutes<15</p>

<u>Results and Comments</u>	In 2018 9 (out of 18), and in 2019 10 9 (out of 18) institutes made available the possibility to work from home and to use flexible working hours. Since 2020, all employees at the institutes and management have an option of work from home.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Survey of changes in the employees' needs caused by the Covid-19 pandemic
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Administration of a questionnaire and analysis of data related to the actual needs of employees in the area of work-life balance conditioned by the Covid-19 pandemic aims at getting an insight into reality of work conditions defined by covid-19 pandemic and lessons learned from it. It is a one-time action that should help ZRC SAZU management to devise suitable strategies of work organization.
<u>Indicators</u>	Survey conducted and the results presented to DMB
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when Survey conducted and the Results presented to DMB Satisfactory when Survey conducted but the Results are not presented
<u>Results and Comments</u>	A modified GEAM survey was completed from September to December 2021 in order to get a better insight into actual needs of employees in the area of work-life balance conditioned by the Covid-19 pandemic. The analysis of survey results presented to all employees and DMB in May 2022. The analysis is available at: https://spoliznanost.zrc-sazu.si/porocilo-o-anketi-na-podrocju-enakosti-spolov-na-zrc-sazu/
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Development and implementation of gender-sensitive models in a specific set of documents at ZRC SAZU
<u>Implements Actions</u>	All actions focused on official communication and documents that address particular persons – at the starting point, the person was always addressed with masculine forms which are considered unmarked/gender neutral.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of documents updated
<u>Thresholds</u>	Number of documents (n) (types) updated (overall): Unsatisfactory $n < 7$ Satisfactory $7 \leq n < 12$ Very satisfactory $12 \leq n \leq 16$

<p><u>Results and Comments</u></p>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory. 14 templates for personal documents and 1 policy document have been changed and produced in a Gender sensitive perspective. They are available online:</p> <p>2019 Education agreement http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2020 Review form for the election to a research degree http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2020 Training agreement http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Annual leave notification http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Agreement on increased workload http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Resolution of the ZS for the appointment of Head of Institute http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Resolution of the Director for the appointment of Head of Institute http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Employment contract and annexes http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Resolution on election to a research degree http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Application for election to a research degree http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Cessation of employment agreement http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Annual evaluation to determine the merit component of salary http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2021 Decision http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p> <p>2022 Rules and Procedures for the Ethics, Integrity and Equal Opportunities in Research Commission http://zrcalo11.zrc-sazu.si/</p>
<p><u>GEP Area</u></p>	<p>Gender equality in recruitment and career progression</p>
<p><u>Gep Strategy</u></p>	<p>Yearly gender-segregated statistics on indicators of career paths of early-career researchers (the number of new young researchers and post-docs; the number of graduates; the number of those who left ZRC SAZU and of those who stayed after their PhD/post-doc project).</p>
<p><u>Implements Actions</u></p>	<p>Regular collection of statistical data</p>
<p><u>Indicators</u></p>	<p>Collection per Year</p>

<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory 1 per year
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>The data were collected for 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021 and presented at the Board of heads of institutes. Data and the trends are publicly available at ZRC SAZU's website.</p> <p>2018 1 February 2019, https://www.zrc-sazu.si/sites/default/files/statistika%20MR%20in%20postdoc%202018-21.pdf</p> <p>2019 3 February 2020, https://www.zrc-sazu.si/sites/default/files/statistika%20MR%20in%20postdoc%202018-21.pdf</p> <p>2020 1 February 2021, https://www.zrc-sazu.si/sites/default/files/statistika%20MR%20in%20postdoc%202018-21.pdf</p> <p>2021 1 February 2022 https://www.zrc-sazu.si/sites/default/files/statistika%20MR%20in%20postdoc%202018-21.pdf</p> <p>2022 1 February 2023 will be available in February 2023</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular trainings for mentors
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Regular training aimed at providing mentors with capacities for adequate early academic socialization of mentees. This is significant because among senior research staff at ZRC SAZU, mentoring is still largely understood as bringing a mentee to the successful completion of the PhD thesis.
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Number of realised trainings per year</p> <p>Number of attendees per training</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Number of realised trainings per year: 1</p> <p>Number of attendees per training:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory men<1 women <4</p> <p>Satisfactory: 4<=women<=7 1<=men<=3</p> <p>Very satisfactory 8<=women<=13 4<=men<=7</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>In the period from 2020 till 2022 no training has been implemented yet due to Covid-19 imposed restrictions.</p> <p>This strategy was Very satisfactory in 2019. Indeed, trainings were carried out during 2019. In particular the training workshop titled “Skillful in communication - skills for more successful work” was held on 28 May, 20 June, 3 October, 10 October 2019</p>

	<p>These workshops were respectively attended as follows: 28 May 2019: 24 (6 Men, 16 Women) 20 June 2019: (22 (8 Men, 14 Women), 3 October 2019: 17 (3 Men, 14 Women) 10 October 2019: 12 (3 Men, 12 Women)</p> <p>The training workshop titled “Selected Leadership Skills Workshop” was held on 2 October, 8 October 2019. These workshops were respectively attended as follows: 2 October 2019: 10 (10 F), 8 October: 9 (3 M, 6 F)</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular workshops for grant and project application writing
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Regular trainings aimed at providing early career researchers with capacities to obtain grants. Relevant because ZRC SAZU has relatively small number of in-house PhD graduates and post-docs receiving international grants and projects (female researchers particularly precarious/vulnerable at early career stages)
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Number (n) of realised workshops per year</p> <p>Number of attendees per training</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Number (n) of realised workshops per year:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: $n < 1$</p> <p>Satisfactory: $1 \leq n \leq 2$</p> <p>Very satisfactory $n > 2$</p> <p>Number of attendees per training:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: women < 6, men < 3</p> <p>Satisfactory: $7 \leq \text{women} \leq 13$, $4 \leq \text{men} \leq 6$ men</p> <p>Very satisfactory $14 \leq \text{women} \leq 23$, $7 \leq \text{men} \leq 10$ men</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was very satisfactory in 2019 and Satisfactory from 2020 to 2022 per Number of seminars organised.</p> <p>It was Very Satisfactory also considering the Number of attendees in 2019 and Satisfactory from 2020 to 2022</p>

	<p>Seminars done were:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Workshop with Dean Vuletić on applications for international fellowships (22 February 2019), 12 participants, 10 Women, 2 Men 2. Workshop on project writing for Horizon2020 Projects with Dr. Sean McCarthy (5 February 2019) 31 participants, 19 Women, 12 Men 3. Workshop on key skills for a successful project application with prof. dr. Carla Guerrón-Montero (3 April 2019), 20 participants (gender structure un available) 4. ERC Yellow Research Seminar, in cooperation with the Ljubljana University, with Lotte Jaspers, 13 participants (8 Women, 5 Men) 5. Seminar on project application writing, with Gill Wells, 17 June 2019; 11 participant (9 Women, 2 Men) 6. Seminar on administrative support for project management, in cooperation with the Ljubljana University with Gill Wells, 17 June 2019, 7 participants, all Women 7. ERC seminars held on 30 May 2019, 6 October 2020, , 13 and 14 October 2021, 16 June 2022 These workshops attracted a significant number of participants (about 15)
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular workshops for improving academic writing
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organising workshops aiming at building capacities of early career researchers for competitive research
<u>Indicators</u>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Number of workshops organized 2) Number of participants per each workshop
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory Number of workshops organized >1</p> <p>Satisfactory Number of workshops organized=1</p> <p>Very satisfactory Number of participants per each workshop >10</p> <p>Satisfactory 5>Number of workshops organized>=10</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Satisfactory for the Number of workshops organised in 2020 (1) and Very Satisfactory for the Number of participants per Workshops. In 2021 strategy was Satisfactory for the Number of workshops organised (1 workshop in three days involved) and people involved (12 people).

	<p>These workshops organised were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop: Science - between research integrity and plagiarism – 12 November 2020 111 (26 M, 85 F) • Workshops titled “Writing and publication strategies for Anglophone audiences” – September-October 2021 (10 September, 24 September, 1 October 2021 12) (5M, 7 F) <p>It was visible the trend in the improvement of high quality publications on the institutional level</p>						
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Yearly workshops on promotion criteria and how to achieve them						
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organisation of one workshop per year answering to the need to plan one's career strategically and in advance, which is particularly relevant for early career researchers (and female researchers as particularly precarious/vulnerable at early career stages)						
<u>Indicators</u>							
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Very satisfactory when the Number of realised workshops per year = 1</p> <p>Number of participants per workshop:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: 0-3 men 0-12 women</p> <p>Satisfactory: 13<=women <15, 4<=men<7</p> <p>Very satisfactory: 15<=women <23, 7<=men<10</p>						
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory for the Number of workshops organised in 2019 and 2020 as the following 2 workshops were organised:</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>Workshop for the newly employed</td> <td>26 November 2019</td> <td>30 (8M, 21 F)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Workshop for the newly employed</td> <td>16 December 2020</td> <td>17 (7M, 10 F)</td> </tr> </table> <p>The strategy was Satisfactory in 2019 for the number of participants (both for Men and Women and Unsatisfactory in 2020 for Women, even if in 2020 the COVID-19 pandemic influenced this aspect.</p> <p>In 2021 the workshop has not been held due to Covid-19 imposed restrictions</p>	Workshop for the newly employed	26 November 2019	30 (8M, 21 F)	Workshop for the newly employed	16 December 2020	17 (7M, 10 F)
Workshop for the newly employed	26 November 2019	30 (8M, 21 F)					
Workshop for the newly employed	16 December 2020	17 (7M, 10 F)					
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Promoting the visibility of female scientists through special PR campaigns and special channels of social media						
<u>Implements</u>	Organisation of events and campaigns aiming to respond to the disbalance detected at ZRC SAZU, where men are prioritized over women and senior researcher over younger						

<u>Actions</u>	ones in awarding and recognition for achievements and in publicizing and promotion of their work. It aims at increasing visibility of female and early career researchers and their achievements
<u>Indicators</u>	Number (n) of posts/campaigns realised per year
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Number of campaigns</p> <p>Very satisfactory 1 per year</p> <p>Number of posts</p> <p>Unsatisfactory $n < 6$ Satisfactory $6 \leq n < 8$ Very satisfactory $8 \leq n < 16$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory considering the number of campaign per year with the organization of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "ZRC: we are women too" on the promotion of science from a gender perspective. (2019) • "Organization of the campaign for promotion outstanding results by female researchers at ZRC SAZU in 2020 (https://spolinznanozrc-sazu.si/zrc-sazu/)" • Organization of the event for the International Women's Day (8 March 2021): od tovarne do pisarne in drugod • "ZRC Atrium exhibition ""Women in Mathematics - Portrait Gallery" (2022) <p>2 women received the Members of Honour award in last 4 years (vs. 0 women in the period 1998-2018)</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organizing events to promote female researchers (girls/women in science activities and programmes)
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Actions such as events or exhibitions are implemented to reduce the disbalance detected at ZRC SAZU, where men are prioritized over women and senior researcher over younger ones in awarding and recognition for achievements and in publicizing and promotion of their work. It aims at increasing visibility of female and early career researchers and their achievements
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of events organized per year
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when the Number of events organized per year = 1
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory for all Years, except for 2020, when the pandemic impacted the activities.</p> <p>The event «Science is female, too» was organized – a talk with four excellent female researchers from ZRC SAZU on promotion of research results; the event held on 20 May</p>

	<p>2019</p> <p>“Women's work: from the factory to the office and beyond” was held on 8 March 2021. It received 226 views. It was an online conversation. https://spolinznanst.zrc-sazu.si/zrc-sazu/delo-zensk-od-tovarne-do-pisarne-in-drugod/</p> <p>ZRC Atrium exhibition "Women in Mathematics - Portrait Gallery" was held on 11 February 2022. 20 people attended. In the occasion of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, on February 11, 2022, we opened the exhibition "Women in Mathematics - Portrait Gallery", co-organized with the Society of Mathematicians, Physicists and Astronomers of Slovenia https://spolinznanst.zrc-sazu.si/zenske-v-matematiki-galerija-portretov-razstava-in-okrogla-miza-ob-mednarodnem-dnevu-deklet-in-zensk-v-znanosti/</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular trainings for young researchers on how to communicate their research results to the media and broader audiences.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Organisation of regular training activities that aims at mitigating sometimes conservative approach of the PR officers, or their inability/unwillingness to intervene into existing promotion practices shaped by authoritative senior researchers. It aims at strengthening researchers' competences to promote their results and achievements themselves
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Number of realised trainings per year</p> <p>Number of attendees per training</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Number of realised trainings per year:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory n=0</p> <p>Satisfactory n=1 per year</p> <p>Very satisfactory n>1 per year</p> <p>Number of attendees per training:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory women<4, men <1</p> <p>Satisfactory: 4<=women<7 1<= men<3</p> <p>Very satisfactory 7<=women<=13, 3<=men<=7</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory in 2020. 2 trainings were done in 2020. In particular, the presentation skills for researchers and scientists was held on 22 and 23 January 2020. On 22 January 24 people attended (7M, 17F), and on 23 January 16 people attended (3M, 13F). In 2021 the training has not been held due to Covid-19 imposed restrictions.</p> <p>In 2022 the organisation did not already actions.</p>

<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Policy on ethics, equal opportunities, and integrity in research.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Actions for the adoption of policies
<u>Indicators</u>	Adoption of a policy
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when adopted
<u>Results and Comments</u>	Officially adopted in June 2022, the policy enabled the establishment of the Commission for ethics, equal opportunities and integrity in research
<u>GEP Area</u>	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishing the Commission for ethics, integrity, and equal opportunities in research
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Actions for the establishment of the commission
<u>Indicators</u>	Establishment of the Commission
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when established Satisfactory if steps started and planned to end in 2022
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Satisfactory, as the steps for the membership selection are planned to finish at the end of August 2022.
<u>GEP Area</u>	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Appointing a Gender Equality Advisor
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Actions for appointing the GE advisor
<u>Indicators</u>	Gender Equality Advisor appointed:Yes/No

<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when a Gender Equality Advisor is appointed
<u>Results and Comments</u>	GE advisor has been appointed in February 2022. See the link at: https://www.zrc-sazu.si/en/node/102609
<u>GEP Area</u>	Measures against Gender-Based Violence, including Sexual Harassment
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Code of conduct in the case of gender-based violence and sexual harassment: update of existing regulation.
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Actions and discussion for the Code of conduct in the case of gender-based violence and sexual harassment
<u>Indicators</u>	Code of conduct approved and adopted
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when approved and adopted Satisfactory when preparatory work is running
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This measure is satisfactory as the activities to build this code started. The code will be approved and adopted at the end of 2023.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Needs analysis in the field combating gender-related violence and sexual harassment
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Actions for collecting and analysing data.
<u>Indicators</u>	Analysis done, analysis presented
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when the analysis is done and presented Satisfactory when the analysis is done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as a modified GEAM survey was completed from September to December 2021. The analysis of survey results presented to all employees and DMB in May 2022.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishing channels for anonymously reporting disrespectful behaviour, abuse, and sexual harassment.
<u>Implements</u>	Action to establish the responsibility of the Commission for ethics, integrity, and equal

<u>Actions</u>	opportunities in research
<u>Indicators</u>	Channels for reporting established and functional
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfying when Channels for reporting are established and functional
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy can be considered Satisfactory. The process is active. This is under the responsibility of the Commission for ethics, integrity, and equal opportunities in research; to be established by December 2023

ANPR's GEP

<u>GEP Area</u>	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular trainings for mentors
<u>Implementations</u>	Regular (annual or twice a year) trainings for mentors would secure sustainability of the measures and on the long run reduce resistance on mentors' side (since often they believe that they are doing enough to teach their colleagues) and raise their awareness of the need of continuous acquiring of new mentoring skills and competence development. It's to favour a widespread gender competence at all levels of the organization with provision of mentoring training to Senior staff.
<u>Indicators</u>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of trainings/workshops organized/participated in per year 2. Number of participants per each training
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Number (n) of trainings per year:</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: n=0</p> <p>Satisfactory: n=1</p> <p>Very satisfactory: n>=2</p> <p>Number (n) of participants per year:</p>

	<p>Unsatisfactory n=0</p> <p>Satisfactory $1 < n \leq 6$</p> <p>Very satisfactory: $n > 6$</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>The implementation of the strategy was Satisfactory for the Number of trainings per year and for the number of participants (from 2019 to 2021). Training related to 2022 have to be organised.</p> <p>The training from 2019 to 2021 are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in European Research and Innovation Days conference, held 24-26 September 2019. This training was attended by 1 person (Woman). The link to materials is https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/events/upcoming-events/european-research-and-innovation-days_en • Open Collaborative course: Gender Equality in research and innovation: the journey towards Institutional Change, held 1st June – 26th July 2020. This training was attended by 1 person (Woman). The link to materials is https://ge-academy.eu/doccc/ • Gender Data Series (Online): Mitigating the impact of COVID-19 on women and girls, held May -July 2020. This training was attended by 3 persons (2 Women and 1 man). The link to materials is https://pages.devex.com/gender-data-covid19 • Online training “How to communicate "gender" in times of resistance”, held 28 April 2021. This training was attended by 3 persons (Women). The link to materials is https://ge-academy.eu/how-to-communicate-gender/ <p>This produced:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of mentors • Empowerment of mentors • Capacity of mentors de coach their colleagues
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organisation and participation in events on relevance of gender dimension in Research area
<u>Implementments Action</u>	Participation in: many events such as

<p>s</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stand on GE organised in Fair (HL event with DG RTD-EC) • ANPR GEP presented in H2020 SWAFS infoday • online workshop organised in European Researchers’ Night • international Woman Day • international African Woman Day <p>Organisation of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 02 workshops merged and organized as part of one (01) workshop in 2019 • ANPR Flagship Event: Gender equality facing the challenges of the R&I ecosystem – The GENDER EQUALITY PLAN of ANPR
<p>Indicators</p>	<p>Number of achieved events per year</p> <p>Number of beneficiaries per event and gender</p>
<p>Thresholds</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unsatisfactory: Number of achieved events per year<1 • Satisfactory: Number of achieved events per year=1 • Very satisfactory: Number of achieved events per year>1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unsatisfactory: women<=10, men<=3 participants per events • Satisfactory: 11<=women<=20, 4<=men<=10 participants per events • Very satisfactory: women >20, men >10 participants per events
<p>Results and Comments</p>	<p>The implementation of the strategy was Very satisfactory as can be observed considering the following events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H2020 infoday 21 February 2018 more than 70 participants (F+M) more than 70 participants (F+M) • Conference under H2020 TARGET project: TAKing a Reflexive approach to Gender Equality for institutional Transformation 07 December 2018 more than 40 participants (F+M) more than 40 participants (F+M) • Workshop on SWAFS Calls-H2020 10 January 2019 more than 20 participants (F+M) 18 participants (F+M) • Participation in the Conference : Tunisian-European Science and Innovation days [TESI]

	<p>9-10 September 2019 General public: 500-1000 (F+M) General public: 500-1000 (F+M)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Infoday on SWAFS Calls - H2020 16 January 2020 more than 40 participants (F+M) more than 40 participants (F+M) • Participation in European Research and Innovation Days conference 24-26 September 2019 more than 50 participants (F+M) more than 50 participants (F+M) • Participation in the closing workshop_Project Promotion of the role of Women in the Energy sector in Tunisia 21 November 2019 more than 70 participants (F+M) more than 70 participants (F+M) • Participation in a workshop: Component 4 of Twinning TN-ES "Institutional support for improving the performance of the Tunisian research and innovation system" 16-19 December 2019 more than 15 participants (F+M) more than 15 participants (F+M) • Workshop on "Smart Specialisation in Sfax Region" 3-4 December 2019 more than 40 participants (F+M) more than 40 participants (F+M) • Participation in European Researchers 'Night 27 November 2020 more than 500 participants (F+M) more than 500 participants (F+M) • Participation in international Woman Day 11 March 2022 more than 150 participants (F+M) more than 150 participants (F+M) • "Organisation of R&I PEERS - ANPR Flagship Event • Seminar Gender equality facing the challenges of the R&I ecosystem: The GENDER EQUALITY PLAN of the National Agency for scientific Research Promotion" 30 June 2022 32 F 16 M <p>Communication around the involvement of ANPR in R&I-PEERS project attract significant number of stakeholders involving in GE</p> <p>Potential synergies started to be developed</p>
<p>Gep Strategy</p>	<p>Establishing a Women in Science Excellence Prize (Award)</p>

<u>Implementations</u>	Postponed because of COVID-19
<u>Action</u>	This strategy aims to directly contributes in thr visibility of research and achievements done by women and raising general societal awareness of women contribution to science in the national and regional historical perspective.
<u>Indicators</u>	Excellence prize attributed, Number of Women researchers awarded
<u>Thresholds</u>	Excellence Prize attributed: very satisfactory, Excellence Prize not attributed: unsatisfactory
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Unsatisfactory as Postponed
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishing a social media channel/a brochure/a series of podcasts... promoting achievements of female Tunisian researchers
<u>Implementations</u>	This action directly contributes to better visibility of research and achievements done by women, with the implementation of Page, Group or Channel on Facebook, LinkedIn and Youtube
<u>Indicators</u>	Social media channel is established Number (n) of flyers brochure/a series of podcasts... distributed per year Number (n) of roll-up produced
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when the Social media channel is established Number (n) of flyers brochure/a series of podcasts... distributed per year: Unsatisfactory: $n < 50$ Satisfactory: $50 \leq n < 200$ Very satisfactory: $n \geq 200$ Very satisfactory Number (n) of roll-up produced=1
<u>Results and</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory as social media channel on Facebook, LinkedIn and Youtube have been established and a brochure/a series of podcasts... realized and distributed

<p><u>Comments</u></p>	<p>and 1 rollup produced.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2018, Presentation of RI-PEERS within Horizon 2020 for general public (5000-10000), Radio Intervention : ExpressFm radio antenna (07/03/2018), https://www.facebook.com/RadioExpressFm/videos/1883737914970878/?hc_ref=ARTjEzXELgTNipsGA1WkQg3fFxpvcvE1HI9OA_-mtzH9BIDUM3jyiEaJ5jYx3HfpRfA&fref=gs&dti=142999792906759&hc_location=group • 2019 01 Roll-Up produced, 500 Flyers distributed, Animation of a Desk for RI-PEERS within an exhibition for H2020 tunisian projects in the framework of The conference Tunisian-European Science and Innovation days -TESI, https://drive.google.com/open?id=1CJA3Hp0eiliB2wMF4FT9P3PWToURsf3Y • 2020 Creation of a Facebook public Group: Success Stories of Tunisian Females in Research & Innovation, Success Stories of Tunisian Females in Research & Innovation honors and promotes the achievements of Tunisian Females in Research & Innovation fields, https://www.facebook.com/groups/222521465741488/ • 2021 - • 2022 Youtube Channel launched “Success Stories of Tunisian Females in Research & Innovation”, This action directly contributes to better visibility of research and achievements done by Tunisian female researchers, https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZtP9FOXC-dZB3QkZ3j52fw <p>This activity contributed to improve the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • visibility of the involvement of ANPR in GE • visibility of the development of ANPR’s GEP • promotion of the achievements of Tunisian females researchers
<p><u>GEP Area</u></p>	<p>Work-life balance and organisational culture</p>
<p><u>Gep Strategy</u></p>	<p>Establishing a Committee for equal opportunities</p>
<p><u>Implementations Action</u></p>	<p>This measure aimed to assure continuous and sustainable addressing of issues related to gender equality in ANPR. It also serve as a mediator between employees and Top management in matters related to equal opportunities and contribute to raising awareness of</p>

<u>s</u>	importance of GE and equal treatment.
<u>Indicators</u>	Committee established
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when established:Yes/No
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory. The ANPR Committee for equal opportunities was created on 2020 by decision of the DG of ANPR. Its mission is to assure continuous and sustainable addressing of issues related to gender equality in ANPR. It would also serve as a mediator between employees and Top management in matters related to equal opportunities and contribute to raising awareness of importance of GE and equal treatment
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Analysis of language of ANPR's documents and official communication and detecting areas where the use of gender sensitive language could be improved
<u>Implementations Action s</u>	This strategy aims to provide evidence for actions envisioned to improve use of gender sensitive language and enable detection of most important areas and appropriate strategies. It will also contribute to awareness raising and facilitate their support and engagement
<u>Indicators</u>	Analysis report status
<u>Thresholds</u>	Analysis report not launched: Unsatisfactory Analysis report started: Satisfactory Analysis report realised: Very satisfactory
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Satisfactory as the analysis report started and in progress
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Improvement of official documents and communication practices at ANPR (Toolkit for employees...)
<u>Implementations Action s</u>	The analysis of actual communication practices at ANPR aims to improve practices of official communication and document writing. A toolkit for employees will be produced. This measure would entail engagement of stakeholders in various levels of ANPR's structure and contribute to raising awareness of importance of GE.

<u>Indicators</u>	Training on gender sensitive communication realised New practices Toolkit adopted
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when Training on gender sensitive communication realised and practices toolkit adopted
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Satisfactory as the analysis report started and in progress
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular analysis of Employees needs/requirements (questionnaire)
<u>Implementations Actions</u>	The actions of the strategy aim to engage a large number of stakeholders and provide DMB members with an insight in actual needs of employees.
<u>Indicators</u>	Analysis incorporated into report offering insight into extent of use of available services and presented to DMB
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory for analysis available
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory. The analysis was produced in 2020. It was incorporated into report offering insight into extent of use of available services and presented to DMB. It provides an inclusive approach providing a picture of your Education and qualification, of the Career Path, of the Work organisation, on the Research output in the years 2018 and 2019. It is available at: https://www.ripgep.eu/public_/personalSurvey
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Improving working policies and condition to make them sensitive to special needs of employees and their families
<u>Implementations Actions</u>	Availability of structured supports inside ANPR for employees and their families, such as: pregnant women facilities, flexible working hours, remote working, respect of Ramadan hours, children-friendly facilities, child-care, family-members with special needs, elder family-members...

	<p>These measures would establish a friendly and supportive institutional culture at the ANPR</p> <p>Activities for specific facilities /conditions are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot experiment for increasing the flexible working hours • Establishing a Well-being Space is being installed and equipped
<u>Indicators</u>	Facilities/condition available: Yes, No, In an experimental phase
<u>Thresholds</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very satisfactory: when facilities/conditions are available • Satisfactory: if temporary used in an experimental phase • Unsatisfactory: if not done
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy is Satisfactory as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A pilot experiment for increasing the flexible working hours started on March 23, 2020 for all the personnel within the framework of the general containment because of COVID-19 • A Well-being Space is being installed and equipped. <p>ANPR experimented the flexible hours but now it is incompatible with the legal framework of public administration and it could be necessary the legal framework of public administration will be updated.</p>
<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Yearly statistic indicators of career paths of employees
<u>Implementations</u>	Regular collection of statistical indicators provides an evidence-grounded basis for actions envisioned to increase career advancement opportunities for career employees.
<u>Indicators</u>	Annual statistics report
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory 1 per year
<u>Results and</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as the collected data and statistics were produces in 2020,

<p><u>Comments</u></p>	<p>2021 and 2022. In particular they are available at:</p> <p>2020, https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1TzH8vINE_SYtgRDUDRs9qU59IX35rVDi/edit?usp=sharing&oid=107734444332867647530&rtpof=true&sd=true</p> <p>2021, https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1IK5Ug6q-wcbOIJ3Gz9zIRO8lQbAG702p/edit?usp=sharing&oid=107734444332867647530&rtpof=true&sd=true</p> <p>2022, https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AoCERDGhrqxRmnz-DTFKbdrJ6MXpzm9/view?usp=sharing</p> <p>Presented to decision-making bodies' members, statistic contribute to awareness raising and facilitate their support and engagement.</p>
<p><u>Gep Strategy</u></p>	<p>Gathering regularly gender disaggregated statistics</p>
<p><u>Implementations</u></p>	<p>Disaggregated statistics on committees, councils, commissions and other decision-making bodies (Recruitment, promotion, technical committees, etc.)</p> <p>Regular collection of statistical indicators provides evidence-grounded basis for raising awareness of gender equality within ANPR and helps preventing widening of the gender gap. This strategy would contribute to Integrate the gender dimension into the ANPR culture work and to apply it in daily process.</p>
<p><u>Indicators</u></p>	<p>Availability of statistics</p> <p>Number Men, Number of Women</p>
<p><u>Thresholds</u></p>	<p>Very satisfactory when Data are available each year</p> <p>Very satisfactory when Men<=Women</p> <p>Satisfactory if at least each 2 years there are available statistics.</p>
<p><u>Results and Comments</u></p>	<p>This strategy is Satisfactory, as statistics were done in 2021. Analysis of these data in a dedicated Report so as to monitor gender and diversity state of art in ANPR. Done 2021 this enabled raising awareness to GE. Before each meeting of committees, councils, commissions and other decision-making bodies (Recruitment, promotion, technical committees, etc.), internal members of the Equal opportunities committee check the balanced composition between men and women.</p>

<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organisation and/or participation in events on gender bias in decision making bodies
<u>Implementations</u>	Actions aiming to assure sustainable maintenance of balance in decision-making bodies, raise awareness of biases in decision making practices and foster competence development.
<u>Indicators</u>	<u>Number of HL event organised/participated in per year</u>
<u>Thresholds</u>	Unsatisfactory: Number of HL events per year < 2 Satisfactory: Number of HL events per year=2 Very satisfactory: Number of HL events per year>2
<u>Results and Comments</u>	The strategy was Unsatisfactory, as there were less than 2 events per year. Specifically it is possible to mention: 1) Participation in a HL meeting organized with representatives of Ministry of Women, and the 2) Participation in a HL Workshop: GE dimension is integrated in the National Development plan, strengthens the establishment of policies for equal opportunities with proposals and/or influencing public policies
<u>GEP Area</u>	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Establishing channels to report anonymously disrespectful behavior, abuse and sexual harassment
<u>Implementations</u>	Following the response to a survey, 63% of respondents find this measure important. these measures should be realized in the framework of activities of the group for equal opportunities
<u>Indicators</u>	Channel established

<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory when the channel established and functional
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy was Very satisfactory as a physical mailbox was set up to report anonymously disrespectful behavior, abuse and sexual harassment. It is accessible to all the employees. Therefore a channel for reporting is established and is functional

GSDFPGE's GEP

<u>GEP Area</u>	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular organisation/attendance of training seminars for GSDFPGE staff covering several general GE aspects (including use of non-sexist language-Guide, raising awareness of gender perspective in research content for GSDFPGE staff involved in evaluation of research proposals)
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>8 seminars</p> <p>Participation of GSDFPGE staff in the Conference to inform about the Annual Report of Implementation of Gender Equality Policies within the Public Sector.</p> <p>Participation of GSDFPGE staff in the Conference of EMPOWER Project on empowering refugee communities to prevent gender-based violence in Greece (Participation: 15 employees)</p> <p>Participation of the GSDFPGE staff in the Conference of the Gender Public Debate Project, about recognizing and fighting sexism in public debate, mass media and journalism</p> <p>Participation of the GSDFPGE staff in the Conference of the SHARE Project, that awarded 18 businesses with the Gender Equality Label for promoting gender equality and work-life balance policies in th workplace</p> <p>Participation of GSDFPGE staff in the seminar titled "Labour perspectives in the workplace" organised by the National School for Public Administration (EKDAA)</p> <p>Participation of GSDFPGE staff in the seminar titled "Preventing and tackling violence against women" organised by the National School for Public Administration (EKDAA)</p> <p>Participation of GSDFPGE staff in the seminar titled "Aspects of gender violence: the trafficking phenomenon" organised by the National School for Public Administration (EKDAA)</p> <p>Participation of GSDFPGE staff in the "Equality and Inclusion in Businesses" Conference organised by Women on Top</p>

<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Number of realized seminars per year</p> <p>Number of participants per seminar</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: 0 seminars x year</p> <p>Satisfactory: 1 seminars x year</p> <p>Very satisfactory: >1 seminars x year</p> <p>from 2019 to 2020 thresholds x N of participants are</p> <p>Unsatisfactory<20 participants</p> <p>20<=Satisfactory<30 participants</p> <p>Very satisfactory>=30 participants</p> <p>from 2021: Unsatisfactory: <7 participants</p> <p>Satisfactory: 7-10 participants</p> <p>Very satisfactory: >10 participants</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Satisfactory in 2019, 2020 and 2021 with the organisation of one seminar per year, and Very satisfactory in 2022 with the organisation of 5 seminars.</p> <p>The seminar organised in 2019 had 40 attendees (Very satisfactory), the seminar held in 2020 had 15 participants, and therefore it received a participation that is unsatisfactory, but it was also the period of maximum pitch for COVID 19 pandemic, and for this reason we believe that is in any case satisfactory due to the unexpected crisis. The participation of 30 people to the seminar in 2021 makes it very satisfactory. Finally, the participation to the seminars in 2022 involved different number of people.: 1 seminar was Very satisfactory in terms of number of participant, one was Satisfactory and three were not satisfactory. This suggests us also that organising seminars is important, but it is also important to maintain a balance with respect to the time availability from people. In the seminars of 2022 the number of participant can also be lower due to the specificity of the topics addressed, which is interesting only for some people with specific competences (increasing the specificity decreases the number of participants..</p> <p>This kind of strategy can reach better results with respect to the past once the COVID19 pandemic emergency is overcome.</p>

<p><u>Gep Strategy</u></p>	<p>Analysis of language of GSDFPGE’s documents and official communication and detecting discrepancies with language use suggested in the guidelines developed by GSGE</p>
<p><u>Implements Actions</u></p>	<p>35 documents and official communication analysed:</p> <p>Document 1 Participation of the Secretary General of Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, in the event of the National Council of Greek Women in memory of Virginia Tsouderos</p> <p>Document 2 A day after International Women's Day...</p> <p>Document 3 Successful completion of the GSGE Conference on Social and Solidarity Economy as a Keystone for the Development of Gender Equality</p> <p>Document 4 GSGE Library: Women and Disability Announcement/Invitation to Event</p> <p>Document 5 GSGE Observatory - E-bulletin No 21 - Results of Local Government Elections and European Elections 2019</p> <p>Document 6 Printed collection of awarded works from GSGE's pan-Hellenic students' creative writing competition 2019</p> <p>Document 7 Letter from the Deputy Minister of the Interior in charge of gender equality issues to public sector bodies on "Inclusion of the gender dimension in administrative documents"</p> <p>Document 8 GSGE Observatory - E-bulletin No 20 - European Ballot Quota 2019</p> <p>Document 9 Graffiti on Gender Equality in 3 schools in Galatsi</p> <p>Document 10 Digital Movie Competition Results 'Gender in the foreground'</p> <p>Document 11 Successful Completion of the 3rd Tribute '50-50 Equality in Cinema Too'</p> <p>Document 12 Two-day conference - educational action on "Gender discrimination, gender identity and sexuality: Inclusive education as a policy to prevent school exclusion"</p> <p>Document 13 GSGE Observatory E-bulletin No22 – Women’s Entrepreneurship</p> <p>Document 14 Breast Cancer: A Battle Worth Winning</p> <p>Document 15 GSGE Library's Participation in the 'Month for Adolescence' of Patakis publications</p> <p>Document 16 Book presentation: "Entrepreneurship and Social Economy: Gender Perspective" - Thursday, October 24, 2019</p>

- Document 17 GSGE Observatory - E-Bulletin No 23 - Gender-Based Violence
- Document 18 GSGE's Support to the study of the ICAP Group for 2019 on women's entrepreneurship in our country '
- Document 19 Meeting on 'Women in the labour market: Challenges and Opportunities'
- Document 20 Digital Pension Calculator-PEGASUS Project
- Document 21 Conference of the Council of Europe's Finnish Presidency on 'Dealing with Gender Stereotypes and Sexism'
- Document 22 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, F. Kouvela, in the Ag. Paraskevi Municipality Event on Trafficking
- Document 23 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, in the event organised by the Greek Delegation to the European Women's Lobby on '50-50 Women for Europe - Europe for Women'
- Document 24 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, in the 4th Panhellenic Conference of Women in the Police-Force
- Document 25 3-day Film Festival "Equality Movierama 2019" GSGE 17 / 4-19 / 4
- Document 26 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, in the Meeting organised by the Ombudsman for the Rights of the Child
- Document 27 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, F. Kouvela, in the conference organised by the Institute of Educational Policy on 'Education in Democracy - Democracy in Education'
- Document 28 Enhancing Women's Participation in Public Dialogue - Launch of GENDER_PUBLIC DEBATE Project
- Document 29 Digital Movie Competition Results 'Gender in the foreground'
- Document 30 Statement by the Secretary General for Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, on the appointment of women at the Supreme Court leadership
- Document 31 The EMPOWER_REF Project
- Document 32 Application form for granting disability pension (issued by the EFKA-Social Security Fund)
- Document 33 Mandatory employee declaration documents for employers (issued by the Ministry for Labour and Social Affairs)
- Document 34 Form of Consent-Personal Affirmation for the Housing Benefit Program

	<p>(issued by the General Secretariat for Social Solidarity/Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs)</p> <p>Document 35 Competence transfer by the Minister for Labour and Social Affairs to Ministry bodies</p>
Indicators	Number of documents analysed
Thresholds	<p>Unsatisfactory: <25 documents/communication</p> <p>Satisfactory: =25-30 documents/communication</p> <p>Very satisfactory: >30 documents/communication</p>
Results and Comments	<p>This activity already closed in 2019 was Very satisfactory with 35 documents and official communication were analysed</p> <p>Document 1 Participation of the Secretary General of Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, in the event of the National Council of Greek Women in memory of Virginia Tsouderos, http://www.isotita.gr/?s=%CE%92%CE%B9%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%BD%CE%AF%CE%B1+%CE%A4%CF%83%CE%BF%CF%85%CE%B4%CE%B5%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%8D</p> <p>Document 2 A day after International Women's Day..., http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%bc%ce%b9%ce%b1-%ce%bc%ce%ad%cf%81%ce%b1-%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%84%ce%ac-%cf%84%ce%b7%ce%bd-%cf%80%ce%b1%ce%b3%ce%ba%cf%8c%cf%83%ce%bc/</p> <p>Document 3 Successful completion of the GSGE Conference on Social and Solidarity Economy as a Keystone for the Development of Gender Equality, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b7-%ce%b5%cf%80%ce%b9%cf%84%cf%85%cf%87%ce%ae%cf%82-%ce%bf%ce%bb%ce%bf%ce%ba%ce%bb%ce%ae%cf%81%cf%89%cf%83%ce%b7-%cf%84%ce%b7-5/</p> <p>Document 4 GSGE Library: Women and Disability Announcement/Invitation to Event, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b5%ce%ba%ce%b4%ce%ae%ce%bb%cf%89%cf%83%ce%b7-%ce%b3%cf%85%ce%bd%ce%b1%ce%af%ce%ba%ce%b5%cf%82-%ce%ba%ce%b1%ce%b9-%ce%b1%ce%bd%ce%b1%cf%80%ce%b7%cf%81%ce%af%ce%b1/</p> <p>Document 5 GSGE Observatory - E-bulletin No 21 - Results of Local Government Elections and European Elections 2019,</p>

	<p>http://www.isotita.gr/%cf%80%ce%b1%cf%81%ce%b1%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%81%ce%b7%cf%84%ce%ae%cf%81%ce%b9%ce%bf-%ce%b3-%ce%b3-%ce%b9-%cf%86-21%ce%bf-%ce%b5%ce%bd%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%81%cf%89%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%ba%cf%8c-%cf%83%ce%b7/</p> <p>Document 6 Printed collection of awarded works from GSGE's pan-Hellenic students' creative writing competition 2019, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%bd%ce%ad%ce%b1-%ce%ad%ce%ba%ce%b4%ce%bf%cf%83%ce%b7-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b3-%ce%b3-%ce%b9-%cf%86-%ce%bc%ce%b5-%cf%84%ce%b1-%ce%b2%cf%81%ce%b1%ce%b2%ce%b5%cf%85%ce%b8%ce%ad%ce%bd%cf%84%ce%b1/</p> <p>Document 7 Letter from the Deputy Minister of the Interior in charge of gender equality issues to public sector bodies on "Inclusion of the gender dimension in administrative documents, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b5%cf%80%ce%b9%cf%83%cf%84%ce%bf%ce%bb%ce%ae-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%cf%80%ce%bf%ce%bb%ce%b9%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%ba%ce%ae%cf%82-%ce%b7%ce%b3%ce%b5%cf%83%ce%af%ce%b1%cf%82-%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%85-%cf%85%cf%80/</p> <p>Document 8 GSGE Observatory - E-bulletin No 20 - European Ballot Quota 2019, http://www.isotita.gr/%cf%80%ce%b1%cf%81%ce%b1%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%81%ce%b7%cf%84%ce%ae%cf%81%ce%b9%ce%bf-%ce%b3-%ce%b3-%ce%b9-%cf%86-20%ce%bf-%ce%b5%ce%bd%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%81%cf%89%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%ba%cf%8c-%cf%83/</p> <p>Document 9 Graffiti on Gender Equality in 3 schools in Galatsi, http://www.isotita.gr/graffiti-%ce%b3%ce%b9%ce%b1-%cf%84%ce%b7%ce%bd-%ce%b9%cf%83%cf%8c%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%84%ce%b1-%cf%84%cf%89%ce%bd-%cf%86%cf%8d%ce%bb%cf%89%ce%bd-%cf%83%ce%b5-3-%cf%83%cf%87%ce%bf%ce%bb%ce%b5%ce%af%ce%b1/</p> <p>Document 10 Digital Movie Competition Results 'Gender in the foreground', http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%85%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b1%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%84%ce%b5%ce%bb%ce%ad%cf%83%ce%bc%ce%b1%cf%84%ce%b1-%ce%b4%ce%b9%ce%b1%ce%b3%cf%89%ce%bd%ce%b9%cf%83%ce%bc/</p> <p>Document 11 Successful Completion of the 3rd Tribute '50-50 Equality in Cinema Too', http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%bf%ce%bb%ce%bf%ce%ba%ce%bb%ce%b7%cf%81%cf%8e%ce%b8%ce%b7%ce%b</p>
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	<p>a%ce%b5-%ce%bc%ce%b5-%ce%b5%cf%80%ce%b9%cf%84%cf%85%cf%87%ce%af-7/ Document 12 Two-day conference - educational action on "Gender discrimination, gender identity and sexuality: Inclusive education as a policy to prevent school exclusion", http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b5%cf%80%ce%b9%cf%83%cf%84%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%bf%ce%bd%ce%b9%ce%ba%ce%ae-%ce%b4%ce%b9%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%81%ce%af%ce%b4%ce%b1-%ce%b5%ce%ba%cf%80%ce%b1%ce%b9%ce%b4%ce%b5%cf%85%cf%84%ce%b9/</p> <p>Document 13 GSGE Observatory E-bulletin No22 – Women’s Entrepreneurship, http://www.isotita.gr/%cf%80%ce%b1%cf%81%ce%b1%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%81%ce%b7%cf%84%ce%ae%cf%81%ce%b9%ce%bf-%ce%b3%ce%b3%ce%bf%cf%80%ce%b9%cf%86-22o-%ce%b5%ce%bd%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%81%cf%89%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%ba%cf%8c-%cf%83/</p> <p>Document 14 Breast Cancer: A Battle Worth Winning, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%ba%ce%b1%cf%81%ce%ba%ce%af%ce%bd%ce%bf%cf%82-%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%bc%ce%b1%cf%83%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%8d-%ce%bc%ce%af%ce%b1-%ce%bc%ce%ac%cf%87%ce%b7-%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b1%ce%be%ce%af%ce%b6%ce%b5/</p> <p>Document 15 GSGE Library's Participation in the 'Month for Adolescence' of Patakis publications, http://www.isotita.gr/%cf%83%cf%85%ce%bc%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%87%ce%ae-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b2%ce%b9%ce%b2%ce%bb%ce%b9%ce%bf%ce%b8%ce%ae%ce%ba%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b8%ce%b5%ce%bc%ce%ac%cf%84%cf%89%ce%bd-%ce%b9%cf%83/</p> <p>Document 16 Book presentation: "Entrepreneurship and Social Economy: Gender Perspective" - Thursday, October 24, 2019, http://www.isotita.gr/%cf%80%ce%b1%cf%81%ce%bf%cf%85%cf%83%ce%af%ce%b1%cf%83%ce%b7-%ce%b2%ce%b9%ce%b2%ce%bb%ce%af%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b5%cf%80%ce%b9%cf%87%ce%b5%ce%b9%cf%81%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b1%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%ba%cf%8c%cf%84/</p> <p>Document 17 GSGE Observatory - E-Bulletin No 23 - Gender-Based Violence, http://www.isotita.gr/%cf%80%ce%b1%cf%81%ce%b1%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%81%ce%b7%cf%84%ce%ae%cf%81%ce%b9%ce%bf-%ce%b3%ce%b3%ce%bf%cf%80%ce%b9%cf%86-23o-%ce%b5%ce%bd%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%81%cf%89%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%ba%cf%8c-%cf%83/</p> <p>Document 18 GSGE's Support to the study of the ICAP Group for 2019 on</p>
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	<p>women's entrepreneurship in our country , http://www.isotita.gr/%cf%85%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%83%cf%84%ce%ae%cf%81%ce%b9%ce%be%ce%b7-%ce%b1%cf%80%cf%8c-%cf%84%ce%b7-%ce%b3-%ce%b3-%ce%bf-%cf%80-%ce%b9-%cf%86-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%bc%ce%b5%ce%bb%ce%ad%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82/</p> <p>Document 19 Meeting on 'Women in the labour market: Challenges and Opportunities, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%81%ce%af%ce%b4%ce%b1-%ce%bc%ce%b5-%ce%b8%ce%ad%ce%bc%ce%b1-%ce%b3%cf%85%ce%bd%ce%b1%ce%af%ce%ba%ce%b5%cf%82-%cf%83%cf%84%ce%b7%ce%bd-%ce%b1%ce%b3%ce%bf%cf%81%ce%ac-%ce%b5%cf%81/</p> <p>Document 20 Digital Pension Calculator-PEGASUS Project, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%cf%88%ce%b7%cf%86%ce%b9%ce%b1%ce%ba%cf%8c%cf%82-%cf%85%cf%80%ce%bf%ce%bb%ce%bf%ce%b3%ce%b9%cf%83%cf%84%ce%ae%cf%82-%cf%83%cf%85/</p> <p>Document 21 Conference of the Council of Europe's Finnish Presidency on 'Dealing with Gender Stereotypes and Sexism, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%cf%83%cf%85%ce%bd%ce%ad%ce%b4%cf%81%ce%b9%ce%bf-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%cf%86%ce%b9%ce%bd%ce%bb%ce%b1%ce%bd%ce%b4%ce%b9%ce%ba%ce%ae/</p> <p>Document 22 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, F. Kouvela, in the Ag. Paraskevi Municipality Event on Trafficking, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b7-%cf%83%cf%85%ce%bc%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%87%ce%ae-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b3%ce%b3%ce%b9%cf%86-%cf%86-%ce%ba%ce%bf-2/</p> <p>Document 23 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, in the event organised by the Greek Delegation to the European Women's Lobby on '50-50 Women for Europe - Europe for Women, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b7-%cf%83%cf%85%ce%bc%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%87%ce%ae-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b3%ce%b3%ce%b9%cf%86-%cf%86%cf%89%cf%84-9/</p> <p>Document 24 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, Fotini</p>
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Kouvela, in the 4th Panhellenic Conference of Women in the Police-Force, <http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b7-%cf%83%cf%85%ce%bc%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%87%ce%ae-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b3%ce%b3%ce%b9%cf%86-%cf%86%cf%89%cf%84-10/>

Document 25 3-day Film Festival "Equality Movierama 2019" GSGE 17 / 4-19 / 4, <http://www.isotita.gr/3%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%81%ce%bf-%cf%86%ce%b5%cf%83%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%b2%ce%ac%ce%bb-%cf%84%ce%b1%ce%b9%ce%bd%ce%b9%cf%8e%ce%bd-%ce%b3%ce%b3%ce%b9%cf%86-17-4-19-4/>

Document 26 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, in the Meeting organised by the Ombudsman for the Rights of the Child, <http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b7-%cf%83%cf%85%ce%bc%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%87%ce%ae-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b3%ce%b3%ce%b9%cf%86-%cf%86-%ce%ba%ce%bf-3/>

Document 27 Participation of the Secretary General for Gender Equality, F. Kouvela, in the conference organised by the Institute of Educational Policy on 'Education in Democracy - Democracy in Education', <http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b7-%cf%83%cf%85%ce%bc%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%87%ce%ae-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b3%ce%b3%ce%b9%cf%86-%cf%86-%ce%ba%ce%bf-4/>

Document 28 Enhancing Women's Participation in Public Dialogue - Launch of GENDER_PUBLIC DEBATE Project, <http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b5%ce%bd%ce%b9%cf%83%cf%87%cf%8d%ce%bf%ce%bd%cf%84%ce%b1%cf%82-%cf%84%ce%b7-%cf%83%cf%85%ce%bc%ce%bc%ce%b5%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%87/>

Document 29 Digital Movie Competition Results 'Gender in the foreground', <http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%85%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b1%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%84%ce%b5%ce%bb%ce%ad%cf%83%ce%bc%ce%b1%cf%84%ce%b1-%ce%b4%ce%b9%ce%b1%ce%b3%cf%89%ce%bd%ce%b9%cf%83%ce%bc/>

Document 30 Statement by the Secretary General for Gender Equality, Fotini Kouvela, on the appointment of women at the Supreme Court leadership, <http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b4%ce%ae%ce%bb%cf%89%cf%83%ce%b7-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82->

	<p>%ce%b3%ce%b5%ce%bd%ce%b9%ce%ba%ce%ae%cf%82-%ce%b3%cf%81%ce%b1%ce%bc%ce%bc-4/</p> <p>Document 31 The EMPOWER_REF Project, http://www.isotita.gr/%ce%ad%cf%81%ce%b3%ce%bf-empower_ref/</p> <p>Document 32 Application form for granting disability pension (issued by the EFKA-Social Security Fund), https://www.efka.gov.gr/el/aitese-gia-aponome-syntaxes-logo-anaperias</p> <p>Document 33 Mandatory employee declaration documents for employers (issued by the Ministry for Labour and Social Affairs), http://www.et.gr/idocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e18iAcc4jHg5cOG6fR5bbOSK8rzSZFgk-XLICQIaWE9-kAYi3ORfmaqBqLOWPE7pe06RUkAPcmIq75h8iB-tM3_vKMSuwFT8g8jMbcMCubIFfxINP8qam0ZL3IV_fUMieqc5U07tzUlrGqj8X3ScOlrWqmaa64z4w..</p> <p>Document 34 Form of Consent-Personal Affirmation for the Housing Benefit Program (issued by the General Secretariat for Social Solidarity/Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs), https://www.epidomastegasis.gr/pub/Content/Documents/common/HBConsentForm.pdf</p> <p>Document 35 Competence transfer by the Minister for Labour and Social Affairs to Ministry bodies, http://www.et.gr/idocs-nph/pdfimageSummaryviewer.html?args=sppFfdN7IQP5_cc--m0e1waP6hGUu9diMTTvwQOUtba8rzSZFgk-XLICQIaWE9-kAYi3ORfmaqE-6i6XIV_NbZnzNAc97U875h8iB-tM3_vKMSuwFT8g8jMbcMCubIFfxINP8qam0bdXXP-D0sjyLAuzWCVw-eJOzK971ANQryEvdSQpZa6nQ..</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Development and implementation of gender sensitive models in communication practices and specific set of documents in GSDFPGE
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Development and implementation of 7 different gender sensitive models</p> <p>Titles of the models</p> <p>Ministerial decision (published by the Ministry of Labour)</p> <p>Press release</p> <p>Form of Consent-Personal Affirmation for the Housing Benefit Program (issued by the General Secretariat for Social Solidarity/Ministry of Labour)</p>

	<p>Leave application form by staff to administration</p> <p>E-bulletin of the GSDFPGE's Observatory</p> <p>Mandatory employee declaration documents for employers to the ERGANI e-system (published by the Ministry of Labour)</p> <p>Application form for granting disability pension (issued by the EFKA-Social Security Fund)</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Documents updated/models and communicated
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: no development of a model</p> <p>Satisfactory: Development and implementation of a model within the GSGE</p> <p>Very satisfactory: Development and implementation of a model within the GSGE and communication to public body services, Universities and research institutions.</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory, as the models has been implemented within the GSGE and communication has been carried out
<u>GEP Area</u>	Work-life balance and organisational culture
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Institutionalizing “an open day” for parents to bring their kids to the office once or twice a year
<u>Implements Actions</u>	An open day was introduced on December 2019, for Christmas.
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of days “institutionalised” per year (1 step)
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: 0</p> <p>Satisfactor: 1-2</p> <p>Very satisfactory: >2</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Satisfactory in 2019, and unsatisfactory in the remaining years, as the last open day was organised in 2019. This result is also due to the COVID 19 pandemic. Indeed, it was not possible to organise that kind of event that needs to be in presence. For this reason, we consider as suspended this activity that will start again.</p> <p>During the only event that was organised 23 of December 2019 fathers were encouraged for the first time to bring their kids for this “open day”.</p>

<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Introducing the possibility of flexible working hours
<u>Implements Actions</u>	There was preliminary action to introduce the strategy, but there was the problem of a need of law introduction due to our public character. Meetings were realized with the political hierarchy of the Ministry, but other meetings and actions need
<u>Indicators</u>	Establishment of flexible working hours.
<u>Thresholds</u>	Unsatisfactory: no introduction Satisfactory: introduction only for mothers Very satisfactory: introduction for both parents
<u>Results and Comments</u>	The indicator related to this strategy is Satisfactory as the organisation started some internal steps even if this is something also connected to external factors. Currently there is a plan to have an official solution for all public sector. A culture of flexibility in working hours for fathers and mothers was well established in the GSDFPGE, there is still a need for legislation in order for that to be a formal part of a GEP.
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Introducing the possibility of telework
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Telework introduced due to COVID 19
<u>Indicators</u>	Establishment of telework.
<u>Thresholds</u>	Unsatisfactory: no introduction Satisfactory: introduction only for mothers Very satisfactory: introduction for both parents
<u>Results and Comments</u>	Satisfactory, considering that it has been introduced but only in view of COVID 19 pandemic. Indeed, till 2021 the measure has been introduced urgently due to the COVID-19 crisis, and not with a work-life balance strategy and criteria.
<u>Gep</u>	Including relevant information on national work-life balance related legislation to the

<u>Strategy</u>	GSDFPGE's website
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>-Till 2021 material on work-life balance legislation, to be posted on the website was collected as relevant legislation was fragmented and clustered.</p> <p>-8 posts on legislation-related information for businesses</p> <p>-4 posts on national work-life balance legislation-related information</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of Posts
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: <2</p> <p>Satisfactory: =2-3</p> <p>Very satisfactory: >3</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This strategy was Very satisfactory as 12 posts were included in the website.</p> <p>LEGISLATION-RELATED INFORMATION FOR BUSINESSES</p> <p>Is flexibility a solution for work-related burn-out?, https://share.isotita.gr/evelixia-burn-out/</p> <p>Can tele-work become a tool for more equality?, https://share.isotita.gr/borei-i-tilergasia-na-ginei-ergaleio-gia-megalyteri-isotita/</p> <p>Is it a luxury to discuss on equality in businesses?, https://share.isotita.gr/einai-polyteleia-i-syzitisi-gia-tin-isotita-stis-epicheiriseis/</p> <p>How can we support working parents during the pandemic?, https://share.isotita.gr/pos-boroume-na-ypostirixoume-tous-ergazomenous-goneis-sti-diarkeia-tis-pandimias/</p> <p>What fathers do at home affects what mothers do at work, https://share.isotita.gr/isokatanomi-efthinon-frontidas/</p> <p>The benefits of paternity leave to the development of children and the family, https://share.isotita.gr/ofeli-adeias-patrotitas/</p> <p>"Paternity leave has turned me from a spectator to a co-protagonist of our family life", https://share.isotita.gr/i-adeia-patrotitas-me-ekane-apo-theati-sybrotagonisti-tis-oikogeneiakis-mas-zois/</p> <p>A key-role for equality and how to fill it, https://share.isotita.gr/enas-rolos-kleidi-gia-tin-isotita-kai-pos-na-ton-kalypsete/</p> <p>GENERAL LEGISLATION-RELATED INFORMATION</p>

	<p>Law 4604/2019 on substantial gender equality (government gazette), https://isotita.gr/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/N.4604-για-την-Ουσιαστική-Ισότητα-των-Φύλων.pdf</p> <p>Press release on Law 4604/2019 on substantial gender equality, https://isotita.gr/δημοσίευση-σε-φεκ-του-νόμου-4604-για-την-πρ/</p> <p>Circular on Law 4604/2019 on substantial gender equality, https://isotita.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Εγκύκλιος-για-τον-N.-4604-2019.pdf</p> <p>Law 4808/2020 [...] Integration of EU Directive 2019/1158 on work-life balance (government gazette), https://isotita.gr/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/N.4808.2021.pdf</p>
<u>GEP Area</u>	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Regular data collection and statistic reports on demographic structure with data disaggregated according to gender and position
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Reports each year
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of reports x Year % Women in senior/decision making positions
<u>Thresholds</u>	Very satisfactory 1 per year Unsatisfactory: % Women <50% Satisfactory: % Women = 50% Very satisfactory: % Women >50%
<u>Results and Comments</u>	This strategy is Very satisfactory as reports were done in 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 Moreover, the percentage of women in senior/decision making positions was > 50% each year, with a tendency to reach a balance in the last years as: 2019: 90% 2020: 90% 2021: 83%

	2022: 77%
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Organisation / attendance of seminars for employees to improve the skills relevant for their career advancement)
<u>Implements Actions</u>	<p>Disaggregated statistics on committees, councils, commissions and other decision-making 8 certified seminars Seminar 1: Public administration and vulnerable social groups. Quality of care</p> <p>Seminar 2: Health and safety in the workplace in the public sector</p> <p>Seminar 3: Financial management: auditing and payment of expenditure in central public administration</p> <p>Seminar 4: Corporate social responsibility and public administration</p> <p>Seminar 5: Principles of organisation and operation of the social welfare system</p> <p>Seminar 6: Public Administration and vulnerable social groups. Quality of care</p> <p>Seminar 7: Public procurement and general services contract awarding and execution</p> <p>Seminar 8: Developing intercultural skills and managing diversity</p>
<u>Indicators</u>	<p>Number of seminars per year</p> <p>Number of participants per seminar</p>
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: <2 seminars per year</p> <p>Satisfactory: =2 seminars per year</p> <p>Very satisfactory: >2 seminars per year</p> <p>Unsatisfactory: participants <4</p> <p>Satisfactory: 4<= participants <7</p> <p>Very satisfactory: >=7 participants</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>This Strategy was Very satisfactory in 2019 and 2021, as 3 seminars per Year were attended, while it seems unsatisfactory for 2020 and 2022. However, 2020 was impacted by COVID 19 crisis, while 2022 is not concluded.</p> <p>One seminar only in 2019 was Satisfactory in terms of participants (4). However, it is necessary to underline that the seminars had specific topics, and can involve different</p>

	<p>professional profiles reducing the number of participants to specific seminars. Moreover, the pandemic period impacted the activity.</p> <p>Therefore, this activity as a whole can be considered Satisfactory as 13 female employees and 5 male employees participated in a total of 8 certified seminars after achieving official collaboration with National School for Public Administration.</p>
<u>Gep Strategy</u>	Introducing mechanisms to facilitate leaves for education and research (e.g. sabbatical, nonpaid leave, fellowship abroad)
<u>Implements Actions</u>	Educational leave, fellowship abroad
<u>Indicators</u>	Number of beneficiaries per year, by gender
<u>Thresholds</u>	<p>Unsatisfactory: Female=0, Male=0</p> <p>Satisfactory: $1 \leq \text{Female} < 3$ $1 \leq \text{Male} < 3$</p> <p>Very satisfactory: Female ≥ 3, Male ≥ 3</p>
<u>Results and Comments</u>	<p>2019:</p> <p>1 female educational leave</p> <p>1 fellowship abroad</p> <p>2020:</p> <p>1 more educational leave Female</p> <p>2021:</p> <p>1 more educational leave Female</p> <p>This strategy is Very satisfactory when in 2021 five females used educational leave of fellowship abroad. However it is unbalanced by gender. This kind of strategy can have an improvement once the pich of COVID 19 pandemic will be overcome.</p>